

შოთა რუსთაველის ეროვნული
სამეცნიერო ფონდი
SHOTA RUSTAVELI NATIONAL
SCIENCE FOUNDATION

20
24

STATISTICAL SURVEY ON FUNCTIONING
AND FOUNDATIONAL LEARNING SKILLS OF CHILDREN
LIVING IN GEORGIAN HOUSEHOLDS

**Giorgi Mikeladze, Nestan Pantsulaia, Ana Varamashvili,
Mariam Okruashvili**

**Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills
of Children Living in Georgian Households**

(Survey Findings Report)

Publishing House **“UNIVERSAL”**

Tbilisi 2026

The authors wish to thank Ivane Javakhishvili Tbilisi State University, Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation of Georgia, the survey team, “LLC BCG”, and the participating households for their time and cooperation.

Scientific Editor: Professor Simon Gelashvili,
Ivane Javakhishvili Tbilisi State University

Reviewers: Associate Professor Nino Abesadze,
Ivane Javakhishvili Tbilisi State University

Assistant-Professor Ivane Kechakmadze,
Ilia State University

This work was supported by Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation of Georgia (SRNSFG) Project №FR-22-25281

© Giorgi Mikeladze, Nestan Pantsulaia, Ana Varamashvili, Mariam Okruashvili, 2026

Publishing House “UNIVERSAL”, 2026

4,A. Politkovskaia st., 0186, Tbilisi, Georgia ☎: 5(99) 17 22 30; 5(99) 33 52 02

E-mail: universal505@ymail.com; gamomcemlobauniversal@gmail.com

ISBN 978-9941-529-71-9

TABLE OF CONTENTS

TABLE OF CONTENTS.....	3
1. Introduction	5
2. Survey methodology.....	6
2.1 Sample design	6
2.2 Questionnaires.....	7
2.3 Ethical protocol	7
2.4 Data collection method.....	8
2.5 Training	8
2.6 Fieldwork quality control measures	8
2.7 Data management, editing and analysis	8
2.8 How to read the tables.....	9
3. Indicators and definitions	10
4. Sample coverage and characteristics of respondents.....	14
4.1 Results of interviews	14
Table SR.1.1: Results of household and children age 7-14's interviews.....	15
4.2 Housing and household characteristics	16
Table SR.2.1: Housing characteristics.....	17
Table SR.2.2: Household and personal assets	18
Table SR.2.3: Wealth quintiles.....	19
4.3 Household composition.....	20
Table SR.3.1: Household composition.....	21
4.4 Age structure of household population	23
Table SR.4.1: Age distribution of household population by sex.....	23
4.5 Background characteristics of children aged 7-14 years.....	24
Table SR.5.3: Children age 7-14 years' background characteristics	24
4.6 ICT	26
Table SR.9.2: Household ownership of ICT equipment and access to internet.....	27
4.7 Children's living arrangements.....	29
Table SR.11.1: Children's living arrangements and orphanhood.....	30
Table SR.11.2: Children's living arrangements and co-residence with parents	32
Table SR.11.3: Children not in parental care	34
5. Learn.....	37
5.1 Kindergarten.....	37
Table LN.1.1: Kindergarten.....	38
Table LN.1.2: Participation rate in organised learning	39
5.2 Attendance.....	40

Table LN.2.1: School readiness.....	41
Table LN.2.2: Primary school entry	42
Table LN.2.3: Primary school attendance and out of school children	43
Table LN.2.4: Lower secondary school attendance and out of school adolescents	45
Table LN.2.5: Age for grade	46
Table LN.2.6: Upper secondary school attendance and out of school youth	48
Table LN.2.7: Gross intake, completion and effective transition rates	50
Table LN.2.8: Parity indices.....	52
5.3 Parental involvement.....	54
Table LN.3.1: Support for child learning at school.....	55
Table LN.3.2: School-related reasons for inability to attend class.....	59
Table LN.3.3: Learning environment at home	62
5.4 Foundational learning skills	65
Table LN.4.1: Foundational reading skills	66
Table LN.4.2: Foundational numeracy skills	73
6. Protected from Violence and Exploitation	79
6.1 Child discipline	79
Table PR.2.1: Child discipline.....	80
Table PR.2.2: Attitudes toward physical punishment	81
7. Equitable Chance in Life	82
7.1 Child functioning.....	82
Table EQ.1.2: Child functioning (children age 7-14 years)	83
Table EQ.1.3: Use of assistive devices (children age 7-14 years)	86
Appendices.....	87
Appendix A - List of personnel involved in the survey	87
Appendix B - Questionnaires Used in the Survey	88
Demographic Questionnaire	88
Household Questionnaire	93
Main Questionnaire	99
FL module booklet.....	126
Refusal Sheet.....	149

1. Introduction

In 2024, a national statistical survey was conducted to assess the wellbeing, functioning, and foundational learning skills of children living in Georgian households.

The survey was implemented on the scientific basis of Ivane Javakhishvili Tbilisi State University, with financial support from the Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation, specifically, the statistical survey was implemented with the support of the Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation of Georgia (SRNSFG) project No. FR-22-25281.

The project's objective was to conduct a statistical survey on the functioning and foundational learning skills of children living in Georgian households. The project envisioned implementing a statistical survey and obtaining representative data at the national level, given the small budget of the scientific grant.

The survey methodology is based on the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) and Eurostat's methodology for calculating living standards indicators. Within the framework of the survey, the Washington Group on Disability Statistics short version of questions on functional difficulties, UNICEF's methodology for assessing foundational learning skills, and Eurostat's methodology for calculating living standards indicators were used.

The survey methodology is based on the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), International Telecommunication Union (ITU), and Eurostat's methodology for calculating living standards indicators. Within the framework of the survey, the Washington Group on Disability Statistics short version of questions on functional difficulties, UNICEF's methodology for assessing foundational learning skills, and Eurostat's methodology for calculating living standards indicators were used. The International Telecommunication Union (ITU) methodology was used to assess Information and Communication Technology (ICT) indicators. This study establishes the housing overcrowding indicator for Georgia for the first time and simultaneously reports such important indicators as SDG 4.1.1a and SDG 4.5.1. As a result, the study creates a solid empirical foundation for the formation of evidence-based educational and social policy, ensures access to education, and ensures that children are not left behind in development, functioning, and foundational learning opportunities.

2. Survey methodology

2.1 Sample design

The 2014 General Census database was used as the sampling frame for the survey. Due to the principle of confidentiality, data from the National Statistics Office of Georgia (Geostat) were obtained at the enumeration area level, which included information with indications of area boundaries and streets.

The survey used a stratified three-stage cluster random sampling, where the primary sampling unit is the enumeration area, the secondary unit is the household address, and the tertiary unit is all children aged 7-14 living in the household. The stratification variables are region and settlement type. The sampling covers 21 strata and 193 enumeration areas.

At the first stage of sampling, the number of households to be surveyed (1,200 households) was distributed proportionally to the square root of the size of regions, and within regions by settlement type. Probability Proportional to Size (PPS) method was used for the selection of enumeration areas, while household selection within areas is done systematically. It should be noted that 5 households were surveyed in urban-type areas, while 8 households were surveyed in rural-type areas. For the selection of enumeration areas in strata, the Probability Proportional to Size (PPS) method was used, while for the selection of households in selected areas, the systematic selection method was used. The required number of households was selected in the area using the systematic selection method: 15 in urban-type settlements and 24 in rural-type settlements. The demographic questionnaire was completed in all selected households, while household and main questionnaires were completed in 5 households in urban-type settlements and 8 households in rural-type settlements. In cases where the indicated addresses were not sufficient for surveying the appropriate number, the required number of households was selected from the last address using a predetermined step (step size: every fifth household). From the updated household database, a total of 3,597 households were selected for the survey.

Given the different ethnic populations living in Georgia, the survey was conducted in several languages. According to the results of Georgia's 2014 General Census, 86.8% of the population living in Georgia belongs to the Georgian, 6.3% to the Azerbaijani, and 4.5% to the Armenian ethnic group, totaling 97.6%. Moreover, the share of representatives of each remaining ethnic group is less than 1%. Thus, the survey was conducted in Georgian, Azerbaijani, and Armenian languages.

2.2 Questionnaires

At the initial stage of the study, the development/adaptation of the survey field instruments and methodology was carried out. Specifically, the survey was conducted using 4 questionnaires: 1) Demographic Questionnaire; 2) Household Questionnaire; 3) Main Questionnaire; and 4) Refusal Sheet. Additionally, instructions for completing questionnaires were created to prepare field personnel. The survey instruments include the following modules: household demographic data; education; childcare; household income; receipt of assistance; living conditions; information about the child (aged 7-14); mother's/caregiver's functioning; child discipline; child functioning; parental involvement; foundational learning skills; and information on non-response.

The survey methodology is based on the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) and Eurostat's methodology for calculating living standards indicators. Within the framework of the survey, the Washington Group on Disability Statistics short version of questions on functional difficulties, UNICEF's methodology for assessing foundational learning skills, and Eurostat's methodology for calculating living standards indicators were used.

At the initial stage of the study, questions and corresponding modules were adapted to obtain information appropriate to Georgia's reality. Specifically, for the adaptation of the foundational learning module, a detailed study was conducted on approved textbooks used in Georgia's education system; accordingly, the foundational learning module is in full compliance with both UN standards and approved textbooks used in Georgia's education system. Additionally, both individual questions and blocks of questions used in the field instruments were adapted.

Following the development and adaptation of the field instruments, they were translated into Azerbaijani and Armenian languages.

2.3 Ethical protocol

Informed consent was obtained from all respondents participating in the study, while in the case of children aged 7-14, written informed consent was obtained from their parents or legal guardians before data collection. Participation in the study was voluntary, and respondents were fully informed about the study's purpose, procedures, confidentiality and anonymity of responses. Additionally, respondents were informed that they had the right not to answer any or specific questions, and could stop the interview at any time.

Data were collected and processed in accordance with internationally recognized ethical standards for research. Respondents' personal identifiers were not collected, and the obtained information was analyzed based on anonymized and aggregated data to ensure confidentiality and data protection.

2.4 Data collection method

Data collection in the study was conducted using the paper-based face-to-face interview (PAPI) method. Interviewers completed standardized questionnaires during household visits, which ensured direct communication with respondents and allowed for verification of data accuracy during the collection process.

2.5 Training

Field personnel training was conducted on February 10-11, and included lectures on interview techniques and questionnaire content, as well as conducting mock interviews among training participants to practice asking questions, with the participation of key study personnel and research company representatives.

Enumeration area listing and address listing was conducted from January 22 to February 2, while field activities were conducted from February 19 to April 19.

2.6 Fieldwork quality control measures

For the purpose of monitoring field activities and timely detection and elimination of possible errors, 8 field activity monitoring tables were developed. According to these tables, the number of responses, household structure, percentage distribution of answers to key questions, and percentage distribution of children of appropriate age were monitored at the interviewer level. Team supervisors were responsible for daily monitoring of field work.

2.7 Data management, editing and analysis

Database formation included creating a working electronic database, data entry, and data editing. At the initial stage, the structure of the electronic database was developed. The structure of the main tables is based on the principles of questionnaire types and database optimization, where information from each questionnaire is separated and tables are defined according to unique units.

After data entry, quality control was carried out, which included verification of 20% of entered questionnaires. The verification did not reveal poor quality of data entry.

For data editing, 219 editing commands were developed, which are conditionally divided into four categories: 1) technical logic commands for data, which check for the existence of theoretically impossible values; 2) questionnaire skip logic commands, which check for missed and excessively entered responses; 3) quantitative commands, which check quantitative characteristics of questionnaires and responses; and 4) content relationship commands between questions, which assess the logical consistency of responses. Identified errors and questionable responses were corrected based on clarification with households and field personnel.

2.8 How to read the tables

The tables presented in the report include specific annotations that are used consistently to indicate the following:

- (*) — an asterisk in tables indicates that the percentage or proportion is based on fewer than 25 unweighted cases and are therefore too small to be reported;
- (number) — a figure in parenthesis indicates that the percentage or proportion is based on 25 to 49 unweighted cases and should be treated with caution;
- Don't know/Missing have been suppressed from the tables in case a small number of unweighted cases;
- "-" — a hyphen in tables indicates 0 unweighted cases in the denominator;
- na: not applicable.

3. Indicators and definitions

FFLS INDICATOR	SDG ¹	Module ²	Definition ³	Value
SAMPLE COVERAGE AND CHARACTERISTICS OF THE RESPONDENTS				
SR.1		HC	Percentage of households that have a television	97.4
SR.2		HC	Percentage of households that have a telephone (fixed line or mobile phone)	99.8
SR.3		HC	Percentage of households that have a computer	80.4
SR.4		HC	Percentage of households that have access to the internet by any device from home	98.3
SR.5		HL	Percentage of children age 0-17 years living with neither biological parent	3.9
SR.6		HL	Percentage of children age 0-17 years with one or both biological parents dead	3.2
SR.7		HL	Percentage of children age 0-17 years with at least one biological parent living abroad	7.0
LEARN				
LN.1		ED	Percentage of children age 36-59 months who are attending an early childhood education programme	75.6
LN.2	4.2.2	ED	Percentage of children in the relevant age group (one year before the official primary school entry age) who are attending an early childhood education programme or primary school	94.4
LN.3		ED	Percentage of children attending the first grade of primary school who attended early childhood education programme during the previous school year	88.8
LN.4		ED	Percentage of children of school-entry age who enter the first grade of primary school	83.8

¹ Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) indicators, <http://unstats.un.org/sdgs/indicators/indicators-list/>. The Inter-Agency Working Group on SDG indicators continuously updates the metadata for various SDG indicators, and changes also affect the list of SDG indicators. For detailed information on SDG indicator metadata, see: <http://unstats.un.org/sdgs/metadata/>

² Some indicators are calculated based on questions from several modules of the survey questionnaires. In such cases, the module(s) containing the most important information are indicated.

³ All survey indicators are disaggregated or can be disaggregated by wealth index quintile, sex, age, ethnicity, functional difficulties, geographical location or other characteristics, depending on statistical reliability, in accordance with the recommendations of the Inter-Agency Expert Group on SDG indicators: <http://unstats.un.org/sdgs/indicators/Official%20List%20of%20Proposed%20SDG%20Indicators.pdf>

FFLS INDICATOR			SDG ¹	Module ²	Definition ³	Value
LN.5a LN.5b LN.5c	Net attendance rate (adjusted)			ED	Percentage of children of a) primary school age currently attending primary, lower or upper secondary school b) lower secondary school age currently attending lower secondary school or higher c) upper secondary school age currently attending upper secondary school or higher	96.9 95.1 84.6
LN.6a LN.6b LN.6c	Out-of-school rate			ED	Percentage of children of a) primary school age who are not attending any level of education b) lower secondary school age who are not attending any level of education c) upper secondary school age who are not attending any level of education	0.4 0.1 1.9
LN.7a LN.7b	Gross intake ratio to the last grade			ED	Ratio of children attending the last grade for the first time to children at appropriate age to the last grade a) Primary school b) Lower secondary school	79.1 67.7
LN.8a LN.8b LN.8c	Completion rate			ED	Percentage of children age 3-5 years above the intended age for the last grade who have completed that grade a) Primary school b) Lower secondary school c) Upper secondary school	99.7 99.1 88.7
LN.9	Effective transition rate to lower secondary school			ED	Percentage of children attending the last grade of primary school during the previous school year and not repeating in the current school year who are attending the first grade of lower secondary school in the current school year	100
LN.10a LN.10b	Over-age for grade			ED	Percentage of children attending school who are at least 2 years above the intended age for grade (a) Primary school (b) Lower secondary school	1.4 2.9

FFLS INDICATOR	SDG ¹	Module ²	Definition ³	Value
a) Availability of information on children's school performance			<p>Net attendance rate (adjusted) for girls divided by net attendance rate (adjusted) for boys</p> <p>a) Organised learning (one year younger than the official primary school entry age)</p> <p>b) Primary school</p> <p>c) Lower secondary school</p> <p>d) Upper secondary school</p> <p>Net attendance rate (adjusted) for children in rural areas divided by net attendance rate (adjusted) for children in urban areas</p> <p>a) Organised learning (one year younger than the official primary school entry age)</p> <p>b) Primary school</p> <p>c) Lower secondary school</p> <p>d) Upper secondary school</p>	<p>1.06</p> <p>0.99</p> <p>0.99</p> <p>0.95</p> <p>0.94</p> <p>1.0</p> <p>1.0</p> <p>0.9</p>
LN.11a LN.11b LN.11c LN.11d	4.5.1	ED	<p>Percentage of girls with foundational learning skills divided by percentage of boys with foundational learning skills</p> <p>a) Reading, age 7-14 years</p> <p>b) Numeracy, age 7-14 years</p> <p>c) Reading, age for grade 2/3</p> <p>d) Numeracy, age for grade 2/3</p> <p>e) Reading, attending grade 2/3</p> <p>f) Numeracy, attending grade 2/3</p> <p>Percentage of children with foundational learning skills in the poorest wealth quintile divided by percentage of children with foundational learning skills in the richest wealth quintile</p> <p>a) Reading, age 7-14 years</p> <p>b) Numeracy, age 7-14 years</p> <p>Percentage of children with foundational learning skills in rural areas divided by percentage of children with foundational learning skills in urban areas</p> <p>a) Reading, age 7-14 years</p> <p>b) Numeracy, age 7-14 years</p> <p>Percentage of children with foundational learning skills among children with functional difficulties divided by percentage of children with foundational learning skills among children without functional difficulties</p> <p>a) Reading age, 7-14 years</p> <p>b) Numeracy age, 7-14 years</p>	<p>1.03</p> <p>0.93</p> <p>1.17</p> <p>0.92</p> <p>1.21</p> <p>0.90</p> <p>0.86</p> <p>0.64</p> <p>0.98</p> <p>0.92</p> <p>0.75</p> <p>0.78</p>
LN.12		PR	Percentage of children age 7-14 years attending school for whom an adult household member received a report card for the child in the last year	64.0

FFLS INDICATOR		SDG ¹	Module ²	Definition ³	Value
LN.13	Opportunity to participate in school management		PR	Percentage of children age 7-14 years attending school for whom their school's governing body is open to parental participation	75.2
LN.14	Participation in school management		PR	Percentage of children age 7-14 years attending school for whom an adult household member attended a school governing body meeting in the last year	33.0
LN.15	Effective participation in school management		PR	Percentage of children age 7-14 years attending school for whom an adult household member attended a school governing body meeting in the last year in which key education/financial issues were discussed	25.1
LN.16	Discussion with teachers regarding children's progress		PR	Percentage of children age 7-14 years attending school for whom an adult household member discussed child's progress with teachers in the last year	86.4
LN.17	Contact with school concerning teacher strike or absence		PR	Percentage of children age 7-14 years attending school and unable to attend class due to teacher strike or absence at least once in the last year for whom an adult household member contacted school representatives for this reason	17.2
LN.18	Availability of books at home		PR	Percentage of children age 7-14 years who have three or more books to read at home	87.3
LN.19	Reading habit at home		FL	Percentage of children age 7-14 years who read books or are read to at home	87.0
LN.20	School and home languages		FL	Percentage of children age 7-14 years attending school who at home speak the language that teachers use at school	97.3
LN.21	Support with homework		PR	Percentage of children age 7-14 years attending school and having homework who receive help with homework	60.1
LN.22a	Children with foundational reading and numeracy skills	4.1.1	FL	Percentage of children who successfully completed three foundational reading tasks	67.0
LN.22b				(a) Age 7-14 years	54.0
LN.22c				(b) Age for grade 2/3	54.8
LN.22d				(c) Attending grade 2/3	
LN.22e				Percentage of children who successfully completed four foundational numeracy tasks	59.8
LN.22f				(d) Age 7-14 years	35.6
				(e) Age for grade 2/3	37.0
				(f) Attending grade 2/3	
PROTECTED FROM VIOLENCE AND EXPLOITATION					
PR.2	Violent discipline	16.2.1	FCD	Percentage of children age 7-14 years who experienced any physical punishment and/or psychological aggression by caregivers in the past one month	40.3

4. Sample coverage and characteristics of respondents

4.1 Results of interviews

Table SR.1.1 presents the sample size and response rates for the household and children aged 7-14 surveys. Of the 3,597 selected households, 3,595 were found to be occupied, of which interviews were successfully conducted in 2,047 households, and the response rate was 56.9 percent.

In the surveyed households, 1,856 children (aged 7-14) were identified, interviews were successfully conducted with 1,780 children; accordingly, the response rate was 95.9 percent.

Table SR.1.1: Results of household and children age 7-14's interviews

Number of household and children age 7-14's interviews by interview results, by area of residence and region, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Area		Region											
	Total	Urban	Rural	Tbilisi	Adjara A.R	Guria	Imereti	Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti	Kakheti	Mtkheta-Mtianeti	Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti	Samtskhe-Javakheti	Kvemo Kartli	Shida Kartli
Households from Demographic														
Sampled	3,597	1,725	1,872	645	324	213	465	126	354	174	351	243	381	321
Occupied	3,595	1,724	1,871	645	324	213	465	126	352	174	351	243	381	321
Interviewed	2,047	907	1,140	307	169	142	278	76	166	91	271	194	197	156
Interviewed by Additional Search Method ^A	567	291	276	108	51	19	85	31	70	31	15	19	42	96
Interview completion rate	56.9	52.6	60.9	47.6	52.2	66.7	59.8	60.3	46.9	52.3	77.2	79.8	51.7	48.6
Interview response rate	56.9	52.6	60.9	47.6	52.2	66.7	59.8	60.3	47.2	52.3	77.2	79.8	51.7	48.6
Target Number of Households														
Target Number of Households	1,199	575	624	215	108	71	155	42	118	58	117	81	127	107
Interviewed	1,198	575	623	215	107	71	155	42	118	58	117	81	127	107
Response Rate of Target Number of Households	99.9	100.0	99.8	100.0	99.1	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Children aged 7-14 years old														
Number of Children in Interviewed Households	1,856	871	985	310	161	111	244	67	213	89	163	129	210	159
Interviewed	1,780	835	945	298	157	104	224	63	209	89	152	126	205	153
Number of Interviewed Mothers/Guardians	1,208	576	632	215	109	71	156	42	118	60	117	81	132	107
Response Rate for Children Aged 7-14	95.9	95.9	95.9	96.1	97.5	93.7	91.8	94.0	98.1	100.0	93.3	97.7	97.6	96.2

^A The household search step and snowball method were used.

4.2 Housing and household characteristics

Tables SR2.1, SR2.2, and SR2.3 reflect additional information obtained based on the household questionnaire regarding household characteristics.

Table SR2.1 presents the percentage distribution of households by living conditions characteristics, disaggregated by settlement type and region: internet access in the dwelling, number of rooms used for sleeping, and Overcrowding Rate.

Table SR2.2 presents the distribution of households by ownership of assets owned by the household and its members.

Table SR2.3 reflects the distribution of the population living in households by wealth index quintile groups, settlement type, and region.

Table SR.2.1: Housing characteristics

Percent distribution of households by selected housing characteristics, according to area of residence and region, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Area		Region											
	Total	Urban	Rural	Tbilisi	Adjara A.R.	Guria	Imereti	Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti	Kakheti	Mtkheta-Mtianeti	Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti	Samtskhe-Javakheti	Kvemo Kartli	Shida Kartli
Total^A	100.0	(100.0)	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0						
Internet access at home														
Yes	98.3	98.2	98.4	97.8	98.2	100.0	99.2	(100.0)	98.8	98.3	99.1	100.0	95.8	98.0
No	1.7	1.8	1.6	2.2	1.8	0.0	0.8	(0.0)	1.2	1.7	0.9	0.0	4.2	2.0
Rooms used for sleeping														
1	12.0	16.9	5.2	20.0	4.6	1.3	12.1	(9.6)	9.3	10.9	7.0	9.9	9.0	6.1
2	44.9	53.6	33.0	61.2	39.0	19.7	34.8	(49.1)	27.4	41.8	44.7	25.1	48.4	42.8
3 or more	43.1	29.5	61.8	18.8	56.4	79.0	53.1	(41.3)	63.3	47.4	48.3	65.0	42.6	51.1
Number of households	1,198	692	506	366	90	38	183	14	107	32	110	48	124	87
Overcrowding Rate	67.8	73.2	58.5	80.4	63.5	37.8	61.9	66.6	47.8	69.0	62.3	60.4	72.8	46.9
Number of units (couples, people aged 18 and over, children of different genders and ages, etc.)	3,506	2,215	1,292	1,253	398	98	365	15	257	94	245	106	483	192

^A "Devices used to access the Internet" has been suppressed from the table due to a small number of unweighted cases

() Figures that are based on 25-49 unweighted cases

Table SR.2.2: Household and personal assets

Percentage of households by using household and personal assets by area of residence and region, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Area		Region																												
	Total	Urban	Rural	Tbilisi		Adjara A.R.		Guria		Imereti		Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti		Kakheti		Mtkheta-Mtianeti		Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti		Samtskhe-Javakheti		Kvemo Kartli		Shida Kartli							
Percentage of households that use^A																															
Washing machine	97.3	99.0	95.0	98.8	100.0	94.7	94.9	(95.1)	98.0	92.6	94.9	98.9	95.4	100.0	97.4	98.9	98.9	95.4	100.0	97.2	98.5	98.5	100.0	95.4	100.0	97.4	98.9	98.9	95.4	100.0	
Television	97.4	96.6	98.6	94.8	99.2	100.0	98.9	(100.0)	94.7	98.7	100.0	97.2	98.5	100.0	97.2	98.7	100.0	98.5	100.0	97.2	98.5	98.5	100.0	98.5	100.0	97.2	98.7	98.9	98.9	95.4	100.0
Vacuum cleaner	57.7	66.9	45.0	66.1	76.3	33.9	47.5	(31.6)	41.6	48.4	43.3	65.0	59.4	73.4	43.3	65.0	65.0	59.4	73.4	65.0	65.0	65.0	65.0	59.4	73.4	65.0	65.0	65.0	65.0	59.4	73.4
Sewing machine	19.3	20.4	17.7	20.1	17.5	23.5	27.0	(22.2)	24.0	12.7	5.2	31.9	17.6	9.3	5.2	31.9	31.9	17.6	9.3	31.9	31.9	31.9	31.9	17.6	9.3	31.9	31.9	31.9	31.9	17.6	9.3
Computer/laptop/tablet	80.4	79.3	82.0	77.8	60.7	97.2	81.5	(95.1)	81.4	89.5	97.4	81.4	83.7	82.6	97.4	81.4	81.4	83.7	82.6	81.4	81.4	81.4	81.4	83.7	82.6	81.4	81.4	81.4	81.4	83.7	82.6
Car, truck, or van	60.3	59.2	61.8	57.2	74.7	42.1	63.4	(63.2)	66.6	70.4	46.0	68.3	63.0	57.8	46.0	68.3	68.3	63.0	57.8	68.3	68.3	68.3	68.3	63.0	57.8	68.3	68.3	68.3	68.3	63.0	57.8
Gas stove / Electric stove	92.8	98.2	85.4	98.8	98.3	98.3	95.9	(91.8)	99.0	98.7	79.3	85.5	69.6	97.3	79.3	85.5	85.5	69.6	97.3	85.5	85.5	85.5	85.5	69.6	97.3	85.5	85.5	85.5	69.6	97.3	
Mobile telephone	99.7	99.8	99.5	100.0	100.0	100.0	99.3	(100.0)	99.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	98.2	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	98.2	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	98.2	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	98.2
Fixed line	7.0	10.4	2.4	10.4	6.6	0.0	5.9	(0.0)	4.6	7.6	0.0	9.4	9.3	6.8	0.0	9.4	9.4	9.3	6.8	9.4	9.4	9.4	9.4	9.3	6.8	9.4	9.4	9.4	9.4	9.3	6.8
Heater (gas or electric)	79.7	93.2	61.2	96.3	74.4	50.8	79.0	(35.3)	64.5	94.8	66.2	51.8	74.1	89.6	66.2	51.8	51.8	74.1	89.6	51.8	51.8	51.8	51.8	74.1	89.6	51.8	51.8	51.8	51.8	74.1	89.6
Heater (wood oven)	31.6	8.8	62.9	2.0	35.4	67.0	37.8	(81.8)	51.0	16.8	59.2	60.2	46.4	26.6	59.2	60.2	60.2	46.4	26.6	60.2	60.2	60.2	60.2	46.4	26.6	60.2	60.2	60.2	46.4	26.6	
Dishwasher	10.4	12.5	7.6	10.9	23.8	4.3	5.9	(0.0)	7.1	1.8	3.7	10.9	16.8	14.8	3.7	10.9	10.9	16.8	14.8	10.9	10.9	10.9	10.9	16.8	14.8	10.9	10.9	10.9	16.8	14.8	
Refrigerator	97.9	98.3	97.4	98.0	99.2	95.9	97.9	(97.6)	95.7	98.6	100.0	97.6	98.1	97.1	100.0	97.6	97.6	98.1	97.1	97.6	97.6	97.6	97.6	98.1	97.1	97.6	97.6	97.6	98.1	97.1	
Water heater	83.5	89.7	75.0	96.3	79.1	82.7	79.4	(59.8)	78.8	94.7	55.2	64.5	81.1	98.0	55.2	64.5	64.5	81.1	98.0	64.5	64.5	64.5	64.5	81.1	98.0	64.5	64.5	64.5	81.1	98.0	
Number of Households	1,198	692	506	366	90	38	183		14	107	32	110	48	124	110	48	48	124	87	48	48	48	48	124	87	48	48	48	48	124	87

^A Don't know/Missing and Radio has been suppressed from the table due to a small number of unweighted cases

() Figures that are based on 25-49 unweighted cases

Table SR.2.3: Wealth quintiles

Percent distribution of the household population by wealth index quintile, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Wealth index quintile					Total	Number of household members
	Poorest	Second	Middle	Fourth	Richest		
Total	20.1	19.9	20.0	20.3	19.8	100.0	3,506
Area							
Urban	10.2	13.1	21.0	26.3	29.4	100.0	2,215
Rural	36.9	31.6	18.3	9.9	3.3	100.0	1,292
Region							
Tbilisi	11.2	10.2	21.7	27.5	29.4	100.0	1,253
Adjara A.R.	21.3	23.7	15.3	21.4	18.3	100.0	398
Guria	24.6	35.6	16.6	16.1	7.2	100.0	98
Imereti	24.5	24.3	21.4	16.9	12.9	100.0	365
Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti	37.5	22.0	22.8	17.7	0.0	100.0	15
Kakheti	33.4	24.2	16.7	15.9	9.8	100.0	257
Mtkheta-Mtianeti	20.9	18.9	32.6	17.0	10.6	100.0	94
Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti	39.7	30.0	11.0	16.7	2.6	100.0	245
Samtskhe-Javakheti	39.9	27.3	14.8	10.8	7.2	100.0	106
Kvemo Kartli	18.6	25.7	20.0	14.4	21.4	100.0	483
Shida Kartli	12.4	21.6	29.5	11.8	24.7	100.0	192

4.3 Household composition

Table SR.3.1 presents the percentage and frequency distribution of households by selected characteristics: sex and age of the household head, settlement type, region, education level of the household head, number of household members, ethnicity of the household head, and household composition.

The table provides both unweighted and weighted numbers. Similar information is necessary for the interpretation of findings presented in the report and reflects basic information about the representativeness of the study sample. Other tables presented in this report include only weighted numbers.

The basic characteristics presented are used in subsequent tables provided in this report. The indicators presented in the table show the number of observations for the main categories of the study.

The weighted and unweighted total number of households are equal, since the sampling weights are normalized. The table also presents the weighted average household size calculated from the study.

Table SR.3.1: Household composition

Percent and frequency distribution of households by selected characteristics, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Weighted percent	Number of households	
		Weighted	Unweighted
Total	100.0	2,614	2,614
Sex of household head			
Male	66.3	1,733	1,889
Female	33.7	881	725
Age of household head			
<18	0.0	0	0
18-34	8.1	212	209
35-64	55.7	1,457	1,578
65-84	33.9	886	774
85+	2.3	59	53
Area			
Urban	57.8	1,511	1,198
Rural	42.2	1,103	1,416
Region			
Tbilisi	30.6	800	415
Adjara A.R	7.6	197	220
Guria	3.1	82	161
Imereti	15.2	398	363
Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti	1.2	30	107
Kakheti	8.9	233	236
Mtskheta-Mtianeti	2.7	70	122
Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti	9.2	239	286
Samtskhe-Javakheti	4.0	104	213
Kvemo Kartli	10.3	270	239
Shida Kartli	7.2	189	252
Education of household head			
Kindergarten or none	0.8	22	10
Primary or Lower Secondary	4.3	113	126
Upper Secondary	41.5	1,086	1,225
Vocational Education	19.8	517	522
Higher	33.5	875	729
DK	0.0	1	2
Number of household members			
1	17.5	457	196
2	20.4	534	460
3	18.9	493	500
4	18.7	489	588
5	12.7	332	384
6	7.5	197	285
7+	4.3	113	201
Ethnicity of household head			
Georgian	90.2	2,357	2,353
Azerbaijani	5.9	154	130
Armenian	2.8	74	100
Other	1.1	28	31

Table SR.3.1: Household composition

Percent and frequency distribution of households by selected characteristics, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Weighted percent	Number of households	
		Weighted	Unweighted
Household with ^A			
At least one child under age 7 years	20.1	525	597
At least one child age 7-14 years	23.9	625	1,258
At least one child age <18 years	40.8	1,067	1,565
No adult (18+) member	0.0	0	0
Mean household size	3.9	2,614	2,614

^A Each proportion is a separate characteristic based on the total number of households

4.4 Age structure of household population

The weighted age and sex distribution of the survey population is provided in Table SR.4.1. In the households successfully interviewed in the survey, a weighted total of 10,120 household members were listed. Of these, 4,861 were males, and 5,259 were females.

Table SR.4.1: Age distribution of household population by sex

Percent and frequency distribution of the household population in five-year age groups and child (age 7-14 years) and adult populations (age 18 or more), by sex, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Males		Females		Total	
	Number	Percent	Number	Percent	Number	Percent
Total	4,861	100.0	5,259	100.0	10,120	100.0
Age						
0-4	287	5.9	303	5.8	590	5.8
5-9	403	8.3	340	6.5	743	7.3
10-14	334	6.9	273	5.2	607	6.0
15-19	295	6.1	295	5.6	590	5.8
15-17	179	3.7	164	3.1	343	3.4
18-19	116	2.4	131	2.5	247	2.4
20-24	304	6.2	279	5.3	582	5.8
25-29	326	6.7	300	5.7	627	6.2
30-34	324	6.7	397	7.5	721	7.1
35-39	424	8.7	345	6.6	769	7.6
40-44	334	6.9	378	7.2	712	7.0
45-49	316	6.5	290	5.5	607	6.0
50-54	303	6.2	332	6.3	636	6.3
55-59	291	6.0	322	6.1	613	6.1
60-64	288	5.9	392	7.5	680	6.7
65-69	260	5.4	329	6.3	589	5.8
70-74	160	3.3	322	6.1	482	4.8
75-79	116	2.4	160	3.0	276	2.7
80-84	59	1.2	127	2.4	186	1.8
85+	35	0.7	74	1.4	109	1.1
Child and adult populations^A						
Children age 7-4 years	564	11.6	489	9.3	1,054	10.4
Children age 15-17 years	179	3.7	164	3.1	343	3.4
Adults age 18+ years	3,657	75.2	4,179	79.5	7,836	77.4

^A Each value represents an independent characteristic of the total household population.

4.5 Background characteristics of children aged 7-14 years

Table SR.5.3 presents the basic characteristics of children aged 7-14 years. The total number of weighted and unweighted observations provided in the table are equal, since the sampling weights are normalized. The given categories of characteristics are used in the tabulation of relevant data in this report.

Table SR.5.3: Children age 7-14 years' background characteristics			
Percent and frequency distribution of children age 7-14 years, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024			
	Weighted percent	Number of children age 7-14	
		Weighted	Unweighted
Total	100.0	1,780	1,780
Sex			
Male	53.1	945	927
Female	46.9	835	853
Area			
Urban	64.9	1,155	835
Rural	35.1	625	945
Region			
Tbilisi	37.1	660	298
Adjara A.R	9.4	168	157
Guria	2.5	45	104
Imereti	10.3	183	224
Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti	0.4	7	63
Kakheti	6.9	123	209
Mtskheta-Mtianeti	2.5	45	89
Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti	7.6	135	152
Samtskhe-Javakheti	3.3	59	126
Kvemo Kartli	13.8	246	205
Shida Kartli	6.2	110	153
Age			
7-9	38.8	691	667
10-14	61.2	1,089	1,113
Mother's education^{A,D}			
Pre-primary or none	0.0	1	1
Primary	6.7	119	118
Secondary	32.9	586	680
Vocational	15.1	269	304
Higher	45.1	802	673
DK/Missing	0.2	3	4
Child's functional difficulties^B			
Has functional difficulty	5.7	102	93
Has no functional difficulty	94.3	1,678	1,687
Mother's functional difficulties^C			
Has functional difficulty	5.2	93	67
Has no functional difficulty	94.8	1,687	1,713

Table SR.5.3: Children age 7-14 years' background characteristics

Percent and frequency distribution of children age 7-14 years, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Weighted percent	Number of children age 7-14	
		Weighted	Unweighted
Ethnicity of household head			
Georgian	89.2	1,587	1,593
Azerbaijani	7.5	133	118
Armenian	2.9	51	60
Other	0.5	9	9
Income quintile			
Poorest	21.8	387	467
Second	19.9	354	407
Middle	20.2	360	368
Fourth	18.9	337	288
Richest	19.2	341	250

^A In this table and throughout the report where applicable, mother's education refers to educational attainment of mothers as well as caretakers (caretaker is interviewed only if the mother is deceased or is living elsewhere)

^B The results of the Child Functioning module are presented in Table EQ1.2.

^C In this table and throughout the report, mother's functional difficulties refer to functional difficulty of respondent as mentioned in note B.

^D The response category "emancipated" is not included in the table, as no cases were recorded.

4.6 ICT

The survey collected information on ownership of information and communication technology devices and internet access.

Table SR.9.2 presents information on ownership of information and communication technology (ICT) devices (radio, television, fixed telephone, mobile phone including smartphone, and computer) and internet access in the household.

Table SR.9.2: Household ownership of ICT equipment and access to internet

Percentage of households with a radio, a television, a telephone and a computer, and have access to the internet at home, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Percentage of households with a:					Percentage of household that have access to the internet at home ⁴	Number of households
	Television ¹	Fixed Line	Mobile Phone	Any ²	Computer ³		
Total	97.4	7.0	99.7	99.8	80.4	98.3	1,198
Area							
Urban	96.6	10.4	99.8	99.8	79.3	98.2	692
Rural	98.6	2.4	99.5	99.7	82.0	98.4	506
Region							
Tbilisi	94.8	10.4	100.0	100.0	77.8	97.8	366
Adjara A.R	99.2	6.6	100.0	100.0	60.7	98.2	90
Guria	100.0	0.0	100.0	100.0	97.2	100.0	38
Imereti	98.9	5.9	99.3	99.3	81.5	99.2	183
Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti	(100.0)	(0.0)	(100.0)	(100.0)	(95.1)	(100.0)	14
Kakheti	94.7	4.6	99.0	100.0	81.4	98.8	107
Mtskheta-Mtianeti	98.7	7.6	100.0	100.0	89.5	98.3	32
Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti	100.0	0.0	100.0	100.0	97.4	99.1	110
Samtskhe-Javakheti	97.2	9.4	100.0	100.0	57.1	100.0	48
Kvemo Kartli	98.5	9.3	100.0	100.0	83.7	95.8	124
Shida Kartli	100.0	6.8	98.2	98.2	82.6	98.0	87
Education of household head							
Kindergarten or none	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	1
Primary or Lower Secondary	97.2	5.3	100.0	100.0	67.7	95.0	59
Upper Secondary	96.9	4.5	99.8	99.8	76.6	97.7	515
Vocational Education	98.5	8.9	99.5	100.0	86.2	99.6	204
Higher	97.5	9.4	99.5	99.5	84.2	98.8	419

Table SR.9.2: Household ownership of ICT equipment and access to internet

Percentage of households with a radio, a television, a telephone, a computer, and have access to the internet at home, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Percentage of households with a:					Number of households
	Television ¹	Fixed Line	Mobile Phone	Any ²	Computer ³	
Ethnicity of household head						
Georgian	97.4	6.6	99.6	99.7	81.0	1,096
Azerbaijani	100.0	8.3	100.0	100.0	80.5	67
Armenian	(98.0)	(16.2)	(100.0)	(100.0)	(64.6)	26
Other	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	10
Wealth index quintile						
Poorest	92.9	2.9	99.4	99.7	52.9	290
Second	97.1	4.6	99.7	99.7	77.7	249
Middle	99.2	7.3	100.0	100.0	85.5	256
Fourth	99.5	9.1	100.0	100.0	97.4	211
Richest	100.0	13.6	99.3	99.3	100.0	192

¹ FFLS Indicator SR.1 - Households with a television

² FFLS Indicator SR.2 - Households with a telephone

³ FFLS indicator SR.3 - Households with a computer

⁴ FFLS indicator SR.4 - Households with internet

(*) Figures that are based on fewer than 25 unweighted cases.

() Figures that are based on 25-49 unweighted cases.

4.7 Children's living arrangements

The Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) recognizes that "the child, for the full and harmonious development of his or her personality, should grow up in a family environment, in an atmosphere of happiness, love and understanding". Millions of children around the world grow up without the care of their parents for several reasons, including due to the premature death of the parents or their migration for work. In most cases, these children are cared for by members of their extended families, while in others, children may be living in households other than their own. Understanding the children's living arrangements, including the composition of the households in which they live and the relationships with their primary caregivers, is key to design targeted interventions aimed at promoting child's care and wellbeing.

Table SR.11.1 presents information on the living arrangements and orphanhood status of children under age 18.

The Survey included a simple measure of one particular aspect of migration related to what is termed "children left behind", i.e. for whom one or both parents have moved abroad. While the amount of literature is growing, the long-term effects of the benefits of remittances versus the potential adverse psycho-social effects are not yet conclusive, as there is somewhat conflicting evidence available as to the effects on children. Table SR.11.2 presents information on the living arrangements and co-residence with parents of children under age 18.

Table SR.11.3 presents information on children under age 18 years not living with a biological parent according to relationship to the head of household and those living in households headed by a family member.

Table SR.11.1: Children's living arrangements and orphanhood

Percent distribution of children age 0-17 years according to living arrangements, percentage of children age 0-17 years not living with a biological parent and percentage of children who have one or both parents dead, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Living with both parents		Living with neither biological parent				Living with mother only				Living with father only		Missing information on father/mother	Total	Not living with biological mother	Living with neither biological parent ¹	One or both parents dead ²	Number of children age 0-17 years
	Only father alive	Only mother alive	Both alive	Both dead	Father alive	Father dead	Mother alive	Mother dead	Mother alive	Mother dead								
Total	82.3	0.3	0.3	3.2	0.1	9.7	2.2	1.5	0.4	0.1	100.0	5.8	3.9	3.2	2,284			
Sex																		
Male	80.7	0.4	0.4	3.1	0.1	11.1	2.0	1.8	0.3	0.1	100.0	6.2	4.0	3.2	1,204			
Female	84.2	0.1	0.2	3.4	0.1	8.1	2.3	1.2	0.4	0.1	100.0	5.4	3.7	3.1	1,080			
Area																		
Urban	80.7	0.4	0.5	2.7	0.0	12.1	2.4	1.0	0.1	0.0	100.0	4.8	3.6	3.4	1,459			
Rural	85.1	0.0	0.1	4.1	0.2	5.4	1.7	2.5	0.7	0.1	100.0	7.6	4.3	2.7	825			
Region																		
Tbilisi	78.9	0.6	0.8	3.2	0.0	12.5	2.8	0.8	0.3	0.0	100.0	5.7	4.7	4.6	805			
Adjara A.R	90.6	0.0	0.3	1.3	0.0	5.1	1.6	1.1	0.0	0.0	100.0	2.6	1.6	1.9	229			
Guria	80.1	0.0	0.0	4.7	0.0	10.3	4.0	0.9	0.0	0.0	100.0	5.6	4.7	4.0	53			
Imereti	76.3	0.0	0.0	4.1	0.0	15.1	1.0	3.3	0.3	0.0	100.0	7.7	4.1	1.3	263			
Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti	87.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.0	4.7	2.2	0.0	0.0	100.0	2.2	0.0	4.7	11			
Kakheti	85.1	0.0	0.0	3.5	0.0	8.0	1.3	2.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	5.5	3.5	1.3	180			
Mtskheta-Mtianeti	77.2	0.0	0.0	3.8	0.0	9.9	2.4	6.1	0.0	0.7	100.0	9.9	3.8	2.4	50			
Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti	84.0	0.0	0.0	4.6	0.0	4.3	2.6	1.8	2.2	0.3	100.0	8.7	4.6	4.9	139			
Samtskhe-Javakheti	92.2	0.9	0.0	0.0	1.3	2.4	0.7	0.3	1.6	0.6	100.0	4.1	2.2	4.5	92			
Kvemo Kartli	83.6	0.0	0.0	5.1	0.0	8.8	0.4	2.0	0.2	0.0	100.0	7.3	5.1	0.5	330			
Shida Kartli	87.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.2	4.2	6.5	1.0	0.2	0.0	100.0	1.4	0.2	6.9	133			

Table SR.11.1: Children's living arrangements and orphanhood

Percent distribution of children age 0-17 years according to living arrangements, percentage of children age 0-17 years not living with a biological parent and percentage of children who have one or both parents dead, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Living with both parents		Living with neither biological parent			Living with mother only		Living with father only		Missing information on father/mother	Total	Not living with biological mother	Living with neither biological parent ¹	One or both parents dead ²	Number of children age 0-17 years
	Only father alive	Only mother alive	Both alive	Both dead	Father alive	Father dead	Mother alive	Mother dead							
Age															
0-4	92.1	0.0	0.6	0.1	5.4	1.0	0.6	0.2	0.0	0.0	100.0	1.5	0.7	1.3	590
5-9	79.8	0.1	3.4	0.1	12.3	1.7	1.5	0.4	0.0	0.0	100.0	6.2	4.2	3.0	743
10-14	79.4	0.8	4.5	0.0	10.4	2.3	1.7	0.4	0.1	0.1	100.0	7.9	5.7	3.9	607
15-17	76.3	0.0	5.3	0.1	9.8	5.1	2.8	0.4	0.2	0.2	100.0	8.6	5.4	5.6	343
Household head's education³															
Kindergarten or none	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	100.0	(*)	(*)	(*)	3
Primary or Lower Secondary	88.0	0.8	1.3	0.0	8.3	1.0	0.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	2.7	2.1	1.8	106
Upper Secondary	84.0	0.1	2.9	0.1	8.5	1.7	2.1	0.3	0.1	0.1	100.0	5.7	3.2	2.3	985
Vocational Education	74.8	1.2	5.6	0.0	13.3	2.7	1.6	0.6	0.1	0.1	100.0	9.1	6.8	4.5	347
Higher	82.7	0.0	2.8	0.0	9.7	2.7	1.0	0.3	0.0	0.0	100.0	4.9	3.6	3.8	842
Ethnicity of household head															
Georgian	81.8	0.3	3.4	0.0	10.0	2.2	1.6	0.4	0.1	0.1	100.0	6.0	4.0	3.2	2,016
Azerbaijani	90.3	0.0	2.5	0.0	4.3	1.1	1.5	0.3	0.0	0.0	100.0	4.2	2.5	1.4	197
Armenian	76.9	1.4	1.1	1.9	15.0	3.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	4.4	4.4	7.1	61
Other	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	100.0	(*)	(*)	(*)	11

¹ FFLS indicator SR.5 - Children's living arrangements

² FFLS indicator SR.6 - Prevalence of children with one or both parents dead

A Don't know has been suppressed from the table due to a small number of unweighted cases

(*) Figures that are based on fewer than 25 unweighted cases

Table SR.11.2: Children's living arrangements and co-residence with parents

Percentage of children age 0-17 years by coresidence of parents, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Percentage of children age 0-17 years with:										Number of children age 0-17 years
	Mother living elsewhere ^a	Father living elsewhere ^a	Both mother and father living elsewhere ^a	At least one parent living elsewhere ^a	Mother living abroad	Father living abroad	Mother and father living abroad	At least one parent living abroad	7.0	2,284	
Total	5.0	12.4	3.0	14.3	3.4	5.0	1.3	7.0	2,284		
Sex											
Male	5.3	13.9	3.0	16.2	3.9	5.5	1.4	8.1	1,204		
Female	4.6	10.7	3.0	12.3	2.8	4.3	1.3	5.8	1,080		
Area											
Urban	4.0	14.4	2.6	15.9	2.6	5.5	1.2	6.9	1,459		
Rural	6.7	8.7	3.8	11.6	4.8	4.1	1.6	7.3	825		
Region											
Tbilisi	4.5	15.3	2.9	16.9	2.5	5.5	1.2	6.7	805		
Adjara A.R	2.6	5.1	0.8	6.9	1.8	0.9	0.0	2.7	229		
Guria	5.6	15.0	4.7	15.9	3.5	10.3	2.6	11.2	53		
Imereti	7.4	18.0	3.7	21.7	6.6	9.0	1.9	13.7	263		
Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti	2.2	6.0	0.0	8.3	0.9	3.8	0.0	4.7	11		
Kakheti	5.5	10.6	3.5	12.5	4.4	3.3	0.5	7.2	180		
Mtskheta-Mtianeti	9.9	13.6	3.8	19.7	9.9	7.4	1.6	15.6	50		
Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti	6.4	8.0	4.6	9.8	5.0	5.5	3.1	7.3	139		
Samtskhe-Javakheti	0.3	3.3	0.0	3.7	0.3	0.9	0.0	1.3	92		
Kvemo Kartli	7.1	13.9	5.1	15.9	3.7	5.0	2.5	6.2	330		
Shida Kartli	1.0	4.2	0.0	5.2	1.0	2.6	0.0	3.6	133		
Age											
0-4	1.2	5.3	0.6	5.9	1.2	2.0	0.6	2.6	590		
5-9	5.3	14.7	3.2	16.9	3.5	5.9	0.9	8.4	743		
5-6	4.2	12.7	1.7	15.3	3.2	5.1	0.0	8.3	297		
7-9	6.1	16.0	4.2	17.9	3.7	6.4	1.6	8.5	446		
10-14	6.4	15.0	4.0	17.5	4.3	6.0	2.1	8.3	607		
15-17	8.1	14.8	5.2	17.7	5.3	6.3	2.2	9.4	343		

Table SR.11.2: Children's living arrangements and co-residence with parents

Percentage of children age 0-17 years by coresidence of parents, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Percentage of children age 0-17 years with:										Number of children age 0-17 years
	Mother living elsewhere ^A	Father living elsewhere ^A	Both mother and father living elsewhere ^A	At least one parent living elsewhere ^A	Mother living abroad	Father living abroad	Mother and father living abroad	At least one parent living abroad	6.8	2,210	
Orphanhood status											
Both parents alive	4.8 (12.7)	12.6	3.1	14.2 (12.7)	3.3 (8.9)	4.9	1.4	na	6.8 (8.9)	2,210	
Only mother alive	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	57	
Only father alive	na	(*)	na	(*)	na	(*)	na	na	(*)	14	
Both parents deceased	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	1	
Unknown	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	1	
Household head's education^B											
Kindergarten or none	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	3	
Primary or Lower Secondary	1.9	8.5	1.3	9.1	1.9	3.1	1.3	3.7	3.7	106	
Upper Secondary	5.1	10.7	2.7	13.0	3.9	4.2	1.1	7.1	7.1	985	
Vocational Education	7.3	19.4	5.6	21.1	4.3	8.3	2.3	10.3	10.3	347	
Higher	4.3	12.0	2.5	13.8	2.6	4.7	1.3	6.1	6.1	842	
Ethnicity of household head											
Georgian	5.2	12.8	3.2	14.9	3.6	5.4	1.4	7.7	7.7	2,016	
Azerbaijani	3.9	6.8	2.5	8.2	1.5	1.7	1.1	2.2	2.2	197	
Armenian	1.1	17.5	1.1	17.5	1.1	2.5	1.1	2.5	2.5	61	
Other	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	11	

¹ FFLS indicator SR.7 - Children with at least one parent living abroad

^A Includes parent(s) living abroad as well as those living elsewhere in the country

^B Don't know has been suppressed from the table due to a small number of unweighted cases

(*) Figures that are based on fewer than 25 unweighted cases

na: not applicable

Table SR.11.3: Children not in parental care

Percent distribution of children age 0-17 years not living with a biological parent according to relationship to head of household and percentage living in households headed by a family member, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Child's relationship to head of household											Total		
	Percentage of children living with neither biological parent ¹	Number of children age 0-17 years	Child is head of household	Spouse/ Partner	Grand-child	Brother/Sister	Other relative	Adopted/ Foster/ Stepchild	Servant (Live-in)	Other not related	Inconsistent/ Don't know/ Missing			
Total	3.9	2,284	0.0	0.0	77.3	1.4	19.1	0.9	0.0	0.0	1.3	100.0	98.7	88
Sex														
Male	4.0	1,204	0.0	0.0	85.3	0.9	12.1	1.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	100.0	48
Female	3.7	1,080	(0.0)	(0.0)	(67.6)	(1.9)	(27.5)	(0.0)	(0.0)	(0.0)	(2.9)	100.0	(97.1)	40
Area														
Urban	3.6	1,459	(0.0)	(0.0)	(72.7)	(1.5)	(24.0)	(0.0)	(0.0)	(0.0)	(1.9)	100.0	(98.1)	53
Rural	4.3	825	0.0	0.0	84.0	1.3	11.9	2.3	0.0	0.0	0.5	100.0	99.5	36
Region														
Tbilisi	4.7	805	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	100.0	(*)	38
Adjara A.R	1.6	229	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	100.0	(*)	4
Guria	4.7	53	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	100.0	(*)	2
Imereti	4.1	263	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	100.0	(*)	11
Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti	0.0	11	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	100.0	-	0
Kakheti	3.5	180	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	100.0	(*)	6
Mtskheta-Mtianeti	3.8	50	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	100.0	(*)	2
Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti	4.6	139	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	100.0	(*)	6
Samtskhe-Javakheti	2.2	92	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	100.0	(*)	2
Kvemo Kartli	5.1	330	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	100.0	(*)	17
Shida Kartli	0.2	133	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	100.0	(*)	0

Table SR.11.3: Children not in parental care

Percent distribution of children age 0-17 years not living with a biological parent according to relationship to head of household and percentage living in households headed by a family member, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

Age	Child's relationship to head of household											Total	Percentage of children living in households headed by a family member ^A	Number of children age 0-17 years not living with a biological parent
	Child is head of household	Spouse/ Partner	Grand-child	Brother/Sister	Other relative	Adopted/ Foster/ Stepchild	Servant (Live-in)	Other not related	Inconsistent/ Don't know/ Missing	Percentage of children living in households headed by a family member ^A	Number of children age 0-17 years not living with a biological parent			
0-4	0.7 (*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	100.0	(*)	4
5-9	4.2 (0.0)	(0.0)	(88.1)	(0.0)	(6.2)	(1.9)	(0.0)	(0.0)	(3.8)	(96.2)	(*)	100.0	(96.2)	31
5-6	3.4 (*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	100.0	(*)	10
7-9	4.7 (0.0)	(0.0)	(82.3)	(0.0)	(9.2)	(2.9)	(0.0)	(0.0)	(5.6)	(94.4)	(*)	100.0	(94.4)	21
10-14	5.7 0.0	0.0	72.6	3.5	23.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	(*)	100.0	100.0	35
15-17	5.4 (*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	100.0	(*)	19
Orphanhood status														
Both parents alive	3.3	0.0	80.2	1.7	15.7	0.8	0.0	0.0	1.6	98.4	(*)	100.0	98.4	74
Only mother alive	12.7 (*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	100.0	(*)	7
Only father alive	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	100.0	(*)	6
Both parents deceased	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	100.0	(*)	1
Unknown	(*)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	100.0	-	0
Household head's education^B														
Kindergarten or none	(*)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	100.0	-	0
Primary or Lower Secondary	2.1 (*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	100.0	(*)	2
Upper Secondary	3.2	0.0	81.3	3.8	11.0	0.7	0.0	0.0	3.1	96.9	(*)	100.0	96.9	32
Vocational Education	6.8	(0.0)	(62.2)	(0.0)	(37.8)	(0.0)	(0.0)	(0.0)	(0.0)	(100.0)	(*)	100.0	(100.0)	24
Higher	3.6	(0.0)	(83.0)	(0.0)	(14.5)	(2.0)	(0.0)	(0.0)	(0.6)	(99.4)	(*)	100.0	(99.4)	31

Table SR.11.3: Children not in parental care

Percent distribution of children age 0-17 years not living with a biological parent according to relationship to head of household and percentage living in households headed by a family member, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Child's relationship to head of household											Total	Percentage of children living in households headed by a family member ^A	Number of children age 0-17 years not living with a biological parent		
	Child is head of household	Spouse/ Partner	Grand-child	Brother/ Sister	Other relative	Adopted/ Foster/ Stepchild	Servant (Live-in)	Other not related	Inconsistent/ Don't know/ Missing	Other not related	Other not related					
Ethnicity of household head																
Georgian	0.0	0.0	77.4	1.5	18.6	1.0	0.0	0.0	1.5	0.0	0.0	100.0	98.5	81		
Azerbaijani	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	100.0	(*)	5		
Armenian	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	100.0	(*)	3		
Other	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	100.0	-	0		

^A Excludes households headed by the child, servants and other not related

^B Don't know has been suppressed from the table due to a small number of unweighted cases

() Figures that are based on 25-49 unweighted cases

(*) Figures that are based on fewer than 25 unweighted cases

"-" Denotes 0 unweighted cases in the denominator

5. Learn

5.1 Kindergarten

Children's readiness for primary school can be improved by attending kindergarten. Kindergarten programs include programs for children that contain organized learning components.

According to legislation, children in public kindergartens are provided with free education and meals. Kindergarten and preparatory programs for school entry are voluntary, universal and accessible to all children of appropriate age.

Table LN1.1 presents the percentage of children aged 3-4 attending kindergarten - indicator LN.1.

In Georgia, kindergarten programs may be provided by both state/public and private, as well as other (for example, religious) types of institutions.

Table LN.1.2 reflects the percentage distribution of children who, at the beginning of the school year, were one year younger than the official age for entering primary school, by attendance at an educational institution, as well as by attendance at kindergarten or the primary level of school.

Table LN.1.1: Kindergarten

Percentage of children age 36-59 months who are attending kindergarten, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Percentage of children age 36-59 months attending kindergarten ¹	Number of children age 36-59 months
Total	75.6	285
Sex		
Male	77.3	123
Female	74.3	162
Area		
Urban	75.4	174
Rural	75.9	111
Region		
Tbilisi	(76.2)	98
Adjara A.R	(73.6)	33
Guria	(*)	2
Imereti	(77.2)	30
Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti	(*)	1
Kakheti	(92.6)	23
Mtskheta-Mtianeti	(*)	7
Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti	(*)	18
Samtskhe-Javakheti	(76.2)	14
Kvemo Kartli	(59.1)	43
Shida Kartli	(*)	17
Age (in months)		
36-47	64.7	145
48-59	87.0	140
Mother's education^A		
Kindergarten or none	-	0
Primary or Lower Secondary	(*)	4
Upper Secondary	65.9	102
Vocational Education	(64.1)	28
Higher	85.0	143
Ethnicity of household head		
Georgian	82.7	239
Azerbaijani	(*)	42
Armenian	(*)	5
Other	-	0

¹ FFLS indicator LN.1 - Attendance to early childhood education^A Don't know/Missing has been suppressed from the table due to a small number of unweighted cases.

() Figures that are based on 25-49 unweighted cases.

(*) Figures that are based on fewer than 25 unweighted cases.

“-“ Denotes 0 unweighted case in the denominator or in the column.

Table LN.1.2: Participation rate in organised learning

Percent distribution of children age one year younger than the official primary school entry age at the beginning of the school year, by attendance to education, and attendance to kindergarten or primary education (adjusted net attendance ratio), Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Percent of children:			Total	Net attendance ratio ¹	Number of children age 5 years at the beginning of the school year
	Attending kindergarten	Attending primary education	Not attending kindergarten or primary education			
Total^A	84.7	9.7	5.6	100.0	94.4	118
Sex						
Male	86.3	5.8	7.9	100.0	92.1	69
Female	82.6	15.2	2.2	100.0	97.8	49
Area						
Urban	86.8	9.8	3.4	100.0	96.6	77
Rural	80.9	9.5	9.6	100.0	90.4	41
Parity indices						
Sex						
Female/male ²	0.96	2.61	0.28	na	1.06	na
Area						
Rural/Urban ³	0.93	0.98	2.84	na	0.94	na

¹ FFLS indicator LN.2- Participation rate in organised learning (adjusted); SDG indicator 4.2.2

² FFLS indicator LN.11a - Parity indices - organised learning (gender); SDG indicator 4.5.1

³ FFLS indicator LN.11b - Parity indices - organised learning (area); SDG indicator 4.5.1

^A The characteristics of "Region", "Mother's education" and "Ethnicity of household head" are not presented in the table, due to the small number of unweighted cases within each category.
na: not applicable

5.2 Attendance

Tables LN.2.1 and LN.2.2 reflect the percentage of children who attend the first grade of primary school and attended kindergarten the previous year, and the percentage of children of appropriate age for entering the primary level of school who attend the first grade.

Table LN.2.3 shows the percentage of children of primary school age who attend primary or lower secondary (basic) level of school (net adjusted attendance rate), the percentage of children who attend kindergarten, the percentage of children who are out of school.

Table LN.2.4 reflects the percentage of children of lower secondary (basic) school age who attend lower secondary (basic) or higher levels of education (net adjusted attendance rate), the percentage of children who attend primary level of school, the percentage of children who are out of school.

Table LN.2.5 presents the percentage of children who attend primary and lower secondary (basic) levels of school and are younger than the official age established for the corresponding grade, of the appropriate official age, 1 year older, 2 or more years older.

Table LN.2.6 shows the percentage of children of upper secondary education age who attend upper secondary or higher levels of education (net adjusted attendance rate), the percentage of children who attend the basic level of school, and the percentage of children who are out of school.

Table LN.2.7 presents the gross intake rate and completion rate for primary school, as well as the effective transition rate to lower secondary (basic) school, the gross intake rate and completion rate for secondary (basic) school.

Table LN.2.8 focuses on the ratio of girl to boy students at primary and secondary levels of school. These ratios are better known as the Gender Parity Index (GPI). It should be noted that the indicators presented in the table are based on net adjusted attendance rates rather than gross attendance rates.

Table LN.2.1: School readiness

Percentage of children attending first grade of primary school who attended kindergarten the previous year, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Percentage of children attending first grade who attended kindergarten in previous year ¹	Number of children attending first grade of primary school
Total^A	88.8	151
Sex		
Male	93.7	81
Female	82.9	69
Area		
Urban	88.4	97
Rural	89.5	54
Mother's education^A		
Kindergarten or none	-	0
Primary or Lower Secondary	(*)	11
Upper Secondary	88.0	51
Vocational Education	(100.0)	21
Higher	83.9	58

¹ FFLS indicator LN.3 - School readiness

^A The characteristics of "Region" and "Ethnicity of household head" are not presented in the table, due to the small number of unweighted cases within each category.

^B Don't know/Missing has been suppressed from the table due to a small number of unweighted cases.

() Figures that are based on 25-49 unweighted cases.

(*) Figures that are based on fewer than 25 unweighted cases.

"-" Denotes 0 unweighted case in the denominator or in the column.

Table LN.2.2: Primary school entry

Percentage of children of primary school entry age entering grade 1 (net intake rate), Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Percentage of children of primary school entry age entering grade 1 ¹	Number of children of primary school entry age
Total^A	83.8	164
Sex		
Male	86.4	92
Female	80.5	73
Area		
Urban	82.8	108
Rural	85.7	56
Mother's education^B		
Kindergarten or none	-	0
Primary or Lower Secondary	(*)	14
Upper Secondary	84.8	57
Vocational Education	(87.4)	16
Higher	81.0	68

¹ FFLS indicator LN.4 - Net intake rate in primary education

^A The characteristics of "Region" and "Ethnicity of household head" are not presented in the table, due to the small number of unweighted cases within each category.

^B Don't know/Missing has been suppressed from the table due to a small number of unweighted cases.

() Figures that are based on 25-49 unweighted cases.

(*) Figures that are based on fewer than 25 unweighted cases.

"-" Denotes 0 unweighted case in the denominator or in the column.

Table LN.2.3: Primary school attendance and out of school children

Percentage of children of primary school age attending primary or lower secondary school (adjusted net attendance ratio), percentage attending kindergarten, and percentage out of school, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children. Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Male			Female			Total					
	Net attendance ratio (adjusted)	Attending kindergarten	Out of school ^A	Number of children of primary school age at beginning of school year	Net attendance ratio (adjusted)	Attending kindergarten	Out of school ^A	Number of children of primary school age at beginning of school year	Net attendance ratio (adjusted) ¹	Attending kindergarten	Out of school ^A	Number of children of primary school age at beginning of school year
Total^B	97.3	2.5	0.2	460	96.3	3.0	0.6	394	96.9	2.7	0.4	854
Area												
Urban	97.3	2.7	0.0	299	95.8	3.4	0.8	257	97.3	2.5	0.2	460
Rural	97.3	2.2	0.5	161	97.2	2.4	0.4	138	96.3	3.0	0.6	394
Region												
Tbilisi	97.3	2.7	0.0	167	97.0	3.0	0.0	152	97.2	2.8	0.0	319
Adjara A.R	97.4	2.6	0.0	51	(94.2)	(5.8)	(0.0)	34	96.1	3.9	0.0	86
Guria	(100.0)	(0.0)	(0.0)	8	(100.0)	(0.0)	(0.0)	12	100.0	0.0	0.0	20
Imereti	100.0	0.0	0.0	47	98.7	1.3	0.0	43	99.4	0.6	0.0	90
Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti	(*)	(*)	(*)	1	(100.0)	(0.0)	(0.0)	2	(100.0)	(0.0)	(0.0)	3
Kakheti	97.8	2.2	0.0	42	94.6	5.4	0.0	29	96.5	3.5	0.0	71
Mtskheta-Mtianeti	(100.0)	(0.0)	(0.0)	9	(100.0)	(0.0)	(0.0)	8	100.0	0.0	0.0	17
Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti	100.0	0.0	0.0	31	100.0	0.0	0.0	30	100.0	0.0	0.0	61
Samtskhe-Javakheti	92.8	7.2	0.0	17	95.5	0.0	4.5	12	93.9	4.2	1.9	30
Kvemo Kartli	93.2	5.5	1.3	63	90.2	5.9	3.9	51	91.8	5.7	2.5	114
Shida Kartli	100.0	0.0	0.0	23	98.6	1.4	0.0	21	99.3	0.7	0.0	45

Table LN.2.3: Primary school attendance and out of school children

Percentage of children of primary school age attending primary or lower secondary school (adjusted net attendance ratio), percentage attending kindergarten, and percentage out of school, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children. Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Male				Female				Total			
	Net attendance ratio (adjusted)	Attending kindergarten	Out of school ^A	Number of children of primary school age at beginning of school year	Net attendance ratio (adjusted)	Attending kindergarten	Out of school ^A	Number of children of primary school age at beginning of school year	Net attendance ratio (adjusted) ¹	Attending kindergarten	Out of school ^A	Number of children of primary school age at beginning of school year
Age at beginning of school year												
6	86.6	12.4	0.9	92	80.5	16.0	3.5	73	83.9	14.0	2.1	164
7	100.0	0.0	0.0	73	99.6	0.4	0.0	72	99.8	0.2	0.0	144
8	100.0	0.0	0.0	79	100.0	0.0	0.0	76	100.0	0.0	0.0	155
9	100.0	0.0	0.0	87	100.0	0.0	0.0	70	100.0	0.0	0.0	156
10	100.0	0.0	0.0	80	100.0	0.0	0.0	54	100.0	0.0	0.0	134
11	100.0	0.0	0.0	50	100.0	0.0	0.0	50	100.0	0.0	0.0	100
Mother's education^C												
Kindergarten or none	-	-	-	0	-	-	-	0	-	-	-	0
Primary or Lower Secondary	(100.0)	(0.0)	(0.0)	24	(93.4)	(0.0)	(6.6)	30	96.3	0.0	3.7	54
Upper Secondary	96.4	3.1	0.5	156	97.3	2.2	0.5	112	96.8	2.7	0.5	268
Vocational Education	98.5	1.5	0.0	62	97.5	2.5	0.0	46	98.1	1.9	0.0	108
Higher	97.2	2.8	0.0	183	95.7	4.3	0.0	184	96.5	3.5	0.0	367

¹ FFLS indicator LN.5a - Primary school net attendance ratio (adjusted)

² FFLS indicator LN.6a - Out-of-school rate for children of primary school age

^A The percentage of children of primary school age who are out of school refers to children who are not attending any level of education.

^B The characteristics of "Ethnicity of household head" are not presented in the table, due to the small number of unweighted cases within each category.

^C Don't know/Missing has been suppressed from the table due to a small number of unweighted cases.

() Figures that are based on 25-49 unweighted cases.

(*) Figures that are based on fewer than 25 unweighted cases.

"-" Denotes 0 unweighted case in the denominator or in the column.

Table LN.2.4: Lower secondary school attendance and out of school adolescents

Percentage of children of lower secondary school age attending lower secondary school or higher (adjusted net attendance ratio), percentage attending primary school, and percentage out of school, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Male				Female				Total			
	Net attendance ratio (adjusted) ¹	Attending primary school	Out of school ^A	Number of children of lower secondary school age at beginning of school year	Net attendance ratio (adjusted)	Attending primary school	Out of school ^A	Number of children of lower secondary school age at beginning of school year	Net attendance ratio (adjusted) ¹	Attending primary school	Out of school ^A	Number of children of lower secondary school age at beginning of school year
Total^B	95.7	3.9	0.2	199	94.5	5.5	0.0	170	95.1	4.7	0.1	369
Area												
Urban	95.6	4.2	0.0	128	94.5	5.5	0.0	117	95.1	4.8	0.0	245
Rural	96.0	3.4	0.6	70	94.3	5.7	0.0	53	95.3	4.4	0.3	124
Age at beginning of school year												
12	86.4	13.6	0.0	56	85.5	14.5	0.0	58	85.9	14.1	0.0	113
13	99.7	0.3	0.0	77	98.3	1.7	0.0	61	99.1	0.9	0.0	138
14	99.0	0.0	0.6	66	100.0	0.0	0.0	51	99.4	0.0	0.3	117
Mother's education^{C,D}												
Kindergarten or none	-	-	-	0	-	-	-	0	-	-	-	0
Primary or Lower Secondary	(*)	(*)	(*)	10	(*)	(*)	(*)	6	(92.6)	(4.8)	(2.6)	16
Upper Secondary	97.1	2.5	0.0	63	98.0	2.0	0.0	46	97.5	2.3	0.0	109
Vocational Education	96.8	3.2	0.0	29	89.8	10.2	0.0	29	93.3	6.7	0.0	58
Higher	93.5	6.5	0.0	81	96.4	3.6	0.0	77	94.9	5.1	0.0	159

¹ FFLS indicator LN.5b - Lower secondary school net attendance ratio (adjusted)

² FFLS indicator LN.6b - Out-of-school rate for adolescents of lower secondary school age

^A The percentage of children of lower secondary school age who are out of school refers to children who are not attending any level of education.

^B The characteristics of "Region" and "Ethnicity of household head" are not presented in the table, due to the small number of unweighted cases within each category.

^C Does not include children aged 15–17 who have been released from parental guardianship, and children aged 18 and older at the time of the interview.

^D Don't know/Missing has been suppressed from the table due to a small number of unweighted cases.

() Figures that are based on 25–49 unweighted cases.

(*) Figures that are based on fewer than 25 unweighted cases.

“-” Denotes 0 unweighted case in the denominator or in the column.

Table LN.2.5: Age for grade

Percentage of children attending primary and lower secondary school who are underage, at official age and coverage by 1 and by 2 or more years for grade, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Primary school						Lower secondary school					
	Percent of children by grade of attendance:						Percent of children by grade of attendance:					
	Under-age	At official age	Over-age by 1 year	Over-age by 2 or more years ^a	Total	Number of children attending primary school	Under-age	At official age	Over-age by 1 year	Over-age by 2 or more years ^a	Total	Number of children attending lower secondary school
Total^A	6.0	81.0	11.6	1.4	100.0	854	3.4	78.5	15.2	2.9	100.0	360
Sex												
Male	5.5	81.9	11.5	1.2	100.0	458	2.2	81.8	11.9	4.1	100.0	195
Female	6.6	79.9	11.8	1.7	100.0	396	4.8	74.6	19.0	1.6	100.0	165
Area												
Urban	6.3	80.9	11.5	1.4	100.0	558	2.9	83.2	13.9	0.0	100.0	226
Rural	5.4	81.2	11.8	1.5	100.0	297	4.2	70.6	17.3	7.9	100.0	134
Mother's education^{B,C}												
Kindergarten or none	-	-	-	-	-	0	-	-	-	-	-	0
Primary or Lower Secondary	7.4	77.8	13.9	0.9	100.0	53	(0.0)	(80.6)	(13.2)	(6.2)	(100.0)	16
Upper Secondary	4.3	81.7	11.8	2.2	100.0	265	1.5	71.6	19.2	7.8	100.0	111
Vocational Education	10.3	80.3	9.3	0.0	100.0	115	7.4	77.2	15.5	0.0	100.0	55
Higher	6.2	80.5	12.1	1.3	100.0	362	4.3	82.0	13.0	0.6	100.0	153
Grade												
1 (primary/lower secondary)	6.8	84.5	8.1	0.6	100.0	151	2.6	76.6	20.1	0.7	100.0	120
2 (primary/lower secondary)	7.6	77.4	12.5	2.4	100.0	155	4.6	83.6	9.8	2.1	100.0	131
3 (primary/lower secondary)	7.2	77.5	13.5	1.7	100.0	164	2.9	74.4	16.2	6.4	100.0	109
4 (primary)	4.8	82.9	11.1	1.2	100.0	155	na	na	na	na	na	na
5 (primary)	2.5	85.4	10.8	1.2	100.0	127	na	na	na	na	na	na
6 (primary)	6.4	78.4	14.0	1.2	100.0	103	na	na	na	na	na	na

Table LN.2.5: Age for grade

Percentage of children attending primary and lower secondary school who are underage, at official age and overage by 1 and by 2 or more years for grade, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Primary school					Lower secondary school						
	Percent of children by grade of attendance:					Percent of children by grade of attendance:						
	Under-age	At official age	Over-age by 1 year	Over-age by 2 or more years ¹	Total	Number of children attending primary school	Under-age	At official age	Over-age by 1 year	Over-age by 2 or more years ²	Total	Number of children attending lower secondary school
Ethnicity of household head												
Georgian	6.1	81.6	10.9	1.4	100.0	764	3.4	81.0	14.4	1.1	100.0	320
Azerbaijani	5.9	72.0	20.3	1.8	100.0	61	(0.0)	(52.0)	(24.2)	(23.9)	(100.0)	29
Armenian	3.2	83.8	13.0	0.0	100.0	24	(12.7)	(74.2)	(13.1)	(0.0)	(100.0)	10
Other	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	5	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	0

¹ FFLS indicator LN.10a - Over-age for grade (Primary)

² FFLS indicator LN.10b - Over-age for grade (Lower secondary)

^A The characteristics of "Region" are not presented in the table, due to the small number of unweighted cases within each category.
^B Does not include children aged 15–17 who have been released from parental guardianship, and children aged 18 and older at the time of the interview.
^C Don't know/Missing has been suppressed from the table due to a small number of unweighted cases.

na: not applicable
 () Figures that are based on 25–49 unweighted cases.
 (*) Figures that are based on fewer than 25 unweighted cases.
 "c" Denotes 0 unweighted case in the denominator or in the column.

Table LN.2.6: Upper secondary school attendance and out of school youth

Percentage of children of upper secondary school age attending upper secondary school or higher (adjusted net attendance ratio), percentage attending lower secondary school, and percentage out of school, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Male			Female			Total								
	Net attendance ratio (adjusted)	Percentage of children: Attending lower secondary school	Attending primary school	Out of school ^A	Number of children of upper secondary school age at beginning of school year	Net attendance ratio (adjusted)	Percentage of children: Attending lower secondary school	Attending primary school	Out of school ^A	Number of children of upper secondary school age at beginning of school year	Net attendance ratio (adjusted) ¹	Percentage of children: Attending lower secondary school	Attending primary school	Out of school ^A	Number of children of upper secondary school age at beginning of school year
Total^B	86.8	7.9	0.0	1.1	171	82.3	8.3	0.0	2.8	160	84.6	8.1	0.0	1.9	331
Area															
Urban	91.5	1.8	0.0	0.1	98	82.7	7.1	0.0	1.3	104	87.0	4.5	0.0	0.7	202
Rural	80.4	16.2	0.0	2.3	73	81.7	10.5	0.0	5.6	56	81.0	13.7	0.0	3.7	129
Age at beginning of school year															
15	80.9	17.6	0.0	1.5	53	78.9	19.6	0.0	0.0	57	79.8	18.6	0.0	0.7	110
16	91.6	7.2	0.0	0.0	59	95.8	3.7	0.0	0.6	58	93.7	5.5	0.0	0.3	116
17	(87.2)	(0.0)	(0.0)	(1.7)	59	(69.6)	(0.0)	(0.0)	(9.2)	45	79.6	0.0	0.0	5.0	105

Table LN.2.6: Upper secondary school attendance and out of school youth

Percentage of children of upper secondary school age attending upper secondary school or higher (adjusted net attendance ratio), percentage attending lower secondary school, and percentage out of school, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Male			Female			Total		
	Net attendance ratio (adjusted)	Percentage of children: Attending lower secondary school Attending primary school Out of school ^A	Number of children of upper secondary school age at beginning of school year	Net attendance ratio (adjusted)	Percentage of children: Attending lower secondary school Attending primary school Out of school ^A	Number of children of upper secondary school age at beginning of school year	Net attendance ratio (adjusted) ¹	Percentage of children: Attending lower secondary school Attending primary school Out of school ^A	Number of children of upper secondary school age at beginning of school year
Mother's education^{CD}									
Kindergarten or none	-	-	0	-	-	0	-	-	0
Primary or Lower Secondary	(*)	(*)	4	(*)	(*)	2	(*)	(*)	7
Upper Secondary	80.9	17.9	67	80.2	7.9	57	80.6	13.3	124
Vocational Education	(97.8)	(0.8)	29	(*)	(*)	17	90.1	9.0	46
Higher	(93.7)	(0.0)	60	91.8	6.4	61	92.7	3.2	120

¹ FFLS indicator LN.5c - Upper secondary school net attendance ratio (adjusted)

² FFLS indicator LN.6c - Out-of-school rate for youth of upper secondary school age

^A The percentage of children of upper secondary school age who are out of school refers to children who are not attending any level of education.

^B The characteristics of "Region" and "Ethnicity of household head" are not presented in the table, due to the small number of unweighted cases within each category.

^C Does not include children aged 15–17 who have been released from parental guardianship, and children aged 18 and older at the time of the interview.

^D Don't know/Missing has been suppressed from the table due to a small number of unweighted cases.

() Figures that are based on 25–49 unweighted cases.

(*) Figures that are based on fewer than 25 unweighted cases.

“-“ Denotes 0 unweighted case in the denominator or in the column.

Table LN.2.7: Gross intake, completion and effective transition rates

	Gross intake rate to the last grade of primary school ¹	Number of children of primary school completion age	Primary school completion rate ²	Number of children age 14-16 years ^a	Effective transition rate to lower secondary school ³	Number of children who were in the last grade of primary school the previous year and are not repeating that grade in the current school year	Gross intake rate to the last grade of lower secondary school ⁴	Number of children of lower secondary school completion age	Lower secondary completion rate ⁵	Number of adolescents age 17-19 years ^a	Upper secondary completion rate ⁶	Number of youth age 20-22 years ^a
Total^b	79.1	100	99.7	344	100.0	117	67.7	117	99.1	353	88.7	345
Sex												
Male	80.8	50	99.8	178	100.0	56	69.8	66	99.3	167	85.8	164
Female	77.3	50	99.5	166	100.0	61	65.0	51	98.9	186	91.4	181
Area												
Urban	80.7	63	99.9	204	100.0	77	68.8	72	99.3	246	91.2	232
Rural	76.2	37	99.4	139	100.0	41	65.9	45	98.6	106	83.7	113

Table LN.2.7: Gross intake, completion and effective transition rates

Gross intake rate and completion rate for primary school, effective transition rate to lower secondary school, gross intake rate and completion rate for lower secondary school and completion rate for upper secondary school, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Gross intake rate to the last grade of primary school ¹	Number of children of primary school completion age ²	Primary school completion rate ²	Number of children age 14-16 years ³	Effective transition rate to lower secondary school ³	Number of children who were in the last grade of primary school the previous year and are not repeating that grade in the current school year	Gross intake rate to the last grade of lower secondary school ⁴	Number of children of lower secondary school completion age	Lower secondary completion rate ⁵	Number of adolescents age 17-19 years ⁴	Upper secondary completion rate ⁶	Number of youth age 20-22 years ⁴
Mother's education^{c,d}												
Kindergarten or none	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	na	na
Primary or Lower Secondary	(*)	8	(*)	11	(*)	5	(*)	4	(*)	3	na	na
Upper Secondary	74.4	28	99.8	129	100.0	31	51.7	42	97.8	105.1	na	na
Vocational Education	(89.9)	13	100.0	48	(100.0)	16	(64.0)	21	(100.0)	46.1	na	na
Higher	75.4	42	100.0	127	100.0	54	85.6	42	100.0	111	na	na

¹ FFLS indicator LN.7a - Gross intake rate to the last grade (Primary)

² FFLS indicator LN.8a - Completion rate (Primary)

³ FFLS indicator LN.9 - Effective transition rate to lower secondary school

⁴ FFLS indicator LN.7b - Gross intake rate to the last grade (Lower secondary)

⁵ FFLS indicator LN.8b - Completion rate (Lower secondary)

⁶ FFLS indicator LN.8c - Completion rate (Upper secondary)

^A Total number of children age 3-5 years above the intended age for the last grade, for primary, lower and upper secondary, respectively.

^B The characteristics of "Region" and "Ethnicity of household head" are not presented in the table, due to the small number of unweighted cases within each category.

^C Does not include children aged 15-17 who have been released from parental guardianship, and children aged 18 and older at the time of the interview.

^D Don't know/Missing has been suppressed from the table due to a small number of unweighted cases.

na: not applicable

() Figures that are based on 25-49 unweighted cases.

(*) Figures that are based on fewer than 25 unweighted cases.

"-" Denotes 0 unweighted case in the denominator or in the column.

Table LN.2.8: Parity indices

Ratio of adjusted net attendance ratios of girls to boys, in primary, lower and upper secondary school, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Primary school				Lower secondary school				Upper secondary school			
	Primary school adjusted net attendance ratio (NAR), girls	Primary school adjusted net attendance ratio (NAR), boys	Primary school adjusted net attendance ratio (NAR), total	Gender parity index (GPI) for primary school adjusted NAR ²	Lower secondary school adjusted net attendance ratio (NAR), girls	Lower secondary school adjusted net attendance ratio (NAR), boys	Lower secondary school adjusted net attendance ratio (NAR), total	Gender parity index (GPI) for lower secondary school adjusted NAR ²	Upper secondary school adjusted net attendance ratio (NAR), girls	Upper secondary school adjusted net attendance ratio (NAR), boys	Upper secondary school adjusted net attendance ratio (NAR), total	Gender parity index (GPI) for upper secondary school adjusted NAR ²
Total^{2A}	96.3	97.3	96.9	0.99	94.5	95.7	95.1	0.99	82.3	86.8	84.6	0.95
Area												
Urban	95.8	97.3	97.3	0.98	94.5	95.6	95.1	0.99	82.7	91.5	87.0	0.90
Rural	97.2	97.3	96.3	1.00	94.3	96.0	95.3	0.98	81.7	80.4	81.0	1.02
Mother's education^{B,C}												
Kindergarten or none	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Primary or Lower Secondary	(93.4)	(100.0)	96.3	(0.9)	(*)	(*)	(92.6)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)
Upper Secondary	97.3	96.4	96.8	1.01	98.0	97.1	97.5	1.01	80.2	80.9	80.6	0.99
Vocational Education	97.5	98.5	98.1	0.99	89.8	96.8	93.3	0.93	(*)	(97.8)	90.1	(*)
Higher	95.7	97.2	96.5	0.99	96.4	93.5	94.9	1.03	91.8	(93.7)	92.7	(1.0)

Table LN.2.8: Parity indices

Ratio of adjusted net attendance ratios of girls to boys, in primary, lower and upper secondary school, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

Parity indices	Primary school				Lower secondary school				Upper secondary school				
	Primary school adjusted net attendance ratio (NAR), girls	Primary school adjusted net attendance ratio (NAR), boys	Primary school adjusted net attendance ratio (NAR), total ¹	Gender parity index (GPI) for primary school adjusted NAR ²	Lower secondary school adjusted net attendance ratio (NAR), girls	Lower secondary school adjusted net attendance ratio (NAR), boys	Lower secondary school adjusted net attendance ratio (NAR), total ¹	Gender parity index (GPI) for lower secondary school adjusted NAR ²	Upper secondary school adjusted net attendance ratio (NAR), girls	Upper secondary school adjusted net attendance ratio (NAR), boys	Upper secondary school adjusted net attendance ratio (NAR), total ¹	Gender parity index (GPI) for upper secondary school adjusted NAR ²	
Rural/Urban ¹	1.0	1.0	1.0	na	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.9	na

¹ FFLS indicator LN.11c - Parity indices - primary, lower and upper secondary attendance (area); SDG indicator 4.5.1

² FFLS indicator LN.11a - Parity indices - primary, lower and upper secondary attendance (gender); SDG indicator 4.5.1

^A The characteristics of "Region", "Ethnicity of household head" and "Orphanhood" are not presented in the table, due to the small number of unweighted cases within each category.

^B Does not include children aged 15–17 who have been released from parental guardianship, and children aged 18 and older at the time of the interview.

^C Don't know/Missing has been suppressed from the table due to a small number of unweighted cases.

na: not applicable

() Figures that are based on 25–49 unweighted cases.

(*) Figures that are based on fewer than 25 unweighted cases.

“-“ Denotes 0 unweighted case in the denominator or in the column.

5.3 Parental involvement

Parental involvement in their children's education process has a positive impact on the quality of their learning. For example, reading activities at home have a significant positive influence on their reading achievements, language comprehension, and expressive language skills.⁴ Research also shows that parental involvement in their children's education process is a positive, long-term indicator of their children's later educational achievement.⁵

In addition to learning activities at home, parents' involvement in school activities (such as attending meetings, talking with teachers, attending school events, and volunteering at school) also promotes students' academic achievement.⁶ Studies have shown that the effect of parental involvement in school activities during the primary school age period may be much greater than the differences associated with school quality, social status, and ethnic group.⁷

Parental involvement is presented in tables LN.3.1, LN.3.2, and LN.3.3.

Table LN.3.1 presents the percentage of children aged 7-14 who attend an educational institution, including the percentage of children whose household adult member received the student's academic report card, as well as adults' involvement in school governance and school activities during the past 12 months.

Table LN.3.2 presents the percentage of children aged 7-14 who missed a lesson due to teacher absence or school closure, by reasons, and the percentage of adult household members who contacted school administration or school governing body representatives due to teacher strike/teacher absence.

Table LN.3.3 presents the percentage of children aged 7-14 who have 3 or more books to read at home, who read books or are read to at home, who attend school and have homework, who speak at home the language used by teachers at school, and who receive help with homework.

⁴ Gest, D. et al. "Shared Book Reading and Children's Language Comprehension Skills: The Moderating Role of Parental Discipline Practices." *Early Childhood Research Quarterly* 19, no. 2 (2004): 319-36. doi:10.1016/j.ecresq.2004.04.007.

⁵ Fluori, E. and A. Buchanan. "Early Father's and Mother's Involvement and Child's Later Educational Outcomes." *Educational Psychology* 74, no. 2 (2004): 141-53. doi:10.1348/000709904773839806.

⁶ Pomerantz, M., E. Moorman and S. Litwack. "The How, Whom, and Why of Parents' Involvement in Children's Academic Lives: More Is Not Always Better." *Review of Educational Research* 77, no. 3 (2007): 373-410. doi:10.3102/003465430305567.

⁷ Desforges, C. and A. Abouchar. *The Impact of Parental Involvement, Parental Support and Family Education on Pupil Achievements and Adjustment: A Literature Review*. Research report. Nottingham: Queen's Printer, 2003. https://www.nationalnumeracy.org.uk/sites/default/files/the_impact_of_parental_involvement.pdf.

Table LN.3.1: Support for child learning at school

Percentage of children age 7-14 attending school and, among those, percentage of children for whom an adult member of the household received a report card for the child, and involvement of adults in school management and school activities in the last year, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Percentage of children attending school ^a	Number of children age 7-14	Percentage of children for whom an adult household member in the last year received a report card for the child ^b	Involvement by adult in school management in last year		Involvement by adult in school activities in last year			Number of children age 7-14 years attending school
				School has a governing body open to parents ²	Attended a meeting called by governing body ³	A meeting discussed key education/ financial issues ⁴	Attended school celebration or a sport event	Met with teachers to discuss child's progress ⁵	
Total	100.0	1,780	64.0	75.2	33.0	25.1	72.8	86.4	1,779
Sex									
Male	99.9	945	62.6	74.6	33.8	26.2	71.2	86.6	944
Female	100.0	835	65.6	75.8	32.0	23.9	74.7	86.2	835
Area									
Urban	100.0	1,155	63.2	75.5	32.4	26.6	67.9	87.6	1,155
Rural	99.9	625	65.5	74.4	34.1	22.4	82.1	84.2	624
Region									
Tbilisi	100.0	660	58.3	70.9	23.3	19.9	65.3	87.1	660
Adjara A.R	100.0	168	70.6	63.3	49.2	42.0	68.9	87.8	168
Guria	100.0	45	98.7	65.4	14.8	12.3	97.4	99.3	45
Imereti	100.0	183	46.0	80.2	17.4	11.9	70.9	90.1	183
Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti	100.0	7	59.2	82.2	18.5	18.5	88.3	100.0	7
Kakheti	100.0	123	36.6	72.6	19.6	15.3	80.6	84.4	123
Mtskheta-Mtianeti	100.0	45	35.3	95.3	19.2	6.4	33.4	24.8	45
Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti	100.0	135	94.8	67.3	27.9	27.2	98.4	98.4	135
Samtskhe-Javakheti	100.0	59	53.0	41.3	14.1	12.6	93.4	85.8	59
Kvemo Kartli	99.7	246	92.5	99.0	87.0	54.9	90.7	87.3	245
Shida Kartli	100.0	110	51.2	83.2	16.9	15.1	41.7	79.6	110

Table LN.3.1: Support for child learning at school

Percentage of children age 7-14 attending school and, among those, percentage of children for whom an adult member of the household received a report card for the child, and involvement of adults in school management and school activities in the last year, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Percentage of children attending school ^A	Number of children age 7-14	Percentage of children for whom an adult household member in the last year received a report card for the child ^B	Involvement by adult in school management in last year			Involvement by adult in school activities in last year			Number of children age 7-14 years attending school
				School has a governing body open to parents ²	Attended a meeting by governing body ³	A meeting discussed key education/ financial issues ⁴	Attended school celebration or a sport event	Met with teachers to discuss child's progress ⁵		
Age at beginning of school year										
6 ^A	100.0	82	65.5	86.2	36.8	30.7	90.7	83.2	82	
7	100.0	219	54.6	71.6	28.9	21.7	82.6	88.4	219	
8	100.0	238	60.5	69.8	30.7	24.6	84.4	89.0	238	
9	100.0	263	59.0	74.9	30.1	20.3	79.2	84.3	263	
10	100.0	250	65.6	73.9	34.7	26.2	77.6	89.4	250	
11	100.0	188	70.0	74.2	29.9	20.1	67.7	82.4	188	
12	100.0	207	69.4	81.9	34.6	29.6	64.1	85.8	207	
13	100.0	230	67.4	73.5	39.1	30.2	53.2	86.3	230	
14	99.2	103.6	69.9	81.9	35.1	28.0	54.2	86.2	103	
Attendance at Educational Institution^B										
Primary	100.0	1259	62.0	74.1	31.5	23.2	79.5	86.7	1,259	
Lower Secondary	100.0	520	68.7	77.7	36.5	29.9	56.7	85.8	520	
Mother's education^C										
Kindergarten or none	-	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	0	
Primary or Lower Secondary	99.3	107	78.8	74.1	55.6	23.6	82.4	86.8	106	
Upper Secondary	100.0	523	58.8	75.0	29.6	22.0	73.6	83.6	523	
Vocational Education	100.0	245	67.4	64.3	29.5	26.3	74.7	89.7	245	
Higher	100.0	777	64.4	80.0	33.8	27.9	71.6	88.8	777	

Table LN.3.1: Support for child learning at school

Percentage of children age 7-14 attending school and, among those, percentage of children for whom an adult member of the household received a report card for the child, and involvement of adults in school management and school activities in the last year, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Percentage of children attending school ^A	Number of children age 7-14	Percentage of children for whom an adult household member in the last year received a report card for the child ^B	Involvement by adult in school management in last year			Involvement by adult in school activities in last year			Number of children age 7-14 years attending school
				School has a governing body open to parents ²	Attended a meeting called by governing body ³	A meeting discussed key education/ financial issues ⁴	Attended school celebration or a sport event	Met with teachers to discuss child's progress ⁵		
School Management^{C,D}										
Public	100.0	1,682	63.8	75.8	33.3	25.2	72.3	86.2	1,682	
Private	100.0	95	66.5	63.2	28.4	24.0	81.8	90.3	95	
Child's functional difficulties										
Has functional difficulty	99.2	102	65.6	83.7	45.8	36.2	73.9	93.3	101	
Has no functional difficulty	100.0	1,678	63.9	74.6	32.2	24.5	72.8	86.0	1,678	
Mother's functional difficulties										
Has functional difficulty	(100.0)	69	(52.0)	(69.8)	(37.9)	(33.3)	(72.3)	(79.4)	69	
Has no functional difficulty	100.0	1,711	64.5	75.4	32.8	24.8	72.9	86.7	1,710	
Ethnicity of household head										
Georgian	100.0	1,587	62.3	74.4	29.5	25.4	70.8	87.0	1,587	
Azerbaijani	99.4	133	90.7	99.0	77.6	22.2	96.9	76.5	132	
Armenian	100.0	51	54.8	45.7	31.4	29.5	82.9	95.3	51	
Other	(*)	9	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	9	
Wealth index quintile										
Poorest	99.8	387	55.1	66.7	25.9	19.2	73.9	86.3	387	
Second	100.0	354	68.7	76.4	35.3	25.8	75.5	84.2	354	
Middle	100.0	360	69.3	74.5	31.2	24.0	70.7	83.9	360	
Fourth	100.0	337	63.2	83.9	39.2	30.7	69.0	90.2	337	
Richest	100.0	341	64.3	75.6	34.3	26.8	74.9	88.0	341	

Table LN.3.1: Support for child learning at school

Percentage of children age 7-14 attending school and, among those, percentage of children for whom an adult member of the household received a report card for the child, and involvement of adults in school management and school activities in the last year, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

Percentage of children attending school ^A	Number of children age 7-14	Percentage of children for whom an adult household member in the last year received a report card for the child ^B	Involvement by adult in school management in last year		Involvement by adult in school activities in last year		Number of children age 7-14 years attending school	
			School has a governing body open to parents ²	Attended meeting called by governing body ³	A meeting discussed key education/ financial issues ⁴	Attended school celebration or a sport event		Met with teachers to discuss child's progress ⁵
			<p>¹ FFLS indicator LN.12 - Availability of information on children's school performance</p> <p>² FFLS indicator LN.13 - Opportunity to participate in School Management</p> <p>³ FFLS indicator LN.14: Participation in school management</p> <p>⁴ FFLS indicator LN.15 - Effective participation in school management</p> <p>⁵ FFLS indicator LN.16 - Discussion with teachers regarding children's progress</p>					
<p>^A Given that eligibility for participation in the study was determined by the age reached at the time of the interview (age 7-14), the disaggregation 'Age at the beginning of the school year' represents children who were 6 years old at the beginning of the school year.</p> <p>^B The attendance rate at an educational institution in this table is not directly comparable to the net attendance rate shown in the previous tables, which uses all children included in the sample for calculation. The results shown in this and subsequent tables are for the modules on parental involvement and fundamental learning skills, which are calculated using information received from the mother, for children aged 7-14.</p> <p>^C Don't know/Missing has been suppressed from the table due to a small number of unweighted cases.</p> <p>^D Information on the governance of the educational institution was collected for children who are attending primary school or a higher level of education. Children out of school and children attending kindergarten are not included in the table.</p> <p>() Figures that are based on 25-49 unweighted cases.</p> <p>(*) Figures that are based on fewer than 25 unweighted cases.</p> <p>“-“ Denotes 0 unweighted case in the denominator or in the column.</p>								

Table LN.3.2: School-related reasons for inability to attend class

Percentage of children age 7-14 not able to attend class due to absence of teacher or school closure, by reason for inability, and percentage of adult household members contacting school officials or governing body representatives on instances of teacher strike or absence, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Percentage of children who attend class due to absence of teacher or school closure	Number of children age 7-14 years attending school	Percentage of children unable to attend class in the last year due to a school-related reason:							Number of children age 7-14 who could not attend class in the last year due to a school-related reason	Percentage of adult household members contacting school officials or governing body representatives on instances of teacher strike or absence	Number of children age 7-14 years in the last year due to teacher strike or absence
			Natural disasters	Man-made disasters	Teacher strike	Other	Teacher absence	Teacher strike or absence	Number of children age 7-14 who could not attend class in the last year due to a school-related reason			
Total^A	17.4	1,779	16.3	3.0	3.2	22.7	70.4	70.4	309	17.2	218	
Sex												
Male	17.4	944	13.7	5.7	3.3	24.4	67.9	67.9	165	21.4	112	
Female	17.3	835	19.2	0.0	3.0	20.9	73.3	73.3	144	12.8	106	
Area												
Urban	17.8	1,155	7.1	4.4	0.9	29.4	73.9	73.9	206	21.4	152	
Rural	16.5	624	34.7	0.3	7.8	9.4	63.5	63.5	103	7.5	65	
Age at beginning of school year												
6 ^B	7.7	82	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	6	(*)	4	
7	11.6	219	(21.4)	(0.0)	(3.1)	(39.9)	(55.3)	(55.3)	25	(*)	14	
8	11.2	238	(39.1)	(1.2)	(4.1)	(24.0)	(46.5)	(46.5)	27	(*)	12	
9	20.0	263	14.3	0.0	0.0	26.7	69.2	69.2	53	(13.8)	36	
10	19.2	250	(8.5)	(11.6)	(5.3)	(19.3)	(69.8)	(69.8)	48	(21.7)	34	
11	17.2	188	(16.8)	(10.7)	(0.0)	(37.5)	(57.0)	(57.0)	32	(*)	18	
12	24.4	207	15.9	0.0	1.6	14.6	85.8	85.8	50	(29.1)	43	
13	20.3	230	7.4	0.0	5.0	19.8	82.6	82.6	47	(19.7)	39	
14	19.9	103	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	20	(*)	17	
Attendance at Educational Institution												
Primary	15.6	1,259	17.3	4.8	2.3	27.7	62.9	62.9	197	15.0	124	
Lower Secondary	21.6	520	14.4	0.0	4.7	14.1	83.7	83.7	112	20.1	94	

Table LN.3.2: School-related reasons for inability to attend class

Percentage of children age 7-14 not able to attend class due to absence of teacher or school closure, by reason for inability, and percentage of adult household members contacting school officials or governing body representatives on instances of teacher strike or absence, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Percentage of children who attend class due to absence of teacher or school closure in the last year could not	Number of children age 7-14 years attending school	Percentage of children unable to attend class in the last year due to a school-related reason:						Number of children age 7-14 who could not attend class in the last year due to a school-related reason	Percentage of adult household members contacting school officials or governing body representatives on instances of teacher strike or absence	Number of children age 7-14 years who could not attend class in the last year due to teacher strike or absence
			Natural disasters	Man-made disasters	Teacher strike	Other	Teacher absence	Teacher strike or absence			
Mother's education^c											
Kindergarten or none	-	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0	
Primary or Lower Secondary	24.2	106	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	26	
Upper Secondary	14.7	523	24.5	0.0	1.0	13.2	71.5	71.5	6.8	55	
Vocational Education	20.3	245	20.7	7.0	2.0	17.9	67.1	67.1	(28.8)	33	
Higher	17.8	777	12.1	4.0	0.0	33.2	65.1	65.1	23.6	90	
School Management^{c,d}											
Public	17.4	1,682	16.4	0.8	3.3	23.2	71.6	71.6	17.9	209	
Private	17.7	95	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	9	
Child's functional difficulties											
Has functional difficulty	22.7	101	24.9	0.0	0.0	15.2	77.2	77.2	32.8	18	
Has no functional difficulty	17.0	1,678	15.6	3.3	3.4	23.3	69.9	69.9	15.8	200	
Mother's functional difficulties											
Has functional difficulty	(22.9)	69	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	18.2	206	
Has no functional difficulty	17.1	1,710	15.8	3.2	3.3	23.2	70.1	70.1	(*)	12	
Ethnicity of household head											
Georgian	16.0	1,587	19.2	3.7	0.1	27.0	64.3	64.3	20.8	163	
Azerbaijani	28.9	132	(0.0)	(0.0)	(24.8)	(4.1)	(100.0)	(100.0)	(0.0)	38	
Armenian	25.7	51	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	13	
Other	(*)	9	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	4	

Table LN.3.2: School-related reasons for inability to attend class

Percentage of children age 7-14 not able to attend class due to absence of teacher or school closure, by reason for inability, and percentage of adult household members contacting school officials or governing body representatives on instances of teacher strike or absence, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

Wealth index quintile	Percentage of children unable to attend class in the last year due to a school-related reason:										Number of children age 7-14 years attending school	Percentage of children who attend class due to absence of teacher or school closure	Number of children age 7-14 who could not attend class in the last year due to a school-related reason	Percentage of adult household members contacting school officials or governing body representatives on instances of teacher strike or absence	Number of children age 7-14 years who could not attend class in the last year due to teacher strike or absence
	Natural disasters	Man-made disasters	Teacher strike	Other	Teacher absence	Teacher strike or absence	Number of children age 7-14 who could not attend class in the last year due to a school-related reason	Percentage of adult household members contacting school officials or governing body representatives on instances of teacher strike or absence	Number of children age 7-14 years who could not attend class in the last year due to teacher strike or absence						
Poorest	13.4	27.5	0.6	4.0	9.1	66.6	66.6	52	(12.1)	35					
Second	19.4	15.0	0.0	6.6	16.6	83.7	83.7	69	9.9	58					
Middle	21.3	15.8	0.0	3.1	25.0	70.9	70.9	77	14.7	54					
Fourth	15.0	14.1	4.2	1.6	35.1	67.3	67.3	50	(23.1)	34					
Richest	17.9	(10.4)	(11.4)	(0.0)	(28.1)	(60.7)	(60.7)	61	(31.6)	37					

¹ FFLS indicator LN.17 - Contact with school concerning teacher strike or absence

^A The characteristics of "Region" are not presented in the table, due to the small number of unweighted cases within each category.
^B Given that eligibility for participation in the study was determined by the age reached at the time of the interview (age 7-14), the disaggregation 'Age at the beginning of the school year' represents children who were 6 years old at the beginning of the school year.
^C Don't know/Missing has been suppressed from the table due to a small number of unweighted cases.
^D Information on the governance of the educational institution was collected for children who are attending primary school or a higher level of education. Children out of school and children attending kindergarten are not included in the table.
 () Figures that are based on 25-49 unweighted cases.
 (*) Figures that are based on fewer than 25 unweighted cases.
 "..." Denotes 0 unweighted case in the denominator or in the column.

Table LN.3.3: Learning environment at home

Percentage of children age 7-14 years with 3 or more books to read and percentage who read or are read to at home, percentage of children age 7-14 years attending school who have homework and percentage who at home speak the language that teachers use at school, and percentage of children age 7-14 years attending school and having homework who receive help with homework, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Percentage of children with 3 or more books to read at home ¹	Number of children age 7-14 years	Percentage of children who read books or are read to at home ²	Number of children age 7-14 years	Percentage of children who have homework	Number of children age 7-14 years attending school	Percentage of children who attend school using the language also used by teachers at school ³	Number of children age 7-14 years attending school	Percentage of children who receive help with homework ⁴	Number of children age 7-14 attending school and have homework
Total	87.3	1,780	87.0	1,780	99.1	1,779	97.3	1,779	60.1	1,763
Sex										
Male	85.3	945	82.4	945	99.7	944	97.3	944	62.3	942
Female	89.5	835	92.3	835	98.3	835	97.3	835	57.7	821
Area										
Urban	94.0	1,155	85.8	1,155	98.9	1,155	98.6	1,155	62.4	1,142
Rural	75.0	625	89.2	625	99.4	624	94.9	624	55.9	620
Region										
Tbilisi	98.6	660	84.6	660	98.9	660	100.0	660	64.8	652
Adjara A.R	65.1	168	76.5	168	98.3	168	100.0	168	63.1	165
Guria	99.1	45	97.4	45	98.1	45	99.1	45	39.6	44
Imereti	94.8	183	86.8	183	99.6	183	99.7	183	62.7	182
Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti	98.4	7	89.5	7	90.3	7	98.7	7	58.7	6
Kakheti	96.2	123	90.3	123	100.0	123	99.2	123	49.4	123
Mtskheta-Mtianeti	98.6	45	97.7	45	98.8	45	100.0	45	54.0	45
Samgrelo-Zemo Svaneti	95.5	135	99.5	135	99.6	135	100.0	135	53.0	134
Samtskhe-Javakheti	67.3	59	60.5	59	98.7	59	94.8	59	56.2	58
Kvemo Kartli	52.7	246	93.0	246	99.5	245	82.6	245	57.1	244
Shida Kartli	98.9	110	90.7	110	99.1	110	100.0	110	63.9	109

Table LN.3.3: Learning environment at home

Percentage of children age 7-14 years with 3 or more books to read and percentage who read or are read to at home, percentage of children age 7-14 years attending school who have homework and percentage who at home speak the language that teachers use at school, and percentage of children age 7-14 years attending school and having homework who receive help with homework, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Percentage of children with 3 or more books to read at home ¹	Number of children age 7-14 years	Percentage of children who read books or are read to at home ²	Number of children age 7-14 years	Percentage of children who have homework	Number of children age 7-14 years attending school	Percentage of children who at home use the language also used by teachers at school ³	Number of children age 7-14 years attending school	Percentage of children who receive help with homework ⁴	Number of children age 7-14 attending school and have homework
Age at beginning of school year										
6 ^A	77.0	82	88.4	82	100.0	82	95.7	82	89.5	82
7	83.9	219	88.6	219	99.4	219	97.8	219	87.9	217
8	87.9	238	85.9	238	97.2	238	97.8	238	79.5	231
9	86.6	263	89.5	263	98.9	263	96.2	263	73.2	260
10	87.6	250	86.3	250	100.0	250	96.7	250	60.3	250
11	88.7	188	87.0	188	99.5	188	98.2	188	48.4	187
12	93.7	207	91.2	207	98.9	207	98.2	207	42.5	204
13	88.3	230	81.2	230	99.2	230	96.7	230	33.0	229
14	84.9	104	85.4	104	99.5	103	98.7	103	17.2	102
Attendance at Educational Institution										
Primary	86.2	1,259	87.5	1,259	99.1	1,259	97.2	1,259	71.1	1,247
Lower Secondary	90.0	520	86.0	520	99.1	520	97.6	520	33.4	515
Out of School	(*)	1	(*)	1	-	0	-	0	-	0
Mother's education^B										
Kindergarten or none	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0
Primary or Lower Secondary	46.5	107	87.7	107	99.7	106	75.5	106	61.2	105
Upper Secondary	423.9	523	429.2	523	99.3	523	97.2	523	59.1	519
Vocational Education	227.5	245	208.3	245	99.7	245	99.6	245	58.4	244
Higher	745.0	777	710.1	777	98.9	777	99.8	777	62.2	769
Child's functional difficulties										
Has functional difficulty	86.0	102	82.9	102	93.2	101	96.2	999	59.5	94
Has no functional difficulty	87.4	1,678	87.3	1,678	99.4	1,678	98.8	780	60.2	1,669

Table LN.3.3: Learning environment at home

Percentage of children age 7-14 years with 3 or more books to read and percentage who read or are read to at home, percentage of children age 7-14 years attending school who have homework and percentage who at home speak the language that teachers use at school, and percentage of children age 7-14 years attending school and having homework who receive help with homework, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Percentage of children with 3 or more books to read at home ¹	Number of children age 7-14 years	Percentage of children who read books or are read to at home ²	Number of children age 7-14 years	Percentage of children who have homework	Number of children age 7-14 years attending school	Percentage of children who at home use the language also used by teachers at school ³	Number of children age 7-14 years attending school	Percentage of children who receive help with homework ⁴	Number of children age 7-14 attending school and have homework
Mother's functional difficulties										
Has functional difficulty	(90.8)	69	(92.0)	69	(93.0)	69	(96.4)	69	(65.2)	64
Has no functional difficulty	87.2	1,711	86.8	1,711	99.3	1,710	97.3	1,710	59.9	1,699
Ethnicity of household head										
Georgian	94.2	1,587	87.3	1,587	99.0	1,587	99.9	1,587	59.8	1,571
Azerbaijani	17.2	133	97.2	133	100.0	132	67.6	132	62.4	132
Armenian	55.6	51	56.6	51	100.0	51	94.1	51	61.3	51
Other	(*)	9	(*)	9	(*)	9	(*)	9	(*)	9
Wealth index quintile										
Poorest	76.6	387	80.8	387	98.8	387	97.4	387	57.3	382
Second	79.1	354	85.9	354	99.9	354	94.9	354	61.8	353
Middle	91.7	360	89.2	360	99.4	360	95.9	360	57.4	358
Fourth	96.5	337	93.6	337	99.2	337	99.1	337	63.6	334
Richest	94.2	341	86.4	341	98.1	341	99.5	341	61.0	335

¹ FFLS indicator LN.18 - Availability of books at home

² FFLS indicator LN.19 - Reading habit at home

³ FFLS indicator LN.20 - School and home languages

⁴ FFLS indicator LN.21 - Support with homework

^A As eligibility for survey was determined based on age at time of interview (age 7-14 years), the disaggregate of Age at beginning of school year inevitably presents children who were age 6 years at the beginning of the school year.

^B Don't know has been suppressed from the table due to a small number of unweighted cases

() Figures that are based on 25-49 unweighted cases

(*) Figures that are based on fewer than 25 unweighted cases

"-" Denotes 0 unweighted cases in the denominator

5.4 Foundational learning skills

The main subject of the study was the assessment of foundational learning skills in children aged 7-14.

Table LN.4.1 provides detailed information on foundational reading skills, specifically the percentage of children aged 7-14 who demonstrated foundational reading skills by successfully completing three foundational reading skills tasks in Georgian, Armenian, or Azerbaijani languages, by sex.

Table LN.4.2 presents foundational mathematics skills, the percentage of children aged 7-14 who demonstrated foundational numeracy skills by successfully completing four foundational numeracy skills tasks, by sex.

Table LN.4.1: Foundational reading skills

Percentage of children aged 7-14 years who demonstrate foundational reading skills by successfully completing three foundational reading tasks in Georgian, Armenian or Azerbaijani, by sex Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Male				Female				Total							
	Percentage who correctly answered comprehension questions		Number of children age 7-14 years	Percentage who demonstrate foundational reading skills	Percentage who correctly answered comprehension questions		Number of children age 7-14 years	Percentage who demonstrate foundational reading skills	Percentage who correctly answered comprehension questions		Number of children age 7-14 years	Percentage who demonstrate foundational reading skills	Gender Parity Index for foundational reading skills ^{4,5,6}	Number of children age 7-14 years ⁵		
	Three literal	Two inferential			Three literal	Two inferential			Three literal	Two inferential						
Total^{1,4,A,B}	86.6	68.4	71.6	66.0	943	89.5	72.3	74.8	68.2	835	88.0	70.2	73.1	67.0	1.03	1,778
Area																
Urban	86.0	70.1	71.5	67.4	607	89.4	72.3	74.4	67.8	548	87.6	71.1	72.9	67.6	1.00	1,155
Rural	87.8	65.3	71.7	63.3	336	89.7	72.4	75.7	69.0	287	88.7	68.6	73.5	65.9	1.09	623
Region																
Tbilisi	85.8	69.8	72.1	68.1	357	87.1	68.0	71.1	63.2	302	86.4	69.0	71.6	65.8	0.93	660
Adjara A.R	90.7	70.7	67.6	67.6	94	93.5	82.0	77.3	77.3	73	92.0	75.7	71.8	71.8	1.14	168
Guria	90.4	81.6	81.8	76.4	23	96.2	83.3	80.4	76.3	22	93.3	82.5	81.1	76.4	1.00	45
Imereti	89.3	75.7	80.2	72.7	90	94.0	80.4	84.9	77.3	92	91.7	78.1	82.6	75.0	1.06	182
Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti	(89.6)	(78.4)	(78.6)	(67.4)	3	(93.6)	(70.2)	(76.5)	(67.1)	4	91.8	74.0	77.5	67.3	(1.00)	7
Kakheti	95.9	81.8	84.9	78.1	59	95.2	83.3	86.9	81.7	63	95.6	82.6	85.9	79.9	1.05	122
Mtskheta-Mtianeti	(100.0)	(90.1)	(87.0)	(84.7)	24	(100.0)	(95.7)	(100.0)	(95.7)	21	100.0	92.7	93.1	89.9	(1.13)	45
Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti	89.6	81.5	81.5	80.1	70	91.4	80.3	78.0	77.4	65	90.4	80.9	79.8	78.8	0.97	135
Samtskhe-Javakheti	93.2	47.6	66.5	43.0	35	88.6	65.0	74.6	62.2	23	91.4	54.5	69.7	50.6	1.45	59
Kvemo Kartli	77.2	56.6	63.6	54.7	136	83.6	61.8	66.2	56.4	110	80.1	59.0	64.8	55.5	1.03	246
Shida Kartli	78.1	37.8	44.4	36.3	52	86.3	59.2	63.8	54.7	58	82.4	49.0	54.5	46.0	1.51	110

Table LN.4.1: Foundational reading skills

Percentage of children aged 7-14 years who demonstrate foundational reading skills by successfully completing three foundational reading tasks in Georgian, Armenian or Azerbaijani, by sex Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

Age at beginning of school year	Male				Female				Total							
	Percentage who correctly read 90% of words in a story		Percentage who demonstrate foundational reading skills		Percentage who correctly read 90% of words in a story		Percentage who demonstrate foundational reading skills		Percentage who correctly answered comprehension questions		Percentage of children who demonstrate foundational reading skills ^{1,2,3,7,8,9}		Gender Parity Index for foundational reading skills ^{4,5,6}		Number of children age 7-14 years ⁵	
	Three literal	Two inferential	Three literal	Two inferential	Three literal	Two inferential	Three literal	Two inferential	Three literal	Two inferential	Three literal	Two inferential				
6 ^C	(47.1)	(32.0)	(35.4)	(29.2)	45	(43.6)	(21.0)	(20.7)	(19.8)	38	45.5	27.0	28.7	24.9	(0.68)	82
7-8 ^{2,5}	73.5	51.9	57.7	50.0	234	79.6	60.8	65.4	58.3	222	76.5	56.2	61.5	54.0	1.17	456
7	63.5	47.9	49.2	47.1	111	75.3	52.4	58.3	49.5	108	69.3	50.1	53.7	48.3	1.05	219
8	82.6	55.5	65.4	52.6	123	83.6	68.7	72.1	66.5	115	83.1	61.9	68.6	59.3	1.27	238
9	84.2	66.8	69.0	63.8	146	93.8	74.4	77.5	70.4	116	88.4	70.2	72.7	66.7	1.10	263
10-14	96.7	79.4	81.7	77.0	518	97.0	81.6	83.2	76.4	459	96.8	80.4	82.4	76.7	0.99	977
10	95.0	74.9	80.8	74.6	138	96.1	80.4	75.7	66.7	111	95.5	77.3	78.5	71.1	0.89	249
11	98.9	77.2	76.1	73.1	90	98.1	83.6	86.0	81.7	98	98.5	80.6	81.2	77.6	1.12	188
12	96.3	78.9	79.6	75.8	105	93.6	83.6	87.2	81.7	102	95.0	81.2	83.3	78.7	1.08	207
13	98.3	82.6	85.4	79.2	130	99.1	76.4	82.6	73.2	100	98.7	79.9	84.2	76.6	0.92	229
14	93.8	87.6	88.3	86.1	55	100.0	86.3	87.4	83.1	48	96.7	87.0	87.8	84.7	0.96	104

Table LN.4.1: Foundational reading skills

Percentage of children aged 7-14 years who demonstrate foundational reading skills by successfully completing three foundational reading tasks in Georgian, Armenian or Azerbaijani, by sex Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Male			Female			Total							
	Percentage who correctly read 90% of words in a story	Percentage who correctly answered comprehension questions		Percentage who correctly read 90% of words in a story	Percentage who correctly answered comprehension questions		Percentage who correctly read 90% of words in a story	Percentage who correctly answered comprehension questions		Number of children age 7-14 years	Percentage of children who demonstrate foundational reading skills	Number of children age 7-14 years ^F	Gender Parity Index for foundational reading skills ^{4,5,6}	Percentage of children who demonstrate foundational reading skills ^{1,2,3,7,8,9}
		Three literal	Two inferential		Three literal	Two inferential		Three literal	Two inferential					
Mother's education^P														
Kindergarten or none	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0	-	0	-	-
Primary or Lower Secondary	72.5	42.6	49.3	41.1	64.4	90.6	66.0	64.4	81.6	53	58.9	107	1.43	50.0
Upper Secondary	85.5	62.0	65.6	59.1	74.7	89.5	71.6	74.7	87.3	237	68.6	522	1.16	63.4
Vocational Education	79.9	64.2	66.0	61.6	71.9	85.7	75.6	71.9	82.7	116	66.2	245	1.08	63.8
Higher	90.7	76.6	79.1	74.0	77.1	89.9	71.1	77.1	90.3	378	69.0	776	0.93	71.6
Child's functional difficulties														
Has functional difficulty	(67.1)	(43.2)	(43.2)	(43.2)	63.9	77.8	63.5	63.9	72.6	51	58.4	101	(1.35)	50.9
Has no functional difficulty	87.7	69.8	73.1	67.2	75.6	90.3	72.9	75.6	88.9	784	68.8	1,677	1.02	68.0
Mother's functional difficulties														
Has functional difficulty	(87.2)	(69.1)	(77.1)	(69.1)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(93.2)	32	(*)	69	(*)	(68.4)
Has no functional difficulty	86.6	68.4	71.3	65.8	74.8	89.1	72.2	74.8	87.8	803	68.2	1,709	1.04	67.0

Table LN.4.1: Foundational reading skills

Percentage of children aged 7-14 years who demonstrate foundational reading skills by successfully completing three foundational reading tasks in Georgian, Armenian or Azerbaijani, by sex Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Male				Female				Total							
	Percentage who correctly answered comprehension questions		Number of children age 7-14 years	Percentage who demonstrate foundational reading skills	Percentage who correctly answered comprehension questions		Number of children age 7-14 years	Percentage who demonstrate foundational reading skills	Percentage who correctly answered comprehension questions		Number of children age 7-14 years	Percentage who demonstrate foundational reading skills	Gender Parity Index for foundational reading skills ^{4,5,6}			
	Three literal	Two inferential	90% of words in a story	90% of words in a story	Three literal	Two inferential	90% of words in a story	90% of words in a story	Three literal	Two inferential	90% of words in a story	90% of words in a story	1.23,7,8,9			
Ethnicity of household head																
Georgian	88.1	71.4	74.0	69.0	841	90.0	74.1	76.8	70.3	745	89.0	72.7	75.3	69.6	1.02	1,586
Azerbaijani	73.2	41.8	49.1	38.3	74	84.1	52.0	53.8	41.8	59	78.0	46.4	51.2	39.9	1.09	133
Armenian	(74.4)	(55.3)	(64.8)	(54.0)	25	(87.6)	(65.9)	(66.5)	(64.7)	27	81.2	60.7	65.7	59.5	1.20	51
Other	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	4	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	5	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	9
Wealth index quintile																
Poorest	83.1	63.4	67.0	62.1	215	85.5	66.8	70.7	64.0	170	84.2	64.9	68.6	62.9	1.03	386
Second	87.7	70.0	70.0	65.7	190	89.1	65.6	69.5	60.7	164	88.4	67.9	69.7	63.4	0.92	354
Middle	85.8	65.0	72.1	63.4	181	89.5	71.0	72.5	67.1	179	87.7	68.0	72.3	65.3	1.06	360
Fourth	90.7	66.4	68.2	63.1	162	90.9	81.2	83.8	78.1	175	90.8	74.1	76.3	70.9	1.24	337
Richest	86.9	77.3	80.5	75.2	194	92.9	77.3	77.8	70.9	147	89.5	77.3	79.3	73.4	0.94	341

Table LN.4.1: Foundational reading skills

Percentage of children aged 7-14 years who demonstrate foundational reading skills by successfully completing three foundational reading tasks in Georgian, Armenian or Azerbaijani, by sex Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Male			Female			Total			
	Percentage who correctly read 90% of words in a story	Percentage who correctly answered comprehension questions	Number of children age 7-14 years	Percentage who correctly read 90% of words in a story	Percentage who correctly answered comprehension questions	Number of children age 7-14 years	Percentage of children who demonstrate foundational reading skills	Percentage who correctly read 90% of words in a story	Percentage who correctly answered comprehension questions	Number of children age 7-14 years ⁵
Parity indices										
Wealth										
Poorest/Richest ⁷	0.96	0.82	0.83	0.92	0.86	0.91	0.90	0.94	0.84	0.86
Area										
Rural/Urban ⁸	1.02	0.93	0.94	1.00	1.00	1.02	1.02	1.01	0.96	0.98
Functional difficulties										
Difficulties/No difficulties ⁹	(0.77)	(0.62)	(0.59)	0.86	0.87	0.85	0.85	0.82	0.75	0.75

¹ FFLS indicator LN.22a - Foundational reading and numeracy skills (reading, age 7-14)

² FFLS indicator LN.22b - Foundational reading and numeracy skills (reading, age for grade 2/3)

³ FFLS indicator LN.22c - Foundational reading and numeracy skills (reading, attending grade 2/3); SDG indicator 4.1.1

⁴ FFLS indicator LN.11a - Parity indices - reading, age 7-14 (gender); SDG indicator 4.5.1

⁵ FFLS indicator LN.11a - Parity indices - reading, age for grade 2/3 (gender); SDG indicator 4.5.1

⁶ FFLS indicator LN.11a - Parity indices - reading, attending grade 2/3 (gender); SDG indicator 4.5.1

⁷ FFLS indicator LN.11b - Parity indices - reading, age 7-14 (wealth); SDG indicator 4.5.1

⁸ FFLS indicator LN.11c - Parity indices - reading, age 7-14 (area); SDG indicator 4.5.1

⁹ FFLS indicator LN.11d - Parity indices - reading, age 7-14 (functioning); SDG indicator 4.5.1

[^] The reading tasks were available in Georgian, Armenian and Azerbaijani. Children were assessed in the language (mainly) spoken by teachers or alternatively in the language (mainly) spoken at home. Children for whom both indicated languages were not available for assessment are recorded here, though children may subsequently have elected to attempt the assessment in one of available languages.

Table LN.4.1: Foundational reading skills

Percentage of children aged 7-14 years who demonstrate foundational reading skills by successfully completing three foundational reading tasks in Georgian, Armenian or Azerbaijani, by sex Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Male		Female		Total	
Percentage who correctly read 90% of words in a story	Three literal	Two inferential	Three literal	Two inferential	Three literal	Two inferential
Percentage who demonstrate foundational reading skills	Number of children age 7-14 years	Number of children age 7-14 years	Percentage who correctly read 90% of words in a story	Percentage who correctly answered comprehension questions	Percentage who correctly read 90% of words in a story	Percentage who correctly answered comprehension questions
Number of children age 7-14 years	Percentage who demonstrate foundational reading skills	Number of children age 7-14 years	Percentage who correctly read 90% of words in a story	Percentage who correctly answered comprehension questions	Percentage who correctly read 90% of words in a story	Percentage who correctly answered comprehension questions
Percentage who demonstrate foundational reading skills	Number of children age 7-14 years	Number of children age 7-14 years	Percentage who correctly read 90% of words in a story	Percentage who correctly answered comprehension questions	Percentage who correctly read 90% of words in a story	Percentage who correctly answered comprehension questions
Gender Parity Index for foundational reading skills ^{4,5,6}	Percentage of children who demonstrate foundational reading skills ^{1,2,3,7,8,9}	Percentage of children who demonstrate foundational reading skills ^{1,2,3,7,8,9}	Percentage of children who demonstrate foundational reading skills ^{1,2,3,7,8,9}	Percentage of children who demonstrate foundational reading skills ^{1,2,3,7,8,9}	Percentage of children who demonstrate foundational reading skills ^{1,2,3,7,8,9}	Percentage of children who demonstrate foundational reading skills ^{1,2,3,7,8,9}
Number of children age 7-14 years ⁵						

⁵ Characteristics of "orphanhood" and "percentage of children for whom the reading tasks were not available in appropriate language" are not included in the table due to the small number of unweighted cases in each category.

⁶ As eligibility for survey was determined based on age at time of interview (age 7-14 years), the disaggregate of Age at beginning of school year inevitably presents children who were age 6 years at the beginning of the school year.

⁷ Don't know has been suppressed from the table due to a small number of unweighted cases

⁸ 3 children aged 7-14 are not included in the table due to their refusal to be surveyed in the foundational learning skills module.

na: not applicable

() Figures that are based on 25-49 unweighted cases

(*) Figures that are based on fewer than 25 unweighted cases

"-" Denotes 0 unweighted cases in the denominator

Table LN.4.2: Foundational numeracy skills

Percentage of children aged 7-14 years who demonstrate foundational numeracy skills by successfully completing four foundational numeracy tasks, by sex, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Male				Female				Total										
	Percentage of children who successfully completed tasks of:				Percentage of children who successfully completed tasks of:				Percentage of children who successfully completed tasks of:										
	Number reading	Number discrimination	Addition	Pattern recognition and completion	Percentage of children who demonstrate foundational numeracy skills	Number of children age 7-14 years	Number reading	Number discrimination	Addition	Pattern recognition and completion	Percentage of children who demonstrate foundational numeracy skills	Number of children age 7-14 years	Number reading	Number discrimination	Addition	Pattern recognition and completion	Percentage of children who demonstrate foundational numeracy skills ^{1,2,3,7,8,9}	Gender Parity Index for foundational numeracy skills ^{4,5,6}	Number of children age 7-14 years ⁰
Total ^{1,4,4}	83.7	83.6	76.3	74.3	61.7	943	82.0	79.3	75.4	71.2	57.5	835	82.9	81.6	75.9	72.8	59.8	0.93	1,778
Area																			
Urban	85.9	84.1	79.2	76.6	64.1	607	83.6	79.7	76.7	71.7	58.5	548	84.8	82.0	78.0	74.3	61.4	0.91	1,155
Rural	79.6	82.6	71.2	70.2	57.5	336	79.0	78.7	73.0	70.2	55.7	287	79.3	80.8	72.0	70.2	56.7	0.97	623
Region																			
Tbilisi	87.9	87.2	79.3	78.4	64.7	357	82.9	79.3	78.8	67.9	55.2	302	85.6	83.6	79.1	73.6	60.3	0.85	660
Adjara A.R	83.5	78.8	82.3	84.2	72.4	94	84.4	78.5	78.3	85.8	71.4	73	83.9	78.7	80.5	84.9	71.9	0.99	168
Guria	87.0	91.6	67.9	71.6	51.4	23	75.2	77.0	60.8	70.3	52.2	22	81.2	84.3	64.4	70.9	51.8	1.02	45
Imereti	80.0	82.3	70.4	66.4	57.1	90	83.9	82.8	73.4	68.0	54.9	92	81.9	82.6	71.9	67.2	56.0	0.96	182
Racha-																			
Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti	(75.4)	(83.0)	(55.3)	(72.0)	(33.9)	3	(66.6)	(75.4)	(48.2)	(56.8)	(33.2)	4	70.7	78.9	51.5	63.8	33.5	(0.98)	7
Kakheti	75.7	86.0	74.3	70.2	53.8	59	81.2	87.8	78.6	71.9	57.3	63	78.5	86.9	76.5	71.1	55.6	1.06	122
Mtskheta-Mtianeti	(86.1)	(91.3)	(77.9)	(79.2)	(73.2)	24	(92.8)	(98.3)	(93.0)	(93.0)	(89.7)	21	89.2	94.6	85.0	85.7	81.0	(1.22)	45
Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti	81.1	90.5	84.4	83.3	71.2	70	71.4	72.7	78.8	70.7	63.1	65	76.4	81.9	81.7	77.3	67.3	0.88	135
Samtskhe-Javakheti	81.0	82.3	66.2	54.3	50.4	35	73.8	76.5	64.5	50.4	45.0	23	78.2	80.0	65.5	52.8	48.3	0.89	59
Kvemo Kartli	81.3	78.5	73.2	69.4	60.0	136	87.2	80.1	72.3	73.9	58.2	110	83.9	79.2	72.8	71.4	59.2	0.97	246
Shida Kartli	79.7	64.4	66.3	60.3	39.7	52	77.6	67.3	61.6	70.7	45.8	58	78.6	66.0	63.9	65.7	42.9	1.15	110

Table LN.4.2: Foundational numeracy skills

Percentage of children aged 7-14 years who demonstrate foundational numeracy skills by successfully completing four foundational numeracy tasks, by sex, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

Age at beginning of school year	Male					Female					Total							
	Percentage of children who successfully completed tasks of:					Percentage of children who successfully completed tasks of:					Percentage of children who successfully completed tasks of:							
	Number reading	Number discrimination	Addition	Pattern recognition and completion	Percentage of children who demonstrate foundational numeracy skills	Number of children age 7-14 years	Number reading	Number discrimination	Addition	Pattern recognition and completion	Percentage of children who demonstrate foundational numeracy skills	Number of children age 7-14 years	Number reading	Number discrimination	Addition	Pattern recognition and completion	Percentage of children who demonstrate foundational numeracy skills	Number of children age 7-14 years
^{6B}	(28.1)	(39.3)	(42.0)	(47.9)	(27.1)	45	(12.8)	(13.6)	(25.3)	(12.7)	(4.7)	38	21.1	27.6	34.4	31.8	16.8	82
7-8 ^{2,5}	63.2	67.6	63.3	59.3	37.1	234	63.7	62.1	61.1	53.4	34.1	222	63.5	64.9	62.2	56.5	35.6	456
7	54.5	55.9	54.9	46.6	26.7	111	42.6	42.8	45.7	41.5	17.8	108	48.6	49.5	50.4	44.1	22.3	219
8	71.1	78.1	70.8	70.9	46.5	123	83.5	80.2	75.5	64.7	49.5	115	77.1	79.1	73.1	67.9	47.9	238
9	87.9	88.9	79.4	74.8	63.2	146	88.7	83.6	85.3	73.7	61.4	116	88.3	86.5	82.0	74.3	62.4	263
10-14	96.5	93.1	84.4	83.2	75.4	518	94.9	92.0	84.0	83.9	72.2	459	95.7	92.6	84.2	83.6	73.9	977
10	94.7	90.9	82.2	81.8	70.4	138	90.7	87.5	76.0	80.8	61.3	111	92.9	89.4	79.5	81.4	66.4	249
11	95.8	91.3	82.5	74.1	66.6	90	91.5	88.9	84.1	81.7	72.1	98	93.5	90.0	83.3	78.0	69.5	188
12	98.3	94.5	85.1	83.3	77.4	105	95.4	90.1	83.7	86.8	72.9	102	96.9	92.3	84.4	85.0	75.2	207
13	97.1	94.6	85.4	89.0	81.6	130	100.0	99.1	88.8	84.6	79.3	100	98.4	96.5	86.9	87.1	80.6	229
14	97.1	95.5	89.1	88.3	84.1	55	100.0	98.1	92.8	88.0	81.2	48	98.5	96.7	90.8	88.1	82.7	104

Table LN.4.2: Foundational numeracy skills

Percentage of children aged 7-14 years who demonstrate foundational numeracy skills by successfully completing four foundational numeracy tasks, by sex, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Male				Female				Total										
	Percentage of children who successfully completed tasks of:				Percentage of children who successfully completed tasks of:				Percentage of children who successfully completed tasks of:										
	Number reading	Number discrimination	Addition	Pattern recognition and completion	Percentage of children who demonstrate foundational numeracy skills	Number of children age 7-14 years	Number reading	Number discrimination	Addition	Pattern recognition and completion	Percentage of children who demonstrate foundational numeracy skills	Number of children age 7-14 years	Number reading	Number discrimination	Addition	Pattern recognition and completion	Percentage of children who demonstrate foundational numeracy skills ^{1,2,3,7,8,9}	Gender Parity Index for foundational numeracy skills ^{4,5,6}	Number of children age 7-14 years ⁰
School attendance																			
Primary	77.9	78.9	72.5	69.4	54.2	663	75.4	73.0	70.6	65.5	50.0	595	76.7	76.1	71.6	67.5	52.2		1,259
Grade 1	(24.3)	(29.4)	(37.6)	(36.8)	(22.8)	42	(7.7)	(8.5)	(21.6)	(7.6)	(4.4)	39	16.2	19.2	29.9	22.6	13.9	(0.19)	81
Grade 2-3 ^{3,6}	62.9	69.3	65.2	63.1	38.8	262	65.5	64.3	63.2	54.0	34.9	230	64.1	66.9	64.2	58.8	37.0	0.90	492
Grade 2	55.0	57.8	56.8	56.4	29.7	126	49.2	47.0	48.7	46.8	21.2	109	52.3	52.8	53.0	52.0	25.7	0.71	235
Grade 3	70.2	79.9	72.9	69.2	47.2	137	80.1	79.8	76.2	60.5	47.2	121	74.8	79.8	74.4	65.1	47.2	1.00	257
Grade 4	92.9	89.7	76.8	71.8	62.2	143	88.9	82.0	82.2	75.1	60.0	118	91.1	86.2	79.3	73.3	61.2	0.96	261
Grade 5	96.2	92.5	84.9	83.9	74.5	119	92.6	90.2	80.2	85.0	68.0	116	94.5	91.4	82.6	84.5	71.3	0.91	235
Grade 6	96.8	94.0	85.9	79.2	72.7	97	90.4	89.3	82.9	81.7	71.4	92	93.7	91.7	84.4	80.4	72.0	0.98	189
Lower secondary	97.7	94.5	85.7	86.3	79.8	279	98.4	95.1	87.6	85.4	76.3	240	98.1	94.8	86.6	85.9	78.2	0.96	519
Grade 7	98.3	93.5	82.7	82.3	74.4	107	96.5	91.9	83.0	84.2	72.0	107	97.4	92.7	82.8	83.2	73.2	0.97	214
Grade 8	97.0	96.0	86.9	89.2	83.2	125	100.0	97.5	89.3	86.3	78.7	90	98.3	96.6	87.9	88.0	81.3	0.95	215
Grade 9	(98.3)	(92.9)	(89.5)	(87.5)	(83.2)	47	100.0	97.8	95.4	86.4	82.3	43	99.1	95.2	92.3	87.0	82.8	(0.99)	89
Out-of-school	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	1	-	-	-	-	-	0	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	1

Table LN.4.2: Foundational numeracy skills

Percentage of children aged 7-14 years who demonstrate foundational numeracy skills by successfully completing four foundational numeracy tasks, by sex, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Male				Female				Total											
	Percentage of children who successfully completed tasks of:				Percentage of children who successfully completed tasks of:				Percentage of children who successfully completed tasks of:											
	Number reading	Number discrimination	Addition	Pattern recognition and completion	Percentage of children who demonstrate foundational numeracy skills	Number of children age 7-14 years	Number reading	Number discrimination	Addition	Pattern recognition and completion	Percentage of children who demonstrate foundational numeracy skills	Number of children age 7-14 years	Number reading	Number discrimination	Addition	Pattern recognition and completion	Percentage of children who demonstrate foundational numeracy skills ^{1,2,3,7,8,9}	Gender Parity Index for foundational numeracy skills ^{4,5,6}	Number of children age 7-14 years ⁰	
Mother's education^c																				
Kindergarten or none	-	-	-	-	-	0	-	-	-	-	-	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
Primary or Lower Secondary	68.0	78.9	60.9	62.9	52.8	53	91.8	90.0	75.1	72.3	57.8	53	79.9	84.5	68.0	67.6	55.3	1.09	107	
Upper Secondary	80.7	78.1	67.9	66.6	52.7	285	77.4	74.2	73.8	73.6	56.6	237	79.2	76.3	70.6	69.8	54.5	1.07	522	
Vocational Education	83.6	78.4	71.5	74.8	56.4	129	80.4	79.9	71.4	73.0	57.8	116	82.1	79.1	71.5	73.9	57.0	1.03	245	
Higher Education	86.8	88.3	84.9	80.7	69.1	399	83.1	79.8	76.4	68.0	55.6	378	85.0	84.2	80.8	74.5	62.5	0.80	776	
Child's functional difficulties																				
Has functional difficulty	(73.4)	(84.8)	(56.9)	(47.9)	(40.1)	50	75.4	77.6	67.7	71.0	53.6	51	74.4	81.1	62.4	59.7	47.0	(1.34)	101	
Has no functional difficulty	84.2	83.5	77.4	75.8	62.9	894	82.5	79.5	76.0	71.2	57.8	784	83.4	81.6	76.7	73.6	60.5	0.92	1,677	
Mother's functional difficulties																				
Has functional difficulty	(67.9)	(75.6)	(62.9)	(48.4)	(27.5)	37	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	32	(80.7)	(79.1)	(74.8)	(53.6)	(34.5)	(*)	69	
Has no functional difficulty	84.3	83.9	76.9	75.4	63.1	907	81.5	79.2	74.9	71.6	58.1	803	83.0	81.7	76.0	73.6	60.8	0.92	1,709	

Table LN.4.2: Foundational numeracy skills

Percentage of children aged 7-14 years who demonstrate foundational numeracy skills by successfully completing four foundational numeracy tasks, by sex, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Male				Female				Total										
	Percentage of children who successfully completed tasks of:				Percentage of children who successfully completed tasks of:				Percentage of children who successfully completed tasks of:										
	Number reading	Number discrimination	Addition	Pattern recognition and completion	Percentage of children who demonstrate foundational numeracy skills	Number of children age 7-14 years	Number reading	Number discrimination	Addition	Pattern recognition and completion	Percentage of children who demonstrate foundational numeracy skills	Number of children age 7-14 years	Number reading	Number discrimination	Addition	Pattern recognition and completion	Percentage of children who demonstrate foundational numeracy skills ^{4,5,6}	Gender Parity Index for	Number of children age 7-14 years ⁶
Ethnicity of household head																			
Georgian	83.4	83.6	77.0	75.2	61.5	841	81.6	78.7	76.0	71.3	57.4	745	82.6	81.3	76.6	73.4	59.6	0.93	1,586
Azerbaijani	87.7	85.3	69.4	72.4	67.6	74	90.9	92.7	74.4	81.6	67.3	59	89.1	88.6	71.6	76.5	67.5	1.00	133
Armenian	(78.4)	(78.4)	(71.4)	(48.1)	(48.1)	25	(77.2)	(66.3)	(61.7)	(49.8)	(49.8)	27	77.8	72.2	66.4	49.0	49.0	(1.04)	51
Other	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	4	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	5	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	9
Wealth index quintile																			
Poorest	71.7	74.8	63.7	63.6	50.1	215	72.5	73.3	68.6	57.8	40.9	170	72.0	74.1	65.8	61.0	46.0	0.82	386
Second	84.5	80.9	75.6	69.1	57.6	190	78.1	75.5	73.4	73.1	59.9	164	81.5	78.5	74.6	71.0	58.7	1.04	354
Middle	80.9	78.7	74.8	79.1	58.5	181	87.2	81.0	72.5	73.3	57.2	179	84.0	79.9	73.7	76.2	57.9	0.98	360
Fourth	90.7	93.1	83.6	78.1	68.3	162	84.7	81.0	82.3	79.1	64.8	175	87.6	86.8	82.9	78.6	66.5	0.95	337
Richest	93.0	92.5	86.5	83.8	76.2	194	88.1	86.6	81.0	72.5	65.9	147	90.9	89.9	84.2	78.9	71.7	0.87	341
Parity indices																			
Wealth																			
Poorest/Richest ⁷	0.77	0.81	0.74	0.76	0.66	na	0.82	0.85	0.85	0.80	0.62	na	0.79	0.82	0.78	0.77	0.64	na	na
Area																			
Rural/Urban ⁸	0.93	0.98	0.90	0.92	0.90	na	0.95	0.99	0.95	0.98	0.95	na	0.94	0.99	0.92	0.95	0.92	na	na
Functional difficulties																			
Difficulties/No difficulties ⁹	(0.87)	(1.02)	(0.73)	(0.63)	(0.64)	na	0.91	0.98	0.89	1.00	0.93	na	0.89	0.99	0.81	0.81	0.78	na	na

6. Protected from Violence and Exploitation

6.1 Child discipline

Teaching children self-control and acceptable behavior is an integral part of child rearing in all cultures. Positive parenting practices involve guiding conflicts and emotions in ways that encourage the child's judgment and sense of responsibility and preserve their self-esteem, physical and psychological integrity and dignity. However, very often, children are raised using punitive methods that rely on the use of physical force or verbal intimidation to obtain desired behaviors. Studies have found⁸, that children's experience of violent discipline has harmful consequences, from immediate impacts to long-term harm that follows children into adulthood. Violence hampers children's development, learning abilities and behavior at school. It inhibits positive relationships, causes low self-esteem, emotional distress and depression, and also leads to risk-taking and self-harm.

In the PR module included in the main questionnaire, parents or caretakers of children aged 7-14 were asked a series of questions about child-rearing methods that adults used during the past month, and were also asked whether the respondent believes that physical punishment is a necessary part of child-rearing. The results are presented in tables PR.2.1 and PR.2.2.

⁸ Straus, M. and M. Paschall. "Corporal Punishment by Mothers and Development of Children's Cognitive Ability: A Longitudinal Study of Two Nationally Representative Age Cohorts." *Journal of Aggression, Maltreatment & Trauma* 18, no. 5 (2009): 459-83. doi:10.1080/10926770903035168.; Erickson, M. and B. Egeland. "A Developmental View of the Psychological Consequences of Maltreatment." *School Psychology Review* 16, no. 2 (1987): 156-68. <http://psycnet.apa.org/record/1987-29817-001>.; Schneider, M. et al. "Do Allegations of Emotional Maltreatment Predict Developmental Outcomes beyond That of Other Forms of Maltreatment?" *Child Abuse & Neglect* 29, no. 5 (2005): 513-32. doi:10.1016/j.chiabu.2004.08.010.

Table PR.2.1: Child discipline

Percentage of children age 7-14 years by child disciplining methods experienced during the last one month, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Percentage of children age 7-14 years who experienced:					Number of children age 7-14 years
	Only non-violent discipline	Psychological aggression	Physical punishment		Any violent discipline method ¹	
			Any	Severe ^A		
Total^C	55.3	38.4	9.2	0.7	40.3	1,780
Sex						
Male	50.2	43.9	11.1	1.2	46.7	945
Female	61.0	32.2	7.0	0.3	33.1	835
Area						
Urban	54.2	39.4	10.1	0.8	41.6	1,155
Rural	57.3	36.6	7.4	0.7	37.8	625
Age						
7-9	56.5	36.5	10.0	0.7	38.9	691
10-14	54.5	39.6	8.6	0.7	41.2	1,089
Mother's education^D						
Kindergarten or none	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	1
Primary or Lower Secondary	52.3	47.2	3.4	0.0	47.2	119
Upper Secondary	50.6	42.5	10.7	0.7	44.8	586
Vocational Education	53.8	41.8	9.3	0.4	44.0	269
Higher	59.7	32.8	8.7	1.0	34.5	802
Child's functional difficulties (age 7-14 years)^B						
Has functional difficulty	59.7	34.2	7.9	1.3	37.2	102
Has no functional difficulty	55.0	38.6	9.2	0.7	40.5	1,678
Mother's functional difficulties						
Has functional difficulty	(53.2)	(45.4)	(9.9)	(0.0)	(45.9)	69
Has no functional difficulty	55.4	38.1	9.1	0.8	40.1	1,711
Ethnicity of household head						
Georgian	56.0	37.4	9.5	0.8	39.3	1,587
Azerbaijani	59.5	39.3	1.4	0.0	39.3	133
Armenian	23.7	66.0	19.0	0.0	73.7	51
Other	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	9
Wealth index quintile						
Poorest	50.6	45.3	9.3	0.7	46.9	387
Second	57.7	35.8	6.6	0.0	37.7	354
Middle	52.7	41.4	12.6	0.9	43.5	360
Fourth	53.8	38.1	9.4	0.9	39.7	337
Richest	62.2	30.4	7.7	1.1	32.8	341

¹ FFLS indicator PR.1 - Violent discipline; SDG 16.2.1^B
^A Severe physical punishment includes: 1) Hit or slapped on the face, head or ears or 2) Beat up, that is, hit over and over as hard as one could.

^B Indicator is calculated for children age 7-14

^C The characteristics of "Region" are not presented in the table, due to the small number of unweighted cases within each category.

^D Don't know has been suppressed from the table due to a small number of unweighted cases

() Figures that are based on 25-49 unweighted cases

(*) Figures that are based on fewer than 25 unweighted cases

Table PR.2.2: Attitudes toward physical punishment

Percentage of mothers/caretakers of children age 7-14 years who believe that physical punishment is needed to bring up, raise, or educate a child properly, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Percentage of mothers/caretakers who believe that a child needs to be physically punished	Number of mothers/caretakers responding to a child discipline module
Total^A	2.4	1,780
Sex		
Male	3.6	945
Female	1.1	835
Area		
Urban	2.7	1,155
Rural	2.0	625
Age		
<25	(*)	25
25-34	1.9	497
35-49	2.5	943
50+	3.2	316
Mother's education^B		
Kindergarten or none	(*)	1
Primary or Lower Secondary	1.0	119
Upper Secondary	3.5	586
Vocational Education	1.7	269
Higher	2.1	802
Child's functional difficulties (age 7-14 years)		
Has functional difficulty	0.2	102
Has no functional difficulty	2.6	1,678
Mother's functional difficulties		
Has functional difficulty	(4.7)	69
Has no functional difficulty	2.3	1,711
Ethnicity of household head		
Georgian	2.7	1,587
Azerbaijani	0.0	133
Armenian	0.0	51
Other	(*)	9
Wealth index quintile		
Poorest	1.7	387
Second	2.7	354
Middle	1.4	360
Fourth	5.6	337
Richest	1.1	341

^A The characteristics of "Region" are not presented in the table, due to the small number of unweighted cases within each category.

^B Don't know has been suppressed from the table due to a small number of unweighted cases

() Figures that are based on 25-49 unweighted cases

(*) Figures that are based on fewer than 25 unweighted cases

7. Equitable Chance in Life

7.1 Child functioning

The Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities⁹ outlines States Parties' obligations to ensure the full realization of rights for children with disabilities on an equal basis with other children. The presence of functional difficulties may place children at risk of experiencing limited participation in an unaccommodating environment and limit the realization of their rights.

The survey included a child functioning module to determine the number/proportion of children who have functional difficulties based on the responses of their mothers and primary caregivers.

Tables EQ.1.1 and EQ.1.2 present the percentage of children by functional difficulty domains and age groups.

⁹ "Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities." United Nations. Accessed August 31, 2018. <https://www.un.org/development/desa/disabilities/convention-on-the-rights-of-persons-with-disabilities/convention-onthe-rights-of-persons-with-disabilities-2.html>.

Table EQ.1.2: Child functioning (children age 7-14 years)

Percentage of children age 7-14 years who have functional difficulty, by domain, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Percentage of children aged 7-14 years with functional difficulty ^A in the domain of:											Number of children age 7-14 years			
	Seeing	Hearing	Walking	Self-care	Communication	Learning	Remembering	Concentrating	Accepting change	Controlling behavior	Making friends		Anxiety	Depression	Percentage of children age 7-14 years with functional difficulty in at least one domain
Total^B	0.5	0.0	0.1	0.3	0.4	1.4	0.5	0.2	0.3	0.5	0.6	3.2	1.5	5.7	1,780
Sex															
Male	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.3	1.6	0.4	0.1	0.4	0.5	0.4	2.8	1.6	5.3	945
Female	1.1	0.1	0.0	0.4	0.6	1.1	0.6	0.4	0.2	0.6	0.8	3.7	1.4	6.2	835
Area															
Urban	0.7	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.4	1.4	0.5	0.3	0.1	0.6	0.7	3.9	1.6	6.4	1,155
Rural	0.3	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.4	1.3	0.5	0.1	0.6	0.3	0.4	1.9	1.3	4.4	625
Region															
Tbilisi	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.4	0.4	1.5	0.4	0.4	0.0	0.7	0.8	3.5	1.6	5.9	660
Adjara A.R	0.5	0.0	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.4	2.8	7.4	168
Guria	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.6	1.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.6	45
Imereti	0.0	0.4	0.0	0.0	0.8	1.2	0.0	0.0	1.2	0.6	0.5	1.4	1.4	4.1	183
Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.7	0.0	0.0	1.6	0.0	1.3	1.7	0.0	6.3	7
Kakheti	0.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.7	2.0	0.2	0.0	1.3	1.3	0.7	0.5	0.8	3.5	123
Mtskheta-Mtianeti	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.2	1.2	45
Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti	0.8	0.0	0.0	0.7	0.7	3.4	0.7	0.0	0.0	0.7	0.7	0.4	0.0	4.6	135
Samtskhe-Javakheti	0.6	0.0	0.6	0.0	0.0	1.4	1.4	1.4	0.5	0.0	0.0	1.8	1.2	4.9	59
Kvemo Kartli	1.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3	1.1	1.0	0.3	0.3	0.4	1.0	2.9	2.2	6.6	246
Shida Kartli	0.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	9.8	0.9	10.4	110

Table EQ.1.2: Child functioning (children age 7-14 years)

Percentage of children age 7-14 years who have functional difficulty, by domain, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Percentage of children aged 7-14 years with functional difficulty ^A in the domain of:										Percentage of children age 7-14 years with functional difficulty in at least one domain	Number of children age 7-14 years				
	Seeing	Hearing	Walking	Self-care	Communication	Learning	Remembering	Concentrating	Accepting change	Controlling behavior			Making friends	Anxiety	Depression	
Age																
7-9	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.4	1.6	0.5	0.0	0.1	0.4	0.7	3.1	1.5	5.4	691	
10-14	0.8	0.0	0.1	0.3	0.4	1.2	0.5	0.4	0.4	0.6	0.5	3.2	1.5	5.9	1,089	
Mother's education^C																
Kindergarten or none	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	1	
Primary or Lower Secondary	1.2	0.0	0.3	0.0	1.5	4.2	1.5	0.7	2.4	0.5	1.9	3.0	1.8	9.1	119	
Upper Secondary	0.4	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.3	1.7	0.6	0.1	0.2	0.6	0.3	2.9	1.9	5.8	586	
Vocational Education	1.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.2	2.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.4	0.0	2.8	1.0	7.1	269	
Higher	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.3	0.2	0.5	0.7	3.6	1.3	4.7	802	
Mother's functional difficulties																
Has functional difficulty	(1.7)	(0.0)	(1.2)	(1.2)	(1.2)	(1.6)	(1.2)	(0.0)	(1.7)	(0.4)	(0.4)	(9.7)	(2.5)	(13.9)	69	
Has no functional difficulty	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.4	1.4	0.5	0.3	0.2	0.5	0.6	2.9	1.5	5.4	1,711	
Ethnicity of household head																
Georgian	0.6	0.0	0.1	0.3	0.4	1.4	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.6	0.6	3.4	1.6	5.9	1,587	
Azerbaijani	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.5	0.6	1.1	0.6	0.6	0.0	1.0	1.4	0.9	4.0	133	
Armenian	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.6	1.6	1.6	0.6	0.0	0.0	2.8	0.6	5.0	51	
Other	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	(*)	9	

Table EQ.1.2: Child functioning (children age 7-14 years)

Percentage of children age 7-14 years who have functional difficulty, by domain, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

Percentage of children aged 7-14 years with functional difficulty^A in the domain of:

Wealth index quintile	Percentage of children age 7-14 years with functional difficulty in at least one domain											Number of children age 7-14 years			
	Seeing	Hearing	Walking	Self-care	Communication	Learning	Remembering	Concentrating	Accepting change	Controlling behavior	Making friends		Anxiety	Depression	
Poorest	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.9	1.7	4.4	2.1	1.1	1.0	2.1	2.1	2.3	1.1	7.4	387
Second	0.9	0.0	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.0	0.3	0.3	0.0	2.5	1.1	4.6	354
Middle	0.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.6	3.6	2.2	5.1	360
Fourth	0.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.6	0.9	6.0	337
Richest	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.1	2.2	5.4	341

^A Functional difficulty for children age 7-14 years is defined as having responded "A lot of difficulty" or "Cannot at all" to questions within all listed domains, except the last domains of anxiety and depression, for which the response category "Daily" is considered a functional difficulty.

^B The characteristics of "School attendance" are not presented in the table, due to the small number of unweighted cases within each category.

^C Don't know has been suppressed from the table due to a small number of unweighted cases

() Figures that are based on 25-49 unweighted cases

(*) Figures that are based on fewer than 25 unweighted cases

Table EQ.1.3: Use of assistive devices (children age 7-14 years)

Percentage of children age 7-14 years who use assistive devices and have functional difficulty within domain of assistive devices, Statistical Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households, 2024

	Percentage of children age 7-14 years who:			Number of children age 7-14 years
	Wear glasses	Use hearing aid	Use equipment or receive assistance for walking	
Total^A	5.0	0.5	0.7	1,780
Sex				
Male	5.1	0.4	0.3	945
Female	5.0	0.6	1.2	835
Area				
Urban	6.6	0.6	1.0	1,155
Rural	2.1	0.3	0.2	625
Region				
Tbilisi	7.0	0.6	1.0	660
Adjara A.R	8.1	1.2	0.0	168
Guria	7.3	0.9	0.7	45
Imereti	4.6	0.8	1.0	183
Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti	8.3	0.0	0.0	7
Kakheti	2.4	0.3	0.0	123
Mtskheta-Mtianeti	0.7	0.0	0.0	45
Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti	1.9	0.0	0.0	135
Samtskhe-Javakheti	1.0	0.0	0.0	59
Kvemo Kartli	3.2	0.3	1.1	246
Shida Kartli	3.2	0.0	1.7	110
Age				
7-9	5.0	0.5	1.1	691
10-14	5.0	0.5	0.5	1,089
Mother's education^B				
Kindergarten or none	(*)	(*)	(*)	1
Primary or Lower Secondary	5.6	0.5	0.0	119
Upper Secondary	2.1	0.4	0.9	586
Vocational Education	5.7	1.3	0.5	269
Higher	6.9	0.3	0.8	802
Mother's functional difficulties				
Has functional difficulty	(3.9)	(2.5)	(6.8)	69
Has no functional difficulty	5.1	0.4	0.5	1,711
Ethnicity of household head				
Georgian	5.5	0.5	0.8	1,587
Azerbaijani	1.6	0.5	0.0	133
Armenian	0.0	0.0	0.0	51
Other	(*)	(*)	(*)	9
Wealth index quintile				
Poorest	4.5	1.1	0.2	387
Second	3.9	0.3	0.1	354
Middle	4.7	0.0	1.7	360
Fourth	8.0	0.0	0.0	337
Richest	4.3	1.0	1.8	341

^A The characteristics of "School attendance" are not presented in the table, due to the small number of unweighted cases within each category.^B Don't know has been suppressed from the table due to a small number of unweighted cases

() Figures that are based on 25-49 unweighted cases

(*) Figures that are based on fewer than 25 unweighted cases

Appendices

Appendix A - List of personnel involved in the survey

Project Key Personnel	
Marine Muchiashvili	Project Manager
Giorgi Mikeladze	Project Coordinator
Mariam Okruashvili	Key Personnel
Ana Varamashvili	Key Personnel
Nestan Pantsulaia	Key Personnel

LLC BCG Research (Company that won the public procurement tender)	Fieldwork
---	-----------

Appendix B - Questionnaires Used in the Survey

The information provided by you is confidential. It is only used for calculating the general statistical indexes. The survey is conducted within the framework of the Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation fundamental research state grants and covers the well-being, functioning and fundamental teaching skills of children living in Georgian households.

The research is financially supported by Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation project № FR-22-25281

Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households Demographic Questionnaire

Cluster number	Household	Interviewer's Name and Surname	Supervisor's Name and Surname	Supervisor's code	Date of the Interview

First complete HL2-HL4 vertically for all household members, starting with the head of the household. Once HL2-HL4 are complete for all members, make sure to probe for additional members: Those that are not currently at home, any infants or small children and any others who may not be family (such as servants, friends) but who usually live in the household. Then, ask questions HL5-HL21 for each member one at a time. If additional questionnaires are used, indicate by ticking this box: □

LINE	HL1. HL2. First, please tell me the name of each person who usually lives here, starting with the head of the household. Probe for additional household members.	HL3. What is the relationship of (name) to (name of the head of household)?	HL4. Is (name) male or female? 1 MALE 2 FEMALE	HL5. What is (name)'s date of birth? 98 DK MONTH YEAR 9998 DK MONTH YEAR	HL6. How old is (name)? Record in completed years.	HL7. Nationality/ethnicity	HL8. Marital status	HL11. Is the household member 7-14 years old? 1 YES 2 NO HL20
01		01	1 2		AGE			Y N 1 2
02			1 2					1 2
03			1 2					1 2
04			1 2					1 2
05			1 2					1 2
06			1 2					1 2
07			1 2					1 2
08			1 2					1 2

HL1. Line number	HL2. First, please tell me the name of each person who usually lives here, starting with the head of the household. Probe for additional household members.	HL3. What is the relationship of (name) to (name of the head of household)?	HL4. Is (name) male or female? 1 MALE 2 FEMALE	HL5. What is (name)'s date of birth? 98 DK 9998 DK	HL6. How old is (name)? Record in completed years.	HL7. Nationality/ethnicity	HL8. Marital status	HL11. Is the household member 7-14 years old? 1 YES 2 NO ↘ HL20
LINE	NAME	RELATION*	M/F	MONTH	YEAR	AGE		Y N
09			1 2					1 2
10			1 2					1 2
11			1 2					1 2
<p>* Codes for HL3: Relationship to head of household: 01 HEAD 02 SPOUSE / PARTNER 03 SON / DAUGHTER 04 SON-IN-LAW / DAUGHTER-IN-LAW 05 GRANDCHILD 06 PARENT 07 PARENT-IN-LAW 08 BROTHER / SISTER 09 BROTHER-IN-LAW / SISTER-IN-LAW 10 UNCLE/AUNT 11 NIECE / NEPHEW 12 OTHER RELATIVE 13 ADOPTED / FOSTER / STEPCHILD 14 SERVANT (LIVE-IN) 96 OTHER (NOT RELATED) 98 DK</p> <p>* Codes for HL7: Nationality/ethnicity 1. GEORGIAN 2. AZERI 3. ABKHAZIAN 4. GREEK 5. OSSETIAN</p> <p>* Codes for HL8: Marital status 1. MARRIED 2. NON-REGISTERED MARRIAGE 3. SINGLE 4. DIVORCED/SEPARATED 5. WIDOWED</p>								

HL1. Line num ber	HL2. Name <i>Transfer the names and ages of all household members from HL2 and HL6 to the rows below and to the next page of this module.</i>	HL12. Is (name)'s biological mother alive? 1 YES 2 NO ↘ HL16 8 DK ↘ HL16	HL13. Does (name)'s biological mother live in this household? 1 YES 2 NO ↘ HL15	HL14. Record mother's line number and go to HL16.	HL15. Where does (name)'s biological mother live?	HL16. Is (name)'s biological father alive? 1 YES 2 NO ↘ HL20 8 DK ↘ HL20	HL17. Does (name)'s biological father live in this househol d? 1 YES 2 NO ↘ HL19	HL18. Record the father's line number and go to HL20.	HL19. Where does (name)'s biological father live?	HL20. Indicate the line number from the first column „No one“, record „90“	HL21. Is the household member 7- 14 years old child?
LINE	NAME	Y N DK	Y N	MOTHER		Y N DK	Y N	FATHER		Spouse/ Partner MOTHER/ GUARDIAN FATHER/ GUARDIAN	Y N
01		1 2 8	1 2	— —	1 2 3 4 8	1 2 8	1 2	— —	1 2 3 4 8		1 2
02		1 2 8	1 2	— —	1 2 3 4 8	1 2 8	1 2	— —	1 2 3 4 8		1 2
03		1 2 8	1 2	— —	1 2 3 4 8	1 2 8	1 2	— —	1 2 3 4 8		1 2
04		1 2 8	1 2	— —	1 2 3 4 8	1 2 8	1 2	— —	1 2 3 4 8		1 2
05		1 2 8	1 2	— —	1 2 3 4 8	1 2 8	1 2	— —	1 2 3 4 8		1 2
06		1 2 8	1 2	— —	1 2 3 4 8	1 2 8	1 2	— —	1 2 3 4 8		1 2
07		1 2 8	1 2	— —	1 2 3 4 8	1 2 8	1 2	— —	1 2 3 4 8		1 2
08		1 2 8	1 2	— —	1 2 3 4 8	1 2 8	1 2	— —	1 2 3 4 8		1 2
09		1 2 8	1 2	— —	1 2 3 4 8	1 2 8	1 2	— —	1 2 3 4 8		1 2
10		1 2 8	1 2	— —	1 2 3 4 8	1 2 8	1 2	— —	1 2 3 4 8		1 2
11		1 2 8	1 2	— —	1 2 3 4 8	1 2 8	1 2	— —	1 2 3 4 8		1 2
* Codes for HL15 and HL19: 1 Abroad 2 In another household in the same region 3 In another region and another household 4 In Georgia, in an institutional establishment 8 Don't know											

EDUCATION 1		ED																						
ED1. Line number	ED2. Name and age Copy names and ages of all members of the household from HL2 and HL6 to below and to next page of the module	ED3. Age 3 or above? 1 YES 2 NO Next line	ED4. Has (name) ever attended school or kindergarten? 1 YES 2 NO Next line	ED5. What is the highest level and grade or year of school (name) has ever attended? LEVEL: 0 KINDERGARTEN 1 PRIMARY 2 LOWER SECONDARY 3 UPPER SECONDARY 4 VOCATIONAL EDUCATION ON THE BASE OF LOWER SECONDARY EDUCATION 5 VOCATIONAL EDUCATION ON THE BASE OF UPPER SECONDARY EDUCATION 6 HIGHER 8 DK	ED6. Did (name) ever complete that (grade/year)? 1 YES 2 NO 8 DK	ED7. Age 3-24? 1 YES 2 NO Next line	ED8. Check ED4: Ever attended school or kindergarten? 1 YES 2 NO Next line																	
LINE	NAME	AGE	YES	NO	YES	NO	YES	NO	DK	YES	NO	YES	NO	YES	NO									
01		---	1	2	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	8	---	1	2	8	1	2	1	2				
02		---	1	2	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	8	---	1	2	8	1	2	1	2	1	2		
03		---	1	2	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	8	---	1	2	8	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2
04		---	1	2	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	8	---	1	2	8	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2
05		---	1	2	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	8	---	1	2	8	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2
06		---	1	2	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	8	---	1	2	8	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2
07		---	1	2	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	8	---	1	2	8	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2
08		---	1	2	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	8	---	1	2	8	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2
09		---	1	2	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	8	---	1	2	8	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2
10		---	1	2	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	8	---	1	2	8	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2
11		---	1	2	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	8	---	1	2	8	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2

EDUCATION 2

ED

ED1 Line number	ED2 Name and age	ED9 At any time during the current 2023-2024 school year did (name) attend school or kindergarten?	ED10 During the current 2023-2024 school year, which level and grade or year is (name) attending?	ED11 Is (he/she) attending a public school? If "Yes", record '1'. If "No", probe to code who controls and manages the school.	ED12 In the current 2023-2024 school year, has (name) received any financial support for school tuition? If "Yes", probe to ensure that support was not received from family, other relatives, friends or neighbours.	ED13 Who provided the tuition support? Record all mentioned.	ED14 For the current 2023-2024 school year, has (name) received any material support or cash to buy shoes, exercise books, notebooks, school uniforms or other school supplies? If "Yes", probe to ensure that support was not received from family, other relatives, friends or neighbours.	ED15 At any time during the previous 2022-2023 school year did (name) attend school or kindergarten?	ED16 During the previous 2022-2023 school year, which level and grade or year did (name) attend?				
LINE	NAME	AGE	LEVEL	AUTHORITY	Y	N	DK	TUITION	Y	N	DK	LEVEL	GRADE/ YEAR
01			0 KINDERGARTEN ∇ ED15	1 GOVT./ PUBLIC 2 RELIGIOUS/ FAITH ORG. 3 PRIVATE 6 OTHER 8 DK	1 YES 2 NO ∇ 8 DK ∇	A GOVT./ PUBLIC B RELIGIOUS/ FAITH ORG. C PRIVATE X OTHER Z DK	1 YES 2 NO 8 DK	1 YES 2 NO ∇ 8 DK ∇ Next line	0 KINDERGARTEN ∇ Next line 1 PRIMARY 2 LOWER SECONDARY 3 UPPER SECONDARY 4 VOCATIONAL EDUCATION ON THE BASE OF LOWER SECONDARY EDUCATION ∇ Next line 5 VOCATIONAL EDUCATION ON THE BASE OF UPPER SECONDARY EDUCATION ∇ Next line 6 HIGHER 8 DK				
02			1 PRIMARY 2 LOWER SECONDARY 3 UPPER SECONDARY 4 VOCATIONAL EDUCATION ON THE BASE OF LOWER SECONDARY EDUCATION ∇ ED11	1 2 3 6 8 1 2 3 6 8	1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8	A B C X Z A B C X Z	1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8	1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 8 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 8				
03			5 VOCATIONAL EDUCATION ON THE BASE OF UPPER SECONDARY EDUCATION ∇ ED11	1 2 3 6 8 1 2 3 6 8	1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8	A B C X Z A B C X Z	1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8	1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 8 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 8				
04			6 HIGHER 8 DK	1 2 3 6 8 1 2 3 6 8	1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8	A B C X Z A B C X Z	1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8	1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 8 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 8				
05				1 2 3 6 8 1 2 3 6 8	1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8	A B C X Z A B C X Z	1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8	1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 8 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 8				
06				1 2 3 6 8 1 2 3 6 8	1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8	A B C X Z A B C X Z	1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8	1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 8 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 8				
07				1 2 3 6 8 1 2 3 6 8	1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8	A B C X Z A B C X Z	1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8	1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 8 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 8				
08				1 2 3 6 8 1 2 3 6 8	1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8	A B C X Z A B C X Z	1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8	1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 8 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 8				
09				1 2 3 6 8 1 2 3 6 8	1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8	A B C X Z A B C X Z	1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8	1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 8 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 8				
10				1 2 3 6 8 1 2 3 6 8	1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8	A B C X Z A B C X Z	1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8	1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 8 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 8				
11				1 2 3 6 8 1 2 3 6 8	1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8	A B C X Z A B C X Z	1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8	1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8 1 2 8	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 8 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 8				

Household Questionnaire

Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of
Children Living in Georgian Households

2024

HOUSEHOLD INFORMATION PANEL		
A1. Cluster number: _____	A2. Household number: _____	
A3. Interviewer's name and number: NAME _____	A4. Supervisor's name and number: NAME _____	
A5. Day / Month / Year of interview: _____ / _____ / <u>20</u> _____	A6. Record the time:	HOURS : MINUTES _____ : _____

A7. Hello! My name is (*name and surname*). Our research is being conducted by Ivane Javakhishvili Tbilisi State University and "BCG Research", which covers the survey of well-being, functioning and foundational learning skills of children living in Georgian households. In this regard, we would like to ask you and your household members several questions. Your household was selected by random selection principle. For high reliability of the research results, your consent to participate in the research is very important. Participation in the research is voluntary and the data you provide is strictly confidential and anonymous. It will be used only to calculate aggregate statistical indicators. Researchers will not have the ability to link your address and other personal data with the information you provide. The interview will last approximately 15 minutes. Can we begin?

YES	1	1 ⇒ CHILDCARE
NO / NOT ASKED	2	2 ⇒ A11

A11. Result of Household Questionnaire interview: Discuss any result not completed with Supervisor.	COMPLETED 01 NO HOUSEHOLD MEMBER AT HOME OR NO COMPETENT RESPONDENT AT HOME AT TIME OF VISIT 02 ENTIRE HOUSEHOLD ABSENT FOR EXTENDED PERIOD OF TIME 03 REFUSED 04 DWELLING VACANT OR ADDRESS NOT A DWELLING 05 DWELLING DESTROYED 06 DWELLING NOT FOUND 07 OTHER (specify)..... 96
---	---

CHILDCARE

HCH

HCH1. Do any of your children aged 7-14 years old attend a kindergarten or a creche, or are they being looked after on a long-term basis by other persons (not belonging to your household) or by other institutions?

YES 1
 NO 2

1 ⇨ HCH2
 2 ⇨ HI1

***Interviewer:** Do not take into account any short-term or irregular arrangements which help you out for a few days (e.g., parents, neighbours, other childcare from time to time, but only irregularly or in emergencies). Compulsory school attendance is not regarded as childcare.*

HCH2. How is the day care of the children aged 7-14 years old in this household organised?

***Interviewer:** Please report for each child separately.*

HHM NO. (From D1)	Name of child	Caring for a child		
		Private institution	Private institution	Private institution
		<input type="checkbox"/> (1)	<input type="checkbox"/> (2)	<input type="checkbox"/> (3)
		<input type="checkbox"/> (1)	<input type="checkbox"/> (2)	<input type="checkbox"/> (3)
		<input type="checkbox"/> (1)	<input type="checkbox"/> (2)	<input type="checkbox"/> (3)
		<input type="checkbox"/> (1)	<input type="checkbox"/> (2)	<input type="checkbox"/> (3)
		<input type="checkbox"/> (1)	<input type="checkbox"/> (2)	<input type="checkbox"/> (3)

HOUSEHOLD INCOME

HI

The following questions concern the income of all household members and any other income received by the household as a whole.

<p>HI1. Which of the following sources of income did your household have during the last 12 month?</p> <p><i>Interviewer: Read the income categories aloud to the respondent and tick "Yes" or "No" for each of them.</i></p> <p>Does your household receive ...?</p> <p>[A] Wages or salaries (in cash or in kind)?</p> <p>[B] Income from self-employment (in cash or in kind)?</p> <p>[C] Income from farming/fishing/forestry (in cash or in kind)?</p> <p>[D] Pensions?</p> <p>[E] Social assistance?</p> <p>[F] Scholarships?</p> <p>[G] Remittances?</p> <p>[H] Income from investment, savings or property?</p> <p>[I] Income from other sources (e.g., private transfers)?</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">YES NO</p> <p>WAGES OR SALARIES 1 2</p> <p>INCOME FROM SELF-EMPLOYMENT.... 1 2</p> <p>INCOME FROM FARMING/ FISHING/ FORESTRY 1 2</p> <p>PENSIONS..... 1 2</p> <p>SOCIAL ASSISTANCE 1 2</p> <p>SCHOLARSHIPS 1 2</p> <p>REMITTANCES..... 1 2</p> <p>INCOME FROM INVESTMENT, SAVINGS OR PROPERTY 1 2</p> <p>INCOME FROM OTHER SOURCES (E.G., PRIVATE TRANSFERS) 1 2</p>	
<p>HI2. Adding up all forms of income you receive as mentioned earlier, what was the average net monthly income of your household during the last 12 month? (that is, the income after tax and Pension Fund contributions)</p> <p><i>Interviewer: Please remind the respondent of the different sources of income: wages, salaries, income from self-employment, income from farming/fishing/forestry, pensions, remittances, social assistance, income from investments, savings or property, etc.</i></p>	<p>INCOME PER MONTH... _____ (GEL)</p> <p>DOES NOT KNOW 99998</p> <p>DECLINES TO ANSWER 99999</p>	
<p>HI3. Could you please give the approximate range of your household's average net monthly income during the last 12 months? (That is, income after tax and Pension Fund contributions)</p>	<p>LESS THAN 400 1</p> <p>FROM 400 TO 670 2</p> <p>FROM 670 TO 1000 3</p> <p>FROM 1000 TO 1550 4</p> <p>1550 OR MORE..... 5</p> <p>DOES NOT KNOW 8</p> <p>DECLINES TO ANSWER 9</p>	

RECEIVING HELP

RC

The following questions concern help and services that you or any of your household members received **from a private person outside your household**. You might have paid something for this help or these services, but it should not have been provided by a private or a public institution.

<p>RC1. Did you or any other member of your household receive help or services on child-care from a private person who is not a member of your household at any time during the last 4 weeks?</p>	<p>YES..... 1 NO..... 2</p>	<p>1 ⇒ RC2 2 ⇒ HC1</p>
<p>RC2. How many times did you receive child-care help or services during the last four weeks?</p>	<p>RECIEVED..... __ __ TIMES</p>	
<p>RC3. Last time you received this help, did you pay for it?</p>	<p>YES..... 1 NO..... 2</p>	

HOUSEHOLD CHARACTERISTICS		HC
<p>HC1. How many rooms does your household use for private purposes (not counting bathrooms, toilets, kitchens, hallways, etc.)?</p>	<p>TOTAL NUMBER OF ROOMS WHICH ARE USED__ __ ROOMS</p> <p>TOTAL NUMBER OF BEDROOMS WHICH ARE USED__ __ BEDROOMS</p>	
<p>HC2. Does your household use the following items? Please include all items irrespective of whether the item is owned, rented or otherwise provided for your use.</p> <p><i>Interviewer: Read the items aloud to the respondent, and tick "Yes" or "No" for each of them.</i></p> <p>Does your household use ... ?</p> <p>[A] Washing machine</p> <p>[B] TV set</p> <p>[C] Vacuum cleaner</p> <p>[D] Sewing machine</p> <p>[E] Personal computer/laptop/tablet</p> <p>[F] Car/minibus/truck</p> <p>[G] Gas stove/electric stove</p> <p>[H] Mobile phone</p> <p>[I] Landline phone</p> <p>[J] Heater (gas or electric)</p> <p>[K] Heater (wood oven)</p> <p>[L] Dishwasher</p> <p>[M] Microwave oven</p> <p>[N] Refrigerator</p> <p>[O] Water heater</p> <p>[P] Radio</p>	<p>YES NO</p> <p>WASHING MACHINE 1 2</p> <p>TV SET 1 2</p> <p>VACUUM CLEANER 1 2</p> <p>SEWING MACHINE 1 2</p> <p>PERSONAL COMPUTER/ LAPTOP/ TABLET 1 2</p> <p>CAR/MINIBUS/TRUCK..... 1 2</p> <p>GAS STOVE/ELECTRIC STOVE..... 1 2</p> <p>MOBILE PHONE 1 2</p> <p>LANDLINE PHONE 1 2</p> <p>HEATER (GAS OR ELECTRIC)..... 1 2</p> <p>HEATER (WOOD OVEN)..... 1 2</p> <p>DISHWASHER 1 2</p> <p>MICROWAVE OVEN 1 2</p> <p>REFRIGERATOR 1 2</p> <p>WATER HEATER..... 1 2</p> <p>RADIO..... 1 2</p>	
<p>HC3. Do you or anyone in your household have access to the Internet at home? (via any device: any type of computer, mobile/smart phone, etc.)</p>	<p>YES..... 1</p> <p>NO..... 2</p>	<p>1 ⇨ HC4</p> <p>2 ⇨ A7</p>

<p>HC4. How do your household members access the internet from home?</p> <p><i>Interviewer: Read each item aloud to the respondent, and tick "Yes" or "No" for each them.</i></p> <p>[A] PC or laptop computer</p> <p>[B] Tablet</p> <p>[C] Mobile phone or smartphone</p> <p>[D] Digital TV</p> <p>[X] Other, please specify:</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">YES NO</p> <p>PC OR LAPTOP COMPUTER 1 2</p> <p>TABLET 1 2</p> <p>MOBILE PHONE OR SMARTPHONE..... 1 2</p> <p>DIGITAL TV 1 2</p> <p>OTHER (<i>SPECIFY</i>) _____ 1 2</p>	
<p>HC5. Does any member of this household use the internet at home to order or buy goods or services?</p>	<p>YES..... 1</p> <p>NO.....2</p>	

HOUSEHOLD INFORMATION PANEL		
<p>A7. End Time of interview:</p>	<p>HOURS : MINUTES</p> <p>___ : ___</p>	<p>A8. Name and line number (HLI) of the respondent to HOUSEHOLD QUESTIONNAIRE interview:</p> <p>NAME _____</p>
<p>A9. Land line number:</p> <p>NUMBER _____</p>	<p>A10. Mobile number:</p> <p>NUMBER _____</p>	

Main Questionnaire

QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN AGE 7-14

Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of
Children Living in Georgian Households
2024

INFORMATION PANEL		FS
M1. Cluster number: _____	M2. Household number: _____	
M3. Child's name and line number: NAME _____	M4. Mother's / Caretaker's name and line number: NAME _____	
M5. Interviewer's name and number: NAME _____	M6. Supervisor's name and number: NAME _____	
M7. Day / Month / Year of interview: _____ / _____ / <u>2</u> <u>0</u> _____	M8. Record the time:	HOURS : MINUTES _____ : _____

M9. Hello, my name is (your name). We are from the research organization BCG. We are conducting a survey about the condition of children, families and households. I want to talk to you about (<i>child's name from M3</i>) health and well-being. The interview will take 15 minutes. The information we collect is strictly confidential and anonymous. If you do not want to answer my questions or wish to stop the interview, tell me immediately. Can we begin?		
YES..... 1	1 ⇨ M10	
NO / NOT ASKED..... 2	2 ⇨ M11	
M10. Check completed questionnaires in this household: Have you interviewed this respondent for another questionnaire for children age 7-14?	YES, INTERVIEWED ALREADY .1 NO, FIRST INTERVIEW2	1 ⇨ CB4 2 ⇨ MF1
M11. Result of interview for child age 5-17 years <i>Codes refer to the respondent.</i> DISCUSS ANY RESULT NOT COMPLETED WITH SUPERVISOR.	COMPLETED.....01 NOT AT HOME02 REFUSED03 PARTLY COMPLETED04 INCAPACITATED (<i>specify</i>) _____ 05 NO ADULT CONSENT FOR MOTHER/ CARETAKER AGE 15-1706 OTHER (<i>specify</i>).....96	

MOTHER'S FUNCTIONING		MF
MF1. Do you use glasses or contact lenses? <i>Include the use of glasses for reading.</i>	YES 1 NO 2	
MF2. Do you use a hearing aid?	YES 1 NO 2	
MF3. I will now ask you about difficulties you may have doing a number of different activities. For each activity there are four possible answers. You may say that you have 1) no difficulty, 2) some difficulty, 3) a lot of difficulty or 4) that you cannot do the activity at all. <i>Repeat the categories during the individual questions whenever the respondent does not use an answer category:</i> Remember, the four possible answers are: 1) no difficulty, 2) some difficulty, 3) a lot of difficulty, or 4) that you cannot do the activity at all.		
MF4. Check MF1: Respondent uses glasses or contact lenses?	YES, MF1=1..... 1 NO, MF1=2 2	1 ⇨MF5A 2 ⇨MF5B
MF5A. When using your glasses or contact lenses, do you have difficulty seeing? MF5B. Do you have difficulty seeing?	NO DIFFICULTY 1 SOME DIFFICULTY 2 A LOT OF DIFFICULTY 3 CANNOT SEE AT ALL 4	
MF6. Check MF2: Respondent uses a hearing aid?	YES, MF2=1..... 1 NO, MF2=2 2	1 ⇨MF7A 2 ⇨MF7B
MF7A. When using your hearing aid(s), do you have difficulty hearing? MF7B. Do you have difficulty hearing?	NO DIFFICULTY 1 SOME DIFFICULTY 2 A LOT OF DIFFICULTY 3 CANNOT HEAR AT ALL..... 4	
MF8. Do you have difficulty walking or climbing steps?	NO DIFFICULTY 1 SOME DIFFICULTY 2 A LOT OF DIFFICULTY 3 CANNOT WALK/ CLIMB STEPS AT ALL 4	
MF9. Do you have difficulty remembering or concentrating?	NO DIFFICULTY 1 SOME DIFFICULTY 2 A LOT OF DIFFICULTY 3 CANNOT REMEMBER/ CONCENTRATE AT ALL..... 4	
MF10. Do you have difficulty with self-care, such as washing all over or dressing?	NO DIFFICULTY 1 SOME DIFFICULTY 2 A LOT OF DIFFICULTY 3 CANNOT CARE FOR SELF AT ALL 4	
MF11. Using your usual language, do you have difficulty communicating, for example understanding or being understood?	NO DIFFICULTY 1 SOME DIFFICULTY 2 A LOT OF DIFFICULTY 3	

CHILD'S BACKGROUND		CB
CB4. Has (<i>name</i>) ever attended school or any early childhood education programme?	YES 1 NO 2	2 ⇒ FCD2
CB5. What is the highest level and grade or year of school (<i>name</i>) has ever attended?	KINDERGARTEN 000 PRIMARY 1 ___ LOWER SECONDARY 2 ___ UPPER SECONDARY 3 ___ VOCATIONAL EDUCATION ON THE BASE OF LOWER SECONDARY EDUCATION 4 ___ VOCATIONAL EDUCATION ON THE BASE OF UPPER SECONDARY EDUCATION 5 ___ HIGHER 6 ___	000 ⇒ CB7
CB6. Did (he/she) ever complete that (grade/year)?	YES 1 NO 2	
CB7. At any time during the current 2023-2024 school year did (<i>name</i>) attend school or any early childhood education programme?	YES 1 NO 2	2 ⇒ CB9
CB8. During current 2023-2024 school year, which level and grade or year is (<i>name</i>) <u>attending</u> ?	KINDERGARTEN 000 PRIMARY 1 ___ LOWER SECONDARY 2 ___ UPPER SECONDARY 3 ___ VOCATIONAL EDUCATION ON THE BASE OF LOWER SECONDARY EDUCATION 4 ___ VOCATIONAL EDUCATION ON THE BASE OF UPPER SECONDARY EDUCATION 5 ___ HIGHER 6 ___	
CB9. At any time during the previous 2022-2023 school year did (<i>name</i>) attend school or any early childhood education programme?	YES 1 NO 2	2 ⇒ FCD2
CB10. During previous 2022-2023 school year, which level and grade or year did (<i>name</i>) <u>attend</u> ?	KINDERGARTEN 000 PRIMARY 1 ___ LOWER SECONDARY 2 ___ UPPER SECONDARY 3 ___ VOCATIONAL EDUCATION ON THE BASE OF LOWER SECONDARY EDUCATION 4 ___ VOCATIONAL EDUCATION ON THE BASE OF UPPER SECONDARY EDUCATION 5 ___ HIGHER 6 ___	

CHILD DISCIPLINE

FCD

CHILD DISCIPLINE		FCD
<p>FCD2. Adults use certain ways to teach children the right behaviour or to address a behaviour problem. I will read various methods that are used. Please tell me if <u>you or any other adult in your household</u> has used this method with <u>(name) in the past 30 days.</u></p> <p>[A] Took away privileges, forbade something <u>(name)</u> liked or did not allow (him/her) to leave the house.</p> <p>[B] Explained why <u>(name)</u>'s behaviour was wrong.</p> <p>[C] Shook (him/her).</p> <p>[D] Shouted, yelled at or screamed at (him/her).</p> <p>[E] Gave (him/her) something else to do</p> <p>[F] Spanked, hit or slapped (him/her) on the bottom with bare hand.</p> <p>[G] Hit (him/her) on the bottom or elsewhere on the body with something like a belt, hairbrush, stick or other hard object.</p> <p>[H] Called (him/her) dumb, lazy or another name like that.</p> <p>[I] Hit or slapped (him/her) on the face, head or ears.</p> <p>[J] Hit or slapped (him/her) on the hand, arm, or leg.</p> <p>[K] Beat (him/her) up, that is hit him/her over and over as hard as one could.</p>	<p>YES NO</p> <p>TOOK AWAY PRIVILEGES 1 2</p> <p>EXPLAINED WRONG BEHAVIOR..... 1 2</p> <p>SHOOK HIM/HER 1 2</p> <p>SHOUTED, YELLED, SCREAMED 1 2</p> <p>GAVE SOMETHING ELSE TO DO..... 1 2</p> <p>SPANKED, HIT, SLAPPED ON BOTTOM WITH BARE HAND..... 1 2</p> <p>HIT WITH BELT, HAIRBRUSH, STICK OR OTHER HARD OBJECT 1 2</p> <p>CALLED DUMB, LAZY OR ANOTHER NAME 1 2</p> <p>HIT / SLAPPED ON THE FACE, HEAD OR EARS..... 1 2</p> <p>HIT / SLAPPED ON HAND, ARM OR LEG 1 2</p> <p>BEAT UP, HIT OVER AND OVER AS HARD AS ONE COULD 1 2</p>	
<p>FCD5. Do you believe that in order to bring up, raise, or educate a child properly, the child needs to be physically punished?</p>	<p>YES..... 1</p> <p>NO 2</p> <p>DK / NO OPINION 8</p>	

CHILD FUNCTIONING		FCF
<p>FCF1. I would like to ask you some questions about difficulties (<i>name</i>) may have.</p> <p>Does (<i>name</i>) wear glasses or contact lenses?</p>	<p>YES.....1</p> <p>NO.....2</p>	
<p>FCF2. Does (<i>name</i>) use a hearing aid?</p>	<p>YES.....1</p> <p>NO.....2</p>	
<p>FCF3. Does (<i>name</i>) use any equipment or receive assistance for walking?</p>	<p>YES.....1</p> <p>NO.....2</p>	
<p>FCF4. In the following questions, I will ask you to answer by selecting one of four possible answers. For each question, would you say that (<i>name</i>) has: 1) no difficulty, 2) some difficulty, 3) a lot of difficulty, or 4) that (he/she) cannot at all.</p> <p><i>Repeat the categories during the individual questions whenever the respondent does not use an answer category:</i></p> <p>Remember the four possible answers: Would you say that (<i>name</i>) has: 1) no difficulty, 2) some difficulty, 3) a lot of difficulty, or 4) that (he/she) cannot at all?</p>		
<p>FCF5. Check FCF1: Child wears glasses or contact lenses?</p>	<p>YES, FCF1=1.....1</p> <p>NO, FCF1=2.....2</p>	<p>1 ⇒FCF6A</p> <p>2 ⇒FCF6B</p>
<p>FCF6A. When wearing (his/her) glasses or contact lenses, does (<i>name</i>) have difficulty seeing?</p> <p>FCF6B. Does (<i>name</i>) have difficulty seeing?</p>	<p>NO DIFFICULTY.....1</p> <p>SOME DIFFICULTY.....2</p> <p>A LOT OF DIFFICULTY.....3</p> <p>CANNOT SEE AT ALL.....4</p>	
<p>FCF7. Check FCF2: Child uses a hearing aid?</p>	<p>YES, FCF2=1.....1</p> <p>NO, FCF2=2.....2</p>	<p>1 ⇒FCF8A</p> <p>2 ⇒FCF8B</p>
<p>FCF8A. When using (his/her) hearing aid(s), does (<i>name</i>) have difficulty hearing sounds like peoples' voices or music?</p> <p>FCF8B. Does (<i>name</i>) have difficulty hearing sounds like peoples' voices or music?</p>	<p>NO DIFFICULTY.....1</p> <p>SOME DIFFICULTY.....2</p> <p>A LOT OF DIFFICULTY.....3</p> <p>CANNOT HEAR AT ALL.....4</p>	

<p>FCF9. Check FCF3: Child uses equipment or receives assistance for walking?</p>	<p>YES, FCF3=11 NO, FCF3=22</p>	<p>2 ⇒FCF14</p>
<p>FCF10. Without (his/her) equipment or assistance, does (<i>name</i>) have difficulty walking 100 meters on level ground? <i>Probe:</i> That would be about the length of 1 football field. <i>Note that category 'No difficulty' is not available, as the child uses equipment or receives assistance for walking.</i></p>	<p>SOME DIFFICULTY2 A LOT OF DIFFICULTY3 CANNOT WALK 100 M AT ALL.....4</p>	<p>3 ⇒FCF12 4 ⇒FCF12</p>
<p>FCF11. Without (his/her) equipment or assistance, does (<i>name</i>) have difficulty walking 500 meters on level ground? <i>Probe:</i> That would be about the length of 5 football fields. <i>Note that category 'No difficulty' is not available, as the child uses equipment or receives assistance for walking.</i></p>	<p>SOME DIFFICULTY2 A LOT OF DIFFICULTY3 CANNOT WALK 500 M AT ALL.....4</p>	
<p>FCF12. With (his/her) equipment or assistance, does (<i>name</i>) have difficulty walking 100 meters on level ground? <i>Probe:</i> That would be about the length of 1 football field.</p>	<p>NO DIFFICULTY1 SOME DIFFICULTY2 A LOT OF DIFFICULTY3 CANNOT WALK 100 M AT ALL.....4</p>	<p>3 ⇒FCF16 4 ⇒FCF16</p>
<p>FCF13. With (his/her) equipment or assistance, does (<i>name</i>) have difficulty walking 500 meters on level ground? <i>Probe:</i> That would be about the length of 5 football fields.</p>	<p>NO DIFFICULTY1 SOME DIFFICULTY2 A LOT OF DIFFICULTY3 CANNOT WALK 500 M AT ALL.....4</p>	<p>1 ⇒FCF16 2 ⇒FCF16 3 ⇒FCF16 4 ⇒FCF16</p>
<p>FCF14. Compared with children of the same age, does (<i>name</i>) have difficulty walking 100 meters on level ground? <i>Probe:</i> That would be about the length of 1 football field.</p>	<p>NO DIFFICULTY1 SOME DIFFICULTY2 A LOT OF DIFFICULTY3 CANNOT WALK 100 M AT ALL.....4</p>	<p>3 ⇒FCF16 4 ⇒FCF16</p>
<p>FCF15. Compared with children of the same age, does (<i>name</i>) have difficulty walking 500 meters on level ground? <i>Probe:</i> That would be about the length of 5 football fields.</p>	<p>NO DIFFICULTY1 SOME DIFFICULTY2 A LOT OF DIFFICULTY3 CANNOT WALK 500 M AT ALL.....4</p>	
<p>FCF16. Does (<i>name</i>) have difficulty with self-care such as feeding or dressing (himself/herself)?</p>	<p>NO DIFFICULTY1 SOME DIFFICULTY2 A LOT OF DIFFICULTY3 CANNOT CARE FOR SELF AT ALL4</p>	

FCF17. When (<i>name</i>) speaks, does (he/she) have difficulty being understood by people inside of this household?	NO DIFFICULTY1 SOME DIFFICULTY2 A LOT OF DIFFICULTY3 CANNOT BE UNDERSTOOD AT ALL4	
FCF18. When (<i>name</i>) speaks, does (he/she) have difficulty being understood by people outside of this household?	NO DIFFICULTY1 SOME DIFFICULTY2 A LOT OF DIFFICULTY3 CANNOT BE UNDERSTOOD AT ALL4	
FCF19. Compared with children of the same age, does (<i>name</i>) have difficulty learning things?	NO DIFFICULTY1 SOME DIFFICULTY2 A LOT OF DIFFICULTY3 CANNOT LEARN THINGS AT ALL4	
FCF20. Compared with children of the same age, does (<i>name</i>) have difficulty remembering things?	NO DIFFICULTY1 SOME DIFFICULTY2 A LOT OF DIFFICULTY3 CANNOT REMEMBER THINGS AT ALL4	
FCF21. Does (<i>name</i>) have difficulty concentrating on an activity that (he/she) enjoys doing?	NO DIFFICULTY1 SOME DIFFICULTY2 A LOT OF DIFFICULTY3 CANNOT CONCENTRATE AT ALL4	
FCF22. Does (<i>name</i>) have difficulty accepting changes in (his/her) routine?	NO DIFFICULTY1 SOME DIFFICULTY2 A LOT OF DIFFICULTY3 CANNOT ACCEPT CHANGES AT ALL4	
FCF23. Compared with children of the same age, does (<i>name</i>) have difficulty controlling (his/her) behaviour?	NO DIFFICULTY1 SOME DIFFICULTY2 A LOT OF DIFFICULTY3 CANNOT CONTROL BEHAVIOUR AT ALL4	
FCF24. Does (<i>name</i>) have difficulty making friends?	NO DIFFICULTY1 SOME DIFFICULTY2 A LOT OF DIFFICULTY3 CANNOT MAKE FRIENDS AT ALL4	
FCF25. The next questions have different options for answers. I am going to read these to you after each question. I would like to know how often (<i>name</i>) seems very anxious, nervous or worried. Would you say: daily, weekly, monthly, a few times a year or never?	DAILY1 WEEKLY2 MONTHLY3 A FEW TIMES A YEAR4 NEVER5	
FCF26. I would also like to know how often (<i>name</i>) seems very sad or depressed. Would you say: daily, weekly, monthly, a few times a year or never?	DAILY1 WEEKLY2 MONTHLY3 A FEW TIMES A YEAR4 NEVER5	

PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT		PR												
<p>PR3. Excluding school text books and holy books, how many books do you have for <i>(name)</i> to read at home?</p>	NONE.....00 NUMBER OF BOOKS..... <u>0</u> ___ TEN OR MORE BOOKS.....10													
<p>PR4. Check CB7: In the current school year, did the child attend school or any early childhood education programme?</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>CHECK ED9 IN THE EDUCATION MODULE IN THE HOUSEHOLD QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILD IF CB7 WAS NOT ASKED.</i></p>	YES, CB7/ED9=1..... 1 NO, CB7/ED9=2 OR BLANK 2	2 ⇒ End												
<p>PR5. Does <i>(name)</i> ever have homework?</p>	YES 1 NO 2 DK 8	2 ⇒ PR7 8 ⇒ PR7												
<p>PR6. Does anyone help <i>(name)</i> with homework?</p>	YES 1 NO 2 DK 8													
<p>PR7. Does <i>(name)</i>'s school have a school governing body in which parents can participate (for example, economic council, disciplinary committee, etc.)?</p>	YES 1 NO 2 DK 8	2 ⇒ PR10 8 ⇒ PR10												
<p>PR8. In the last 12 months, have you or any other adult from your household attended a meeting called by this school governing body?</p>	YES 1 NO 2 DK 8	2 ⇒ PR10 8 ⇒ PR10												
<p>PR9. During any of these meetings, was any of the following discussed:</p> <p>[A] A plan for addressing key education issues faced by <i>(name)</i>'s school?</p> <p>[B] School budget or use of funds received by <i>(name)</i>'s school?</p>	<table style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="width: 80%;"></th> <th style="width: 10%; text-align: center;">YES</th> <th style="width: 10%; text-align: center;">NO</th> <th style="width: 10%; text-align: center;">DK</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>PLAN FOR ADDRESSING SCHOOL'S ISSUES</td> <td style="text-align: center;">1</td> <td style="text-align: center;">2</td> <td style="text-align: center;">8</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SCHOOL BUDGET</td> <td style="text-align: center;">1</td> <td style="text-align: center;">2</td> <td style="text-align: center;">8</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		YES	NO	DK	PLAN FOR ADDRESSING SCHOOL'S ISSUES	1	2	8	SCHOOL BUDGET	1	2	8	
	YES	NO	DK											
PLAN FOR ADDRESSING SCHOOL'S ISSUES	1	2	8											
SCHOOL BUDGET	1	2	8											
<p>PR10. In the last 12 months, have you or any other adult member of your household received <i>(name)</i>'s academic assessment, for example, a grade sheet or written evaluation?</p>	YES 1 NO 2 DK 8													

<p>PR11. In the last 12 months, have you or any adult from your household gone to (name)'s school for any of the following reasons?</p> <p>[A] A school celebration or a sport event?</p> <p>[B] To discuss (name)'s progress with (his/her) teachers?</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">YES NO DK</p> <p>CELEBRATION OR SPORT EVENT.....1 2 8</p> <p>TO DISCUSS PROGRESS WITH TEACHERS1 2 8</p>	
<p>PR12. In the last 12 months, has (name)'s school been closed on a school day due to any of the following reasons:</p> <p>[A] Natural disasters, such as flood, cyclone, epidemics or similar?</p> <p>[B] Man-made disasters, such as fire, building collapse, riots or similar?</p> <p>[C] Teacher strike?</p> <p>[X] Other?</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">YES NO DK</p> <p>NATURAL DISASTERS.....1 2 8</p> <p>MAN-MADE DISASTERS1 2 8</p> <p>TEACHER STRIKE.....1 2 8</p> <p>OTHER.....1 2 8</p>	
<p>PR13. In the last 12 months, was (name) unable to attend class due to (his/her) teacher being absent?</p>	<p>YES 1</p> <p>NO 2</p> <p>DK 8</p>	
<p>PR14. Check PR12[C] and PR13: Any 'Yes' recorded?</p>	<p>YES, PR12[C]=1 OR PR13=1..... 1</p> <p>NO 2</p>	<p>2 ⇒End</p>
<p>PR15. When (teacher strike / teacher absence) happened did you or any other adult member of your household contact any school officials or school governing body representatives?</p>	<p>YES 1</p> <p>NO 2</p> <p>DK 8</p>	

FL1. Now I would like to talk to (*name*). I will ask (*him/her*) a few questions about (*himself/herself*) and about reading, and then ask (*him/her*) to complete a few reading and number activities.

These are not school tests and the results will not be shared with anyone.

You will not benefit directly from participating and I am not trained to tell you how well (*name*) has performed.

The activities are to help us find out how well children in this country are learning to read and to use numbers so that improvements can be made.

This will take about 20 minutes. Again, all the information we obtain will remain strictly confidential and anonymous.

May I talk to (<i>name</i>)?	YES, PERMISSION IS GIVEN..... 1 NO, PERMISSION IS NOT GIVEN 2	2 ⇒ FL28
--------------------------------	--	----------

FL2. Record the time.	HOURS AND MINUTES ... ___ : ___	
------------------------------	--	--

FL3. My name is (*your name*). I would like to tell you a bit about myself.

Could you tell me a little bit about yourself?

When the child is comfortable, continue with the verbal consent:

Let me tell you why I am here today. I am part of a team trying to find out how children are learning to read and to use numbers. We are also talking to some of the children about this and asking them to do some reading and number activities. (*Your mother/Name of caretaker*) has said that you can decide if you want to help us. If you wish to help us, I will ask you some questions and give you some activities to do. I will explain each activity, and you can ask me questions any time. You do not have to do anything that you do not want to do. After we begin, if you do not want to answer a question or you do not want to continue that is alright.

Are you ready to get started?	YES..... 1 NO / NOT ASKED..... 2	2 ⇒ FL28
-------------------------------	-------------------------------------	----------

FL4. Before you start with the reading and number activities, tick each box to show that:

- You are not alone with the child unless he/she is at least visible to an adult known to the child.
- You have engaged the child in conversation and built rapport, e.g. using an icebreaker.
- The child is sat comfortably, able to use the **READING & NUMBERS BOOK** without difficulty, while you can see which page is open.

FL6. First we are going to talk about reading.	YES NO	
[A] Do you read books at home?	READS BOOKS AT HOME 1 2	
[B] Does someone read to you at home?	READ TO AT HOME..... 1 2	

<p>FL7. Which language do you speak most of the time at home?</p> <p><i>Probe if necessary and read the listed languages.</i></p>	<p>READING TEST AVAILABLE GEORGIAN 11 ARMENIAN 12 AZERBAIJANI 13</p> <p>READING TEST NOT AVAILABLE RUSSIAN 21</p> <p>OTHER (<i>specify</i>) 96 DK 98</p>	
<p>FL8. Check CB7: In the current school year, did the child attend school or any early childhood education programme?</p>	<p>YES, CB7=1 1 NO, CB7=2 OR BLANK 2</p>	<p>1 ⇒FL9A</p>
<p>FL8A. Check CB4: Did the child ever attend school or any early childhood education programmes?</p>	<p>YES, CB4 =1 1 NO, CB4 =2 OR BLANK 2</p>	<p>1 ⇒FL9B 2 ⇒FL9C</p>
<p>FL9A. What language do your teachers use most of the time when teaching you in class?</p> <p>FL9B. When you were in school, what language did your teachers use most of the time when teaching you in class?</p> <p><i>Probe if necessary and read the listed languages.</i></p>	<p>READING TEST AVAILABLE GEORGIAN 11 ARMENIAN 12 AZERBAIJANI 13</p> <p>READING TEST NOT AVAILABLE RUSSIAN 21</p> <p>OTHER (<i>specify</i>) 96 DK 98</p>	<p>11 ⇒FL10A 12 ⇒FL10A 13 ⇒FL10A</p>
<p>FL9C. Check FL7: Is READING & NUMBERS BOOK available in the language spoken at home?</p>	<p>YES, FL7=11, 12 OR 13 1 NO, FL7=21, 96 OR 98 2</p>	<p>1 ⇒FL10B 2 ⇒FL10C</p>
<p>FL10A. Now I am going to give you a short story to read in (<i>Language recorded in FL9A/B</i>). Would you like to start reading the story?</p> <p>FL10B. Now I am going to give you a short story to read in (<i>Language recorded in FL7</i>). Would you like to start reading the story?</p>	<p>YES 1 NO 2</p>	<p>1 ⇒FL11</p>
<p>FL10C. I have short stories in Georgian, Armenian and Azerbaijani. The stories are almost the same. Would you like to try to read one of them?</p>	<p>GEORGIAN 11 ARMENIAN 12 AZERBAIJANI 13</p> <p>DOES NOT WANT TO TRY 95</p>	<p>95 ⇒FL23</p>
<p>FL11. Check Demographic Questionnaire HL6: Child's age?</p>	<p>AGE 7-9 YEARS 1 AGE 10-14 YEARS 2</p>	<p>1 ⇒FL13</p>
<p>FL12. Check CB7: In the current school year, did the child attend school or any early childhood education programme?</p>	<p>YES, CB7 =1 1 NO, CB7 =2 OR BLANK 2</p>	<p>1 ⇒FL18B</p>

FL13. Give the child the **READING & NUMBERS BOOK** in the language recorded for the test: Use response to **FL10C** if available. If not, use response to **FL9A/B** if available. Otherwise use response to **FL7**.

Open the page showing the reading practice item and say:

Now we are going to do some reading. *Point to the sentence.* I would like you to read this aloud. Then I may ask you a question.

(English: *Kuda is a cat. Richi is a dog. Kuda is 5. Richi is 6.*)

ქართული: *კუდა არის კატა. რიჩი ძაღლია. კუდა 5 წლისაა. რიჩი 6 წლისაა.*

Հայերեն. *Կուդան կատու է: Ռիչին շուն է: Կուդան 5 տարեկան է: Ռիչին 6 տարեկան է:*

AZƏRBAYCANCA: *Məstan pişikdir. Riçi itdir. Məstanın 5 yaşı var. Riçinin 6 yaşı var.*)

<p>FL14. Did the child read every word in the practice correctly?</p>	<p>YES 1 NO 2</p>	<p>2 ⇒FL21D</p>
<p>FL15. Once the reading is done, ask: (How old is Kuda? რამდენი წლის არის კუდა? Քանի տարեկան է Կուդան: Məstan neçə yaşındadır?)</p>	<p>CORRECT (5/ 5/ 5/ 5)..... 1 OTHER ANSWERS..... 2 NO ANSWER AFTER 5 SECONDS..... 3</p>	<p>1 ⇒FL17</p>
<p>FL16. Say: (Kuda is 5 years old. კუდა არის 5 წლის. Կուդան 5 տարեկան է: Məstan 5 yaşındadır)</p>		<p>⇒FL21D</p>
<p>FL17. Here is another question: (Who is older: Kuda or Richi? რომელია უფროსი: კუდა თუ რიჩი? Ո՞րն է ավագը՝ Կուդան թե Ռիչին: Hansı böyükdür: Məstan və ya Riçi?)</p>	<p>CORRECT (Richi/ რიჩი/ Ռիչին / Riçi) 1 OTHER ANSWERS 2 NO ANSWER AFTER 5 SECONDS..... 3</p>	<p>1 ⇒FL18A</p>
<p>FL18. Say: (Richi is older than Kuda. Richi is 6 and Kuda is 5. რიჩი კუდაზე უფროსია. რიჩი 6 წლისაა, ხოლო კუდა კი 5 წლის. Ռիչին Կուդայից մեծ է: Ռիչին 6 տարեկան է, իսկ Կուդան 5 տարեկան: Riçi Məstandan böyükdür. Riçi 6 yaşındadır, Məstan isə 5 yaşında.)</p>		<p>⇒FL21D</p>
<p>FL18A. Turn the page to reveal the reading passage. Say: Thank you. Now I want you to try this.</p>		<p>⇒FL19</p>

FL18B. Give the child the *READING & NUMBERS BOOK* in the language recorded for the test: Use response to *FL10C* if available. If not, use response to *FL9A/B* if available. Otherwise use response to *FL7*.

Open the book on the page of the reading passage.

<p>FL19. Here is a story. I want you to read it aloud as carefully as you can.</p> <p>You will start here (point to the first word on the first line) and you will read line by line (point to the direction for reading each line).</p> <p>When you finish, I will ask you some questions about what you have read.</p> <p>If you come to a word you do not know, go on to the next word.</p> <p>Put your finger on the first word. Ready? Begin.</p>	დაჩი	მეორე	კლასში ა.	ერთ	დღეს	დაჩი	სკოლი დან
	ჩაქინ	ერկრიორ	ჩასარ ანო მ	ქ:	ში	ორ	ჩაქინ
	Daçi	ikinci	sinifdädi r.	Bir	gün,	Daçi	məktəbd ən
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
	სახლში	მიდიოდ ა.	გზად	მან	წითელ ო	ყვავილე ბი	დაინახა .
	ჩაქინი	თონ	ქ	გნოა:	ჯანააყ არჩინ	ნა	მი
	evə	qayırdı.	Yolda,	o	bir	neçə	qırmızı
	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
	ყვავილ ები	პომიდვ რის	ბოსტან თან	ახლოს	იყო.	დაჩის	მოუნდა ,
	ქანი	კარმიქ	ბაქინ	თხააქ:	ბაქინ ქ	ქინი	აქარა ქ
	gül	gördü.	Güller	pomidor	fermasını n	yanında	idi.
	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
	რომ	დედის თვის	რამდენ იმე	ყვავილ ო	წელი.	დაჩი	ბოსტნი ს
	მთ	ქინ:	ჩაქინ	განსკა გაქ	მაქინ ქ	ჩამარ	მი
	Daçi	istədi	ki,	anası	üçün	bir	neçə
	22	23	24	25	26	27	28
	გავლი თ	ყვავილე ბის	დასაკრ ეჯად	გაქეა.	ის	ვამლის	ხესთან
	ქანი	ბაქინ	თანსქ:	ჩაქინ	ბაქინ ქ	ქარქი	ჩამარ
	gül	aparsın.	Daçi	gülləri	dərmək	üçün	dərhal
	29	30	31	32	33	34	35
	წაქეა.	დაჩიმ	ტირილ ო	დაიწყო .	გლებმა	ის	დაინახა
ჩეაქ	გქექექ	აქარა ქ	ქაქე:	სა	ქინი	ბაქინ	
fermaya	qaçdı.	O,	alma	ağacının	yanında	yıxıldı.	
36	37	38	39	40	41	42	
და	მასთან	მივიდა .	მან	დაჩის	ბერი	ყვავილ ო	
მთ	ქინაქ:	ჩაქინ	ქ	ქინ	სქე:	ქინი ქ	
Daçi	ağlamağa	başladı.	Fermer	onu	gördü	və	

43	44	45	46	47	48	49
აჩუქა.	დაზი	ძაღიან	ბედნიე რი	იყო.		
նրան	տեսավ	ու	մոտեց ավ:	Նա	Դաչիին	շատ
ona	yaxınlaşd ı.	O,	Daçiyə	çoxlu	güllər	bağışladı .
50	51	52	53	54	55	56
ծաղիկն եր	նվիրեց:	Դաչին	շատ	երջանի կ	եր:	
Daçi	çox	xoşbəxt	idi.			
57	58	59	60	61	62	63

<p>FL20. <i>Results of the child's reading.</i></p> <p><i>Incorrect or missed words (B) are those marked incorrect while reading plus the difference between the number of the last word in the story (ქართული: 54 / Հայերեն՝ 62 / AZƏRBAYCANCA: 60) and the last word attempted (A).</i></p> <p><i>If the child did not try to read the story, record '00' as the last word attempted (A).</i></p>	<p>LAST WORD ATTEMPTED (A).....NUMBER ___</p> <p>TOTAL NUMBER OF WORDS INCORRECT OR MISSED (B).....NUMBER ___</p>	
<p>FL21A. <i>Check FL20(B): Did the child incorrectly read or miss (Georgian:6/ Armenian:7/ Azerbaijani:7) or more words?</i></p>	<p>YES, AT LEAST (GEORGIAN:6/ ARMENIAN:7/ AZERBAIJANI:7) INCORRECT WORDS.....1</p> <p>NO, LESS THAN (GEORGIAN:6/ ARMENIAN:7/ AZERBAIJANI:7) INCORRECT WORDS.....2</p>	<p>1 ⇨ FL21D</p>
<p>FL21B. <i>Now I am going to ask you a few questions about what you have read.</i></p> <p><i>If the child does not provide a response after a few seconds, repeat the question. If the child seems unable to provide an answer after repeating the question, mark 'No response' and say: Thank you. That is ok. We will move on.</i></p> <p><i>Make sure the child can still see the passage and ask:</i></p>		

<p>[A] (What class is Dachı in?/ რომელ კლასშია დაჩი?/ Ո՞ր դասարանում է Դաչին:/ Daçi neçenci sinifdədir?)</p>	<p>CORRECT (TWO/ მეორე/ Երկրորդ / İKİNCİ).....1 INCORRECT2 NO RESPONSE / SAYS ‘I DON’T KNOW’ 3</p>
<p>[B] (What did Dachı see on the way home?/ რა დაინახა დაჩიმ სახლის გზაზე?/ Ի՞նչ տեսավ Դաչին տան ճանապարհին:/ Daçi evə gedən yolda nə gördü?)</p>	<p>CORRECT (FLOWERS/ ყვავილები/ ծաղիկներ / GÜLLƏR).....1 INCORRECT2 NO RESPONSE / SAYS ‘I DON’T KNOW’ 3</p>
<p>[C] (Why did Dachı start crying?/ რატომ დაიწყო დაჩიმ ტირილი?/ Ինչո՞ւ սկսեց Դաչին լաց լինել:/ Nə üçün Daçi ağlamağa başladı?)</p>	<p>CORRECT (BECAUSE HE FELL/ იმიტომ, რომ დაეცა / որովհետև ընկավ / ÇÜNKİ YIXILDI)1 INCORRECT2 NO RESPONSE / SAYS ‘I DON’T KNOW’ 3</p>
<p>[D] (Where did Dachı fall?/ სად დაეცა დაჩი?/ Որտե՞ր ընկավ Դաչին:/ Daçi harada yixildi?)</p>	<p>CORRECT (NEAR A APPLE TREE/ ვამლოს ხესთან ახლოს / խնձորի ծառի մոտ / ALMA AĞACININ YAXINLIĞINDA) ..1 INCORRECT2 NO RESPONSE / SAYS ‘I DON’T KNOW’ 3</p>
<p>[E] (Why was Dachı happy?/ რატომ იყო დაჩი ბედნიერი?/ Ինչո՞ւ էր Դաչին երջանիկ:/ Nə üçün Daçi xoşbəxt idi?)</p>	<p>CORRECT (BECAUSE THE FARMER GAVE HIM MANY FLOWERS OR BECAUSE HE HAD FLOWERS TO GIVE TO HIS MOTHER/ იმიტომ, რომ გლეხმა მას ბევრი ყვავილი აჩუქა, ან იმიტომ, რომ მას ჰქონდა დედასთვის მისატანი ყვავილები/ ՈՐՈՎՉԵՏԵՆ, ԱԳԱՐԱԿԱՏԵՐԸ ՆՐԱՆ ՇԱՏ ԾԱՂԻԿՆԵՐ ՆՎԻՐԵՑ, ԿԱՄ ՈՐՈՎՉԵՏԵՆ ՆԱ ՄՈՐ ՀԱՄԱՐ ՏԱՆԵԼՈՒ ԾԱՂԻԿՆԵՐ ՈՒՆԵՐ / ÇÜNKİ FERMER ONA ÇOXLU GÜLLƏR BAĞIŞLADI VƏ YA ÇÜNKİ ANASINA GÜLLƏR APARACAQDI) ...1 INCORRECT2 NO RESPONSE / SAYS ‘I DON’T KNOW’ 3</p>

FL21C. Check FL21B[A-E]: Did the child answer all questions correctly?	YES, ALL FL21B[A-E]=11 NO, AT LEAST ONE FL21B[A-E]=2 OR 3.2	1 ⇨FL23
FL21D. I have another story in (<i>list languages not yet attempted</i>). Would you like to try to read one of them? <i>The child cannot pick the same language as already attempted.</i>	GEORGIAN11 ARMENIAN.....12 AZERBAIJANI13 DOES NOT WANT TO TRY95	95 ⇨FL23
FL21E. Check HL6: Child's age?	AGE 7-9 YEARS.....1 AGE 10-14 YEARS.....2	1 ⇨FL21G
FL21F. Check CB7: In the current school year, did the child attend school or any early childhood education programme?	YES, CB7=11 NO, CB7 =2 OR BLANK.....2	1 ⇨FL21N
<p>FL21G. Give the child the READING & NUMBERS BOOK in the language recorded in FL21D.</p> <p>Open the page showing the reading practice item, point to the sentence and say: Just as before I would like you to read this aloud. Then I may ask you a question.</p> <p>(English: <i>Niko is a boy. Anne is a girl. Niko has 2 eggs. Anne has 3 eggs.</i> (ქართული: <i>ნიკო ბიჭია. ანა გოგონა. ნიკოს აქვს 2 კვერცხი. ანას აქვს 3 კვერცხი./</i> Հայերեն՝ <i>Նիկոն տղա է: Աննան աղջիկ է: Նիկոն 2 ձու ունի: Աննան 3 ձու ունի:/</i> AZƏRBAYCANCA: <i>Niko oğlandır, Anna qızdır. Nikonun 2 yumurtası var. Annanın 3 yumurtası var.</i></p>		
FL21H. Did the child read every word in the practice correctly?	YES.....1 NO2	2 ⇨FL23
FL21I. Once the reading is done, ask: (How many eggs does Niko have?/ რამდენი კვერცხი აქვს ნიკოს?/ Քանի՞ ձու ունի Նիկոն?/ Nikonun neçə yumurtası var?)	CORRECT (2/ 2/ 2/ 2).....1 OTHER ANSWERS2 NO ANSWER AFTER 5 SECONDS3	1 ⇨FL21K
FL21J. Say: (John has 2 eggs./ ნიკოს აქვს 2 კვერცხი./ Նիկոն ունի 2 ձու:/ Nikonun 2 yumurtası var.)		⇨FL23

<p>FL21K. Here is another question: (Who has more eggs: Niko or Anne?/ ვის უფრო მეტი კვერცხი აქვს: ნიკოს თუ ანას?/ Ո՞վ ավելի շատ ձու ունի՝ Նիկոն թե Աննան:/ Kimin daha çox yumurtası var: Nikonun və ya Annanın?)</p>	<p>CORRECT (ANNE/ ანას/ ԱՆՆԱՆ / ANNANIN)1 OTHER ANSWERS2 NO ANSWER AFTER 5 SECONDS3</p>	<p>1 ⇒FL21M</p>
<p>FL21L. Say: (Anne has more eggs than Niko. Anne has 3 eggs and Niko has 2./ ანას უფრო მეტი კვერცხი აქვს, ვიდრე ნიკოს. ანას აქვს 3 კვერცხი, ხოლო ნიკოს კი 2./ Աննան ավելի շատ ձու ունի, քան Նիկոն: Աննան ունի 3 ձու, իսկ Նիկոն՝ 2:/ Annanın daha çox yumurtası var, nəinki Nikonun. Annanın 3 yumurtası var, Nikonun isə 2.)</p>		<p>⇒FL23</p>
<p>FL21M. Turn the page to reveal the reading passage. Say: Thank you. Now I want you to try this.</p>		<p>⇒FL21O</p>
<p>FL21N. Give the child the <i>READING & NUMBERS BOOK</i> in the language recorded in FL21D. <i>Open the book on the page of the reading passage.</i></p>		

<p>FL210. Here is a story. I want you to read it aloud as carefully as you can.</p> <p>You will start here (point to the first word on the first line) and you will read line by line (point to the direction for reading each line).</p> <p>When you finish, I will ask you some questions about what you have read.</p> <p>If you come to a word you do not know, go on to the next word.</p> <p>Put your finger on the first word. Ready? Begin.</p>	მარიამი	შვიდი	წლისაა.	ერთ	დილას,	ბებია	ის
	სარქაა ლ	იუ	თარქა ს	է:	Մի	ստապուտ	տատիկը
	Məryəm	yeddi	yaşındadı r.	Bir	səhər,	nənəsi	Onu
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
	მღაზია ში	სტაფილ ოს	საციდლა დ	გაუმვა.	მან	მარიამს	ფული
	სრას	խანოქ	ილაქს გ	ს	գազար	գնել	խնդրեց:
	mağazaya	göndərdi	və	yerkökü	almağy	xahiş	etdi.
	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
	მისცა.	მარიამმა	ის	ჩანთაში	ჩაიღო.	ჩანთა	გახეული
	სა	სარქაა ჩს	ქილ	თქვ:	სარქაა ლ	აქს	ყაქოსა სქ
	ო,	Məryəmə	pul	verdi.	Məryəm	pulu	çantasına
	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
	იყო.	გზაში	მარიამს	ფული	დაეკარგ ა.	პეტრემ	ფული
	მე	ქვ:	ღაქოსა სქ	მავქაბ	ქ:	ჯანაყ არქის	სარქაა ლ
qoydu.	Çanta	sökülmüş	idi.	Yolda	Məryəm	pulu	
22	23	24	25	26	27	28	
იბოვა	და	მარიამს	დაუბრუ ნა.	მარიამი	გახარებ ული	იყო.	
ქილ	სიქვქვ:	ღესქენს	გთაქ	ქილ	ს	აქს	
itirdi.	Petre	pulu	tapdı	və	onu	Məryəmə	
29	30	31	32	33	34	35	
მან	პეტრეს	მადლობ ა	გადაუბა და	და	მღაზი საკენ	წავიდა.	
სარქაა ჩს	ქსრაქა რქვ:	სარქაა ლ	ილაქს	ქ:	სარქაა ლ	ღესქენს	
qaytardı.	Məryəm	çox	sevindi.	Məryəm	Petreyə	təşəkkür	
36	37	38	39	40	41	42	
ჯიქრქას სიქქონს	ხაქსნქვ	ს	ქსაქ	ქანოქ ლ	გსაგ:		
Etdi	və	mağazaya	getdi.				
43	44	45	46	47	48	49	

<p>FL21P. <i>Results of the child's reading.</i></p> <p><i>Incorrect or missed words (B) are those marked incorrect while reading plus the difference between the number of the last word in the story (ქართული: 42 / Հայերեն` 48 / AZƏRBAYCANCA:46) and the last word attempted (A).</i></p> <p><i>If the child did not try to read the story, record '00' as the last word attempted (A).</i></p>	<p>LAST WORD ATTEMPTED (A).....NUMBER __ __</p> <p>TOTAL NUMBER OF WORDS INCORRECT OR MISSED (B).....NUMBER __ __</p>	
<p>FL21Q. <i>Check FL21P(B): Did the child incorrectly read or miss (Georgian:5/ Armenian:5/ Azerbaijani:5) or more words?</i></p>	<p>YES, AT LEAST (GEORGIAN:5/ ARMENIAN:5/ AZERBAIJANI:5) INCORRECT WORDS1</p> <p>NO, LESS THAN (GEORGIAN:5/ ARMENIAN:5/ AZERBAIJANI:5) INCORRECT WORDS2</p>	<p>1 ⇒FL23</p>
<p>FL22. Now I am going to ask you a few questions about what you have read.</p> <p><i>If the child does not provide a response after a few seconds, repeat the question. If the child seems unable to provide an answer after repeating the question, mark 'No response' and say: Thank you. That is ok. We will move on.</i></p> <p><i>Make sure the child can still see the passage and ask:</i></p> <p>[A] (How old is Mary?/ (რამდენი წლის არის მარიამი?/ Քանի՞ տարեկան է Մարիամը:/ Məryəm neçə yaşındadır?)</p> <p>[B] (Who sent Mary to the market?/ (ვინ გააგზავნა მარიამი მაღაზიაში?/ Ո՞վ ուղարկեց Մարիամին խանութ:/ Məryəmi mağazaya kim göndərdi?)</p>	<p>CORRECT (7/ 7/ 7/ 7).....1</p> <p>INCORRECT.....2</p> <p>NO RESPONSE / SAYS 'I DON'T KNOW'3</p> <p>CORRECT (HER GRANDMOTHER/ (მისმა ბებიაშ/ ՆՐԱ ՏՄՏԻԿԸ / ONUN NƏNƏSİ).....1</p> <p>INCORRECT.....2</p> <p>NO RESPONSE / SAYS 'I DON'T KNOW'3</p>	

<p>[C] (What was Mary asked to buy?/ (რისი ყიდვა სთხოვეს მარიამს?/ Ի՞նչ խնդրեցին գնել Մարիամին:/ Məryəmdən nəyi almağı xahiş etdilər?)</p>	<p>CORRECT (CARROTS/ (სტაფილოს/ ԳԱԶԱՐԻ / YERKÖKÜ)1 INCORRECT.....2 NO RESPONSE / SAYS ‘I DON’T KNOW’3</p>
<p>[D] (Why did Mary lose the money?/ (რატომ დაეკარგა მარიამს ფული?/ Ինչ՞ու կորցրեց Մարիամը փողը:/ Nə üçün Məryəm pulunu itirdi?)</p>	<p>CORRECT (BECAUSE IT FELL THROUGH THE HOLE IN THE BAG OR BECAUSE THE BAG HAD A HOLE/ (იმიტომ, რომ ჩანთა გახეული იყო/ ՈՐՈՎՅԵՏՆ ԴԱՅՈՒՍԱԿԸ ՄԱՇՎԱԾ ԷՐ / ÇÜNKİ ÇANTASI SÖKÜLMÜŞDÜ)1 INCORRECT.....2 NO RESPONSE / SAYS ‘I DON’T KNOW’3</p>
<p>[E] (Why was Mary happy?/ (რატომ იყო მარიამი გახარებული?/ Ինչ՞ու էր Մարիամը ուրախացել:/ Məryəm nə üçün sevinirdi?)</p>	<p>CORRECT (BECAUSE PETER GAVE HER THE MONEY OR BECAUSE PETER FOUND THE MONEY/ (იმიტომ, რომ პეტრემ მას ფული დაუბრუნა ან იმიტომ, რომ პეტრემ ფული იპოვა / ՈՐՈՎՅԵՏՆ ԴԵՏՐԵՆ ՆՐԱՆ ՎԵՐԱԴԱՐՁՐԵԼ ԷՐ ԴՐԱՍԸ ԿԱՄ, ՈՐՈՎՅԵՏՆ ԴԵՏՐԵՆ ԴՐԱՍԸ ՊՏԵԼ ԷՐ / ÇÜNKİ PETRE ONA PULU QAYTARDI VƏ YA ÇÜNKİ PETRE ONUN PULUNU TAPDI) ..1 INCORRECT.....2 NO RESPONSE / SAYS ‘I DON’T KNOW’3</p>

<p>FL23. Turn the page in the <i>READING & NUMBERS BOOK</i> so the child is looking at the list of numbers. Make sure the child is looking at this page.</p> <p>Now here are some numbers. I want you to point to each number and tell me what the number is.</p> <p><i>Point to the first number and say:</i> Start here.</p> <p><i>If the child stops on a number for a while, tell the child what the number is, record '3', No attempt, point to the next number and say:</i> What is this number?</p> <p><i>If the child does not attempt 2 consecutive numbers, record '3', No attempt, for remaining numbers and say:</i> Thank you. That is ok.</p>	<p>9 CORRECT1 INCORRECT2 NO ATTEMPT3</p> <p>12 CORRECT1 INCORRECT2 NO ATTEMPT3</p> <p>30 CORRECT1 INCORRECT2 NO ATTEMPT3</p> <p>48 CORRECT1 INCORRECT2 NO ATTEMPT3</p> <p>74 CORRECT1 INCORRECT2 NO ATTEMPT3</p> <p>731 CORRECT1 INCORRECT2 NO ATTEMPT3</p>	
<p>FL23A. Check FL23: Did the child correctly identify two of the first three numbers (9, 12 and 30)?</p>	<p>YES, AT LEAST TWO CORRECT1 NO, AT LEAST 2 INCORRECT OR WITH NO ATTEMPT2</p>	<p>2 ⇒ FL27A</p>

<p>FL24. Turn the page so the child is looking at the first pair of numbers. Make sure the child is looking at this page. Say:</p> <p>Look at these numbers. Tell me which one is bigger.</p> <p><i>Record the child's answer before turning the page in the book and repeating the question for the next pair of numbers.</i></p> <p><i>If the child does not provide a response after a few seconds, repeat the question. If the child seems unable to provide an answer after repeating the question, record '3', No attempt, for the appropriate pair of numbers, turn the booklet page and show the child the next pair of numbers.</i></p> <p><i>If the child does not attempt 2 consecutive pairs, record '3', No attempt, for remaining pairs and say:</i></p> <p>Thank you. That is ok. We will go to the next activity.</p>	<p>7 & 5 CORRECT (7)1 INCORRECT.....2 NO ATTEMPT3</p> <p>11 & 24 CORRECT (24)1 INCORRECT.....2 NO ATTEMPT3</p> <p>58 & 49 CORRECT (58)1 INCORRECT.....2 NO ATTEMPT3</p> <p>65 & 67 CORRECT (67)1 INCORRECT.....2 NO ATTEMPT3</p> <p>146 & 154 CORRECT (154)1 INCORRECT.....2 NO ATTEMPT3</p>	
--	--	--

<p>FL25. Give the child a pencil and paper. Turn the page so the child is looking at the first addition. Make sure the child is looking at this page. Say:</p> <p>Look at this sum. How much is (number plus number)? Tell me the answer. You can use the pencil and paper if it helps you.</p> <p>Record the child's answer before turning the page in the book and repeating the question for the next sum.</p> <p>If the child does not provide a response after a few seconds, repeat the question. If the child seems unable to provide an answer after repeating the question, record '3', No attempt, for the appropriate sum, turn the booklet page and show the child the next addition.</p> <p>If the child does not attempt 2 consecutive sums, record '3', No attempt, for remaining sums and say:</p> <p>Thank you. That is ok. We will go to the next activity.</p>	<p>3 + 2 CORRECT (5)1 INCORRECT.....2 NO ATTEMPT3</p> <p>8 + 6 CORRECT (14)1 INCORRECT.....2 NO ATTEMPT3</p> <p>7 + 3 CORRECT (10)1 INCORRECT.....2 NO ATTEMPT3</p> <p>13 + 6 CORRECT (19)1 INCORRECT.....2 NO ATTEMPT3</p> <p>12 + 24 CORRECT (36)1 INCORRECT.....2 NO ATTEMPT3</p>	
<p>FL26. Turn to the first practice sheet for pattern recognition. Say:</p> <p>Here are some numbers. 1, 2, __, and 4.</p> <p>Point to each number and blank space and say:</p> <p>What number goes here?</p>	<p>CORRECT (3)1 INCORRECT.....2 NO ATTEMPT3</p>	<p>2 ⇒FL26B 3 ⇒FL26B</p>
<p>FL26A. That's correct, 3. Let's do another one.</p>		<p>⇒FL26C</p>
<p>FL26B. Do not explain how to get the correct answer. Just say:</p> <p>The number 3 goes here. Say the numbers with me. (Point to each number) 1, 2, 3, 4. 3 goes here. Let's do another one.</p>		

<p>FL26C. Here are some more numbers. 5, 10, 15 and __.</p> <p><i>Point to each number and blank space and say:</i></p> <p>What number goes here?</p>	<p>CORRECT (20)1 INCORRECT.....2 NO ATTEMPT3</p>	<p>2 ⇒FL26E 3 ⇒FL26E</p>
<p>FL26D. That’s correct, 20.</p>		<p>⇒FL27</p>
<p>FL26E. <i>Do not explain how to get the correct answer. Just say:</i></p> <p>The number 20 goes here. Say the numbers with me. (<i>Point to each number</i>) 5, 10, 15, 20. 20 goes here.</p>		
<p>FL26F. <i>Check FL26: Was the answer correct?</i></p>	<p>YES, FL26=1.....1 NO, FL26=2 OR 3.....2</p>	<p>2 ⇒FL27A</p>
<p>FL27. Now I want you to try this on your own.</p> <p>Here are some more numbers. Tell me what number goes here (<i>pointing to the missing number</i>).</p> <p><i>Record the child’s answer before turning the page in the book and repeating the question.</i></p> <p><i>If the child does not provide a response after a few seconds, repeat the question. If the child seems unable to provide an answer after repeating the question, record ‘3’, No attempt, for the appropriate question, turn the page and show the child the next question.</i></p> <p><i>If the child does not attempt 2 consecutive patterns, record ‘3’, No attempt, for remaining patterns. and say:</i></p> <p>Thank you. That is ok.</p>	<p>5, 6, 7, __ CORRECT (8)1 INCORRECT.....2 NO ATTEMPT3</p> <p>14, 15, __, 17 CORRECT (16)1 INCORRECT.....2 NO ATTEMPT3</p> <p>20, __, 40, 50 CORRECT (30)1 INCORRECT.....2 NO ATTEMPT3</p> <p>2, 4, 6, __ CORRECT (8)1 INCORRECT.....2 NO ATTEMPT3</p> <p>5, 8, 11, __ CORRECT (14)1 INCORRECT.....2 NO ATTEMPT3</p>	

<p>FL27A. That was my last question. I really enjoyed talking to you. It was very nice of you to help us out. Thank you very much.</p> <p><i>If you are asked by the child or the mother/caretaker how well the child has done, praise the child for effort but do not comment on performance.</i></p> <p><i>You may say:</i></p> <p>I am not trained to tell you how (you have/your child has) performed but (your/his/her) participation will help the authorities understand how much children are learning in Georgia.</p>		
---	--	--

<p>FL28. <i>Result of interview with child.</i></p> <p><i>Discuss any result not completed with Supervisor.</i></p>	<p>COMPLETED..... 01</p> <p>NOT AT HOME 02</p> <p>MOTHER / CARETAKER REFUSED 03</p> <p>CHILD REFUSED..... 04</p> <p>OTHER (<i>specify</i>)..... 96</p>	
--	--	--

<p>FS11. <i>Record the time.</i></p>	<p>HOURS AND MINUTES __ : __</p>	
<p>FS16. <i>Thank the respondent for her/his cooperation.</i></p> <p><i>Make arrangements for the administration of the remaining questionnaire(s) in this household.</i></p>		

INTERVIEWER'S OBSERVATIONS

SUPERVISOR'S OBSERVATIONS

Kuda is a cat. Richi is a dog. Kuda is 5. Richi is 6.

Ⓟ

Dachi is in class two. One day, Dachi was going home from school. He saw some red flowers on the way. The flowers were near a tomato farm. Dachi wanted to get some flowers for his mother. Dachi ran fast across the farm to get the flowers. He fell down near an apple tree. Dachi started crying. The farmer saw him and came. He gave Dachi many flowers. Dachi was very happy.

Niko is a boy. Anne is a girl. Niko has 2 eggs.
Anne has 3 eggs.

Mary is seven years old. One morning, her grandmother sent her to the market to buy carrots. She gave Mary some money. Mary put it in her bag. The bag had a big hole. On the way, Mary lost the money. Peter saw the money and gave it to Mary. She was happy. Mary thanked Peter and walked to the market.

9

12

30

48

74

731

7

5

11

24

58

49

65

67

146

154

$$3 + 2 =$$

$$8 + 6 =$$

$$7 + 3 =$$

$$13 + 6 =$$

$$12 + 24 =$$

1 2 — 4

Ⓟ

5 10 15 —

Ⓟ

5 6 7 —

14 15 — 17

20 — 40 50

2 4 6 —

5

8

11

—

Survey on Functioning and Foundational Learning Skills of Children Living in Georgian Households

Refusal Sheet

Please, fill only one refusal sheet for each cluster

Cluster number _____ Supervisor's code _____ Interviewer's code _____

Refusal sheet – should be filled out if after three visits the interview was not conducted (i.e., was not filled out “Demographic questionnaire” and consequently the “Main Questionnaire”) in the household (column 3) or “Main questionnaire” was not filled out. *To the interviewer: if column 3 is filled, do not fill column 4, and vice versa. If the house is locked for a long period of time, try to find out from their neighbors whether household is gone for a period of less or more than a year.*

#	Household Code	The reasons of not conducting the interview <i>(None of the questionnaires were filled, was not filled out “Demographic questionnaire” and consequently the “Main Questionnaire”)</i>	The reasons for not filling the main questionnaire <i>(Household and Main questionnaires were not completed)</i>	Respondent's code
1	2	3	4	5
1				
2				
3				
4				
5				
6				
7				
8				
9				
10				
11				
12				
13				
14				
15				
16				
17				
18				
19				
20				
21				
22				
23				
24				

The reasons for not conducting the interview (column 3):

Dwelling is inhabited, but:

1. Refused to be interviewed;
2. Nobody was at home;
3. Temporarily absent (for a few weeks, or seasonally) to other region of Georgia;
4. Temporarily absent (for a few weeks, months or seasons) abroad;
5. Other reason (Indicate in the corresponding row);

No one lives at the address:

6. Residents have moved to another place, another region of Georgia
7. Residents have moved to live abroad;
8. Resident(s) died;
9. Other reason (Indicate in the corresponding row);

The address is not (no longer) residential:

1. A non-existent address;
2. Flat (House) has been destroyed or damaged and is not used for living;
3. Flat (House) is not being used for living (converted to other type of facility);
4. Other reason (Indicate in the corresponding row);

The reasons for not filling the “Main Questionnaire” (column 4):

1. All household members failed to pass the filter questions (Do not fill column 5);
2. Household member(s) passed the filter questions, but the respondent was not at home;
3. Household member(s) passed the filter questions, but the respondent refused to answer.

Publishing House “UNIVERSAL”

4, A. Politkovskaia st., 0186, Tbilisi, Georgia ☎: 5(99) 33 52 02, 5(99) 17 22 30
E-mail: gamomcemlobauniversali@gmail.com; universal505@ymail.com

